

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	--	--

A follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia

Nobel Nominee Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia

engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au)

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Keynote

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) is asking for legal costs and legal support from Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is requesting to ensure personal safety, earning safety, professional safety, salary/stipend (chief professor/senior professor category), investigation of killing conspiracy, and ‘compensation award’ of 83,90,000 Australian penalty units (230,72,50,000AUD) (M. A. Hossain, 2023f, 2023g; M. A. Hossain, 2023c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x; Hossain, 2025f). To eliminate the life-threatening conspiracy against Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, to eliminate international criminals/Australian criminals in Australia and Bangladesh; Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should have the right to access the legal aid fund/welfare fund/research fund of Australia and/or Bangladesh and/or United Nations (UN); without which the country policy is failing, without which the policy of UN is disrupting. Every president/prime minister should be liable to ensure the safety against international criminals. Every president/prime minister should be accountable to ensure the living and food support of the professor/researcher. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should have right to ask life safety and earning safety to the prime minister of Australia and UN. The research and development department of high court of every country should/may extend/recommend their judicial support and scrutiny this assessment for the support of Australian court and/or international court. Therefore, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is approaching zero-crime approach for global peace and peace survival. This message is being requested and circulated to the countries

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

to the presidents of the nations of the UN. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is approaching to the whole president community to fight and invest for the protection against international criminal. This report has cited the repeated slogans of messages of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain to satisfy the individual person/administration/government/profession/court/parliament/authority. This is a performance report of ministerial cabinet of Australia and Bangladesh. In this report of legal notice, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) approached and asked 'compensation awards' of 29,00,000 Australian penalty units from the administration of public service of Australia, Bangladesh, and UN. This study was continued and reported since 2021-2022(M. A. Hossain, 2023f). Prime minister of Australia took and assessed a lot of time for the support to victim which may disturb the court assessment process in Australia and/or international court. The intensity of negligence and delaying of assessment of life-threatening conspiracy to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is increasing and increasing which is tending to the example against peace surviving. Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia should take the full liability and full accountability for the support to victim against international/Australian criminal/offender/culprit. This report has contributions in public administration, public service, and law implementation for the peace practice and peace survival in the planet.

Proposal of legal act and/or outcomes of the crime analysis (M. A. Hossain, 2023f)

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) is proposing a victim-friendly legal act of every government.

- ✓ Every PhD scholar in Australia should get a free-of-cost legal support in Australian court and/or international court (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024b; Hossain, 2025g).
- ✓ Every victim should have a legal right/human right to get/access a legal aid/welfare fund/research fund of any country/Australia/United Nations (UN) under the special circumstances (M. A. Hossain, 2023f).
- ✓ Every country/Australia should have a free-of-cost education court/student court to minimize the crime in higher education in university (M. A. Hossain, 2023c; Hossain, 2025f).
- ✓ Every PhD scholar in Australia should have access support of free-of-cost education court/student court to minimize the crime in higher education in university (M. A. Hossain, 2023c).
- ✓ Every office of prime minister, president, chancellor, high commissioner, secretary of any country should be officially liable for a letter of client for a letter of citizen for a letter of

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
 Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*}
 Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
 MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process,
 color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁸
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
 PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg
 & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam);
 Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
 Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
 Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
 University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and
 Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

response to ensure appropriate action and support if a prime minister/president/chief advisor/chancellor/high commissioner/secretary is a chief executive officer of the office of prime minister/president without which the genuine purpose/respect/responsibility of the top designated office/officer may be invalid (M. A. Hossain, 2023bw; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k).

- ✓ Every office of UN and/or secretary general should be liable for a letter of client for a letter from the citizen for a letter of response/action without which the genuine purpose/respect/responsibility of the top designated office/officer may be invalid (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024i; Hossain, 2025g).
- ✓ Every office of human rights commission/legal aid office/humanitarian support centre should be liable for a letter of client for a letter of citizen for a letter of response/action without which the genuine purpose/respect/responsibility of the top designated office/officer may be invalid.
- ✓ Every chief executive category personnel should pay 1,00,000 Australian penalty units for the intentional negligence of the government duty for the intentional negligence of the public service (M. A. Hossain, 2023bw; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k; Hossain, 2025d).
- ✓ Every bomb/weapon production unit should be disposed and/or remarked by the UN. The explosive device should only be used for the criminal protection for the right peace of human survival, but the production unit should be affiliated by the UN to minimize international offences. Every bombing violence/action should be peer reviewed by the professor community and/or relevant experts without which the UN membership of the relevant countries should be cancelled immediately and immediately for the peace surviving (M. A. Hossain, 2023bu).
- ✓ If any country has any connection with the international criminal, if any country is run by international criminal, the country should/may be controlled/monitored by the UN. Every country should have equal liability for zero-crime approach for peace surviving in the planet.
- ✓ Every national court/high court should have a branch of international court and/or relevant support.
- ✓ Nobody should cease the ethical weapon of any person. Nobody should tend/conspire to cease the ethical weapon of any person. No country/organization should cease the ethical weapon of any person. No country/organization should tend/conspire to cease the ethical

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

weapon of any person. The intentional offence/conspiracy/administrative force should be punishable of 1,00,000 Australian penalty units.

- ✓ Every member of ministerial cabinet/ministry/organization of the citizen/country/UN should be 100% liable to serve the citizen should be 100% dedicate to serve the citizen. No person should deny the responsibility and accountability due to their high rank of designation due to their high-power of designation. The intentional offence should be punishable of 1,00,000 Australian penalty units.
- ✓ Every high court bench should have a lawyer of research and development to satisfy the right service of plaintiff and defender to eliminate the side-effect of the court system, and law implementation. Such as: human influence, political influence, financial influence, sex influence, threat influence, attitude of the person, prestige/ego of justice/lawyer, lack of understanding capability/knowledge of lawyer/justice, wrong/limitation of legal acts, lack of one dimensional concentration of judge/lawyer, mistake in writing/hearing/recommendation/approach, artificial/natural afraid symptom/disorder of human brain, biological decision versus human brain versus human psychology, and relevant facts (Hossain, 2025a, 2025b).

Keywords

Life-threatening conspiracy, legal costs, legal notice, public service, citizen, Australian penalty units, compensation award, PhD scholar, Nobel nominee, RMIT, Australia, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain.

1 Letter of proceeding to Mr. Anthony Albanese, MP, Prime Minister of Australia from the office of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.); RMIT University, Australia (M. A. Hossain, 2023bw)

Date: 27 September 2025

Mr. Anthony Albanese, MP

Prime Minister

Parliament house

Canberra act 2600

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	---	--

Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia (M. A. Hossain, 2023bw).

Dear Mr. Anthony Albanese,

Your honour for the peace of mankind

Your honour for the peace of Australian PhD schooling at RMIT

2 Introduction

Every prime minister, minister, president, justice, secretary general, and relevant government officer should pay reasonable penalty unit if the citizen is also paying the penalty unit without which the power is winning without which the government force is winning without which the political leader is winning and forcing the citizen without which the practice of the government service is showing and displaying only, but the democracy is failing and failing, but the ethical practice is failing and failing, but the right surviving practice in the planet is failing and failing, but the right practice of a country is failing and failing, but the right practice of United Nations (UN) is failing and failing (Hossain, 2025a). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) is approaching zero-crime practice for the global surviving. Every chief executive officer (CEO) should have a study desk should have a reading room to respond/understand the service/letter of his/her office. A secretary may be a supportive person of a chief executive office, but a secretary is not a CEO of an office, but the CEO is not a secretary of the office, but a CEO should not 100% depend on his/her secretaries. Every prime minister/president/CEO is also a separate person rather than his/her secretaries/board of secretaries/board of ministries/board of parliament members. In general, prime minister/president is a more honorable person/designation is a more respected person than a minister. So, the responsibility, accountability, and understanding capability should also be higher and superior than a minister and/or a general citizen. So, a prime minister or a president should be the chief higher quality person of the country should be a chief higher ethical person of the country should be a chief confidential person of the country should have a chief directorial/chief commanding attitude of the country. Every country can purchase weapons of millions and billions of dollars. Every country has money and money to purchase bullets, fighting aircraft, and expensive aircraft. Every

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia
Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

country has a tendency to force the citizen of the country. Where are the human rights? Where is the human right of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) in Australia? What is the function of human rights commission in Australia and Bangladesh if the commission is taking salary/benefit from the countries? Where is the legal right of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) in Australia? Zero money of a PhD scholar in Australia = zero legal support in Australia. This is the symptom of global threat to the PhD scholar to the researcher to the scientist to the professor. Legal rights and human rights are crying and crying, democracy and advocacy are crying and crying, democracy and advocacy are afraid and afraid but the force is laughing and laughing, but the criminals are laughing and laughing, but the criminals are winning and winning in the planet. Where is the right conscience of the people in public Administration? Why should Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain ask for legal support to Mr. Anthony Albanese, MP, Prime Minister of Australia? Why should Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain ask legal support to the political leaders? What is the function of the executive officers of the country? What is the function of the executive ministers of the country? What is the function of the executive secretaries of the country? What should be the reason? Who should take care the reason? Who should take care the legal rights in Australia? Who should take care the human rights in Australia? Where are the action and supports? Prestige of the designation is winning and winning, but the public service is failing and failing, but the performance is failing and failing. These are the question marks in Australia to the global community, researcher community, and professor community (M. A. Hossain, 2023bw; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k; Hossain, 2025g) (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024b; Hossain, 2025f).

3 Recommendation and approach of 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to the public officials for their negligence of legal support and public service

Figure 1. Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) self-funded and self-communicated with RMIT University, Australia; and the ministerial administration of Australia, Bangladesh; and UN secretary general who simultaneously showed zero responsibility to investigate to assess the life-threatening conspiracy to Nobel Nominee Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.); RMIT University, Australia. What should be the reason? Possibly every CEO of a country serves to citizen for the personal benefit rather than the monthly salary of the public office. These are the disturbing situation to survive in the planet. What is the purpose of a prestigious designation of a country or united nations or university? Who should take care the legal rights? Who should take care the citizens? Who should take care the country? Who should defence against international criminal? Who should take care the planet? Everyone should pay 1,00,000 Australian penalty units, if they are neglecting their service.

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
 Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD²
 Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
 MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process,
 color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
 PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg., City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg., BCMC College of Engg
 & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg.; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam);
 Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
 Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
 Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
 University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and
 Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Figure 1. Self-funded communication of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain with RMIT University; and ministerial administration of Australia, Bangladesh; and UN secretary general.

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia
Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

4 Theory of criminal and crime for the self-protection of the chief criminal and limitations of criminal and crime assessment (M. A. Hossain, 2023f)

4.1 Time duration of crime for the self-protection of the chief criminal

When the time duration of crime increases, the degree of harassment to plaintiff/victim increases, the degree of confusing to plaintiff/victim increases, the degree of patience of a plaintiff/victim decreases, the support of criminal investigation department may decline due to the complication of the crime and criminal assessment.

Page | 8

4.2 Multidimensional connection and planning of criminal for the self-protection of the chief criminal

When the number of connections of the criminal increases, the degree of harassment to plaintiff/victim increases, the degree of confusing to plaintiff/victim increases, the degree of patience of a plaintiff/victim decreases, the support of criminal investigation department may decline due to the complication of the crime and criminal assessment. Professional criminal tries to involve quality person of the society/profession with their crimes, professional criminal tries to involve surrounding people of the target person, but the surrounding people can not understand the right intention of the professional criminal. Professional criminal tries to increase the number of criminals and number of confusing for their self-protection. Therefore, a good person may be twisted with the crimes and criminals, but the criminal investigation department can not understand accordingly. This is also a side-effect of the court system and law implementation.

4.3 Pictorial evidence of the crime, crime scene, and criminal

A theory of evidence also represents like the pictorial evidence of the crime, crime scene, and criminal. International criminal has high quality expertise to destroy the evidence to hide the evidence to confuse the evidence under the implementation of unethical power, multidimensional illegal roads of connectivity, and professional practice of crimes. People like to say good/bad by the personal benefit/professional benefit/situation. People like to execute their duty by the personal benefit/professional benefit/situation. Both lower-class and higher-class person may follow the theory. These are the limitation of human attitude. These are the limitation of the department of criminal investigation, court system, and law enforcement. These are limitations to establish to approach of zero crime.

4.4 Number of criminals for the self-protection of the chief criminal

When the number of criminal increases, the degree of harassment to plaintiff/victim increases, the degree of confusing to plaintiff/victim increases, the support of criminal investigation department may decline due to the complication of the crime and criminal assessment.

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.). Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁹ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	---	---

5 Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) is recommending and proposing an eighteen-dimensional alternative solution to ensure the legal services to ensure the acceptability of legal rights to the global community to the professor community (M. A. Hossain, 2023f)

5.1 Recommendation and approach to Australia for the assessment to ensure the situation-friendly and/or victim-friendly legal service (M. A. Hossain, 2023bw)

1. High court of Australia should/can assess the situation of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) to make a decision of the final outcomes of the plaintiff (M. A. Hossain, 2023f). Legal aid fund/welfare fund/research fund of high court of Australia/welfare fund of foreign ministry of Australia should/can ensure the legal service.
2. High court of Australia should/can assess the situation of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) to make a decision to ensure the proper legal service to the plaintiff (M. A. Hossain, 2023f). Legal aid fund/welfare fund/research fund of high court of Australia/welfare fund of foreign ministry of Australia should/can ensure the legal service.
3. High court of Australia should/can assess the situation of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) for recommendation for going to international court. Legal aid fund/welfare fund/research fund of foreign ministry of Australia should/can ensure the legal funding for going to international court (M. A. Hossain, 2023f).
4. High court of Australia should/can assess the situation of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) for recommendation to the UN (M. A. Hossain, 2023f). Legal aid fund/welfare fund/research fund of the UN should/can ensure the legal funding for going to international court (M. A. Hossain, 2023f).
5. High court of Australia should/can ensure the safety, income support in camouflage situation against criminals, merit/scholarly growth support in camouflage situation against criminals, living, and food support to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) for the protection against international criminals (M. A. Hossain, 2023a; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k; Md.. Anowar Hossain, 2024).

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

6. High court of Australia and/or international court should individually/jointly recommend and announce Nobel prize winner in peace and/or Nobel prize winner in camouflage physics to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) to ensure/declare the right acceptability of Nobel prize to the global community to the professor community to the researcher community (M. A. Hossain, 2023g; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x) (M. A. Hossain, 2023bx; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x).

5.2 Recommendation and approach to United Kingdom (UK) for the assessment to ensure the situation-friendly and/or victim-friendly legal service (M. A. Hossain, 2023bw)

7. High court of UK should/can assess the situation of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) to make a decision of the final outcomes of the plaintiff (M. A. Hossain, 2023f). Legal aid fund/welfare fund/research fund of high court of UK/welfare fund of foreign ministry of UK should/can ensure the legal service.
8. High court of UK should/can assess the situation of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) to make a decision to ensure the proper legal service to the plaintiff (M. A. Hossain, 2023f). Legal aid fund/welfare fund/research fund of high court of UK/welfare fund of foreign ministry of UK should/can ensure the legal service.
9. High court of UK should/can assess the situation of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) for recommendation for going to international court. Legal aid fund/welfare fund/research fund of foreign ministry of UK should/can ensure the legal funding for going to international court (M. A. Hossain, 2023f).
10. High court of UK should/can assess the situation of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) for recommendation to the UN (M. A. Hossain, 2023f). Legal aid fund/welfare fund/research fund of the UN should/can ensure the legal funding for going to international court (M. A. Hossain, 2023f).
11. High court of UK should/can ensure the safety, income support in camouflage situation against criminals, merit growth support in camouflage situation against criminals, living, and food support to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) for the protection against international criminals (M. A. Hossain, 2023a; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k; Md.. Anowar Hossain, 2024).

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCRC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	--	---

12. High court of UK and/or international court should individually/jointly recommend and announce Nobel prize winner in peace and/or Nobel prize winner in camouflage physics to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) to ensure/declare the right acceptability of Nobel prize to the global community to the professor community to the researcher community (M. A. Hossain, 2023g; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x) (M. A. Hossain, 2023bx; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x).

5.3 Recommendation and approach to Bangladesh for the assessment to ensure the situation-friendly and/or victim-friendly legal service (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k)

13. Foreign ministry of Bangladesh should/can forward/recommend this letter to the high commissioner of Australia and/or UN and/or international court.

14. High court of Bangladesh should/can assess the situation of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) for recommendation for going to international court. Legal aid fund/welfare fund/research fund of foreign ministry of Bangladesh should/can ensure the legal fund for going to international court (M. A. Hossain, 2023f).

15. High court of Bangladesh should/can assess the situation of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) for recommendation to the UN. Legal aid fund/welfare fund/research fund of the UN should/can ensure the legal funds for going to international court (M. A. Hossain, 2023f).

16. High court of Bangladesh should/can ensure the safety, income support in camouflage situation against criminals, living, and food support to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) for the protection against international criminals (M. A. Hossain, 2023a; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k; Md.. Anowar Hossain, 2024).

5.4 Recommendation and approach to the United Nations for the assessment to ensure the situation-friendly and/or victim-friendly legal service (Hossain, 2025g)

17. UN should/can assess the situation of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) for recommendation for going to international court. Legal aid fund/welfare fund/research fund of the UN should/can ensure the legal fund for going to international court (M. A. Hossain, 2023f).

18. UN should/can ensure the safety, income support in camouflage situation against criminals, living, and food support to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain,

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) for the protection against international criminals (M. A. Hossain, 2023a; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k; Md.. Anowar Hossain, 2024).

6 Situation of public service in Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations; the policy of country, the policy of United Nations, the policy of public service is failing and failing due to the human negligence and/or habitual practice of the government and/or ministerial administration and/or chief executive officer and/or person; figure 1 (M. A. Hossain, 2023f)

Page | 12

6.1 Legal notice to Mr. Anthony Albanese, MP, Prime Minister of Australia from the office of Nobel Nominee Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) (M. A. Hossain, 2023bw)

A full information and evidence of life-threatening conspiracy and history of long-term harassment was sent to the office of prime minister of Australia, attorney general's department of Australia, law minister of Australia, foreign ministry of Australia, education ministry of Australia, ministry of home affairs of Australia, high commissioner of Australia in Bangladesh, high commissioner of Bangladesh in Australia, human rights commission in Australia and Bangladesh, vice chancellor of RMIT University and school administration in Australia, professor community of RMIT University, local police station in Australia, registry of high court in Australia, Victoria legal aid, local ministerial cabinet of Victoria in Australia, relevant offices and professional communities (M. A. Hossain, 2023f). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) was/is seeking the administrative action and support from the office of prime minister of Australia. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain has been a sufferer since 2021-2022 at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Australia. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain would like to refer the administrative communications. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain acknowledges the letter from the prime minister's office on 11 December 2023, reference: MC23-103435 (M. A. Hossain, 2023bw). Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain couldn't understand that the official letter of prime minister office had no date with the signature of Mr./Ms. Megan, Senior adviser, ministerial correspondence unit, department of prime minister and cabinet. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is asking assessment support of prime minister of Australia if the ministers of education and home affairs are ignoring the administrative command and administrative decisions of the prime minister and cabinet. Therefore, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) is asking for legal costs and legal support to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia. Accordingly, Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain sent a few letters/follow-up letters to the office of Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also submitted, repeated, informed,

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.). Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assis. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assis. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assis. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	---	--

and knocked the condition of letter and situation of assessment on 3 September 2025, but he didn't receive any administrative reply from the office of prime minister of Australia (M. A. Hossain, 2023bw; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024b). Responsibilities versus public services are the vital role of a prime minister if he is a CEO of Australian government if he is getting salary from the government of Australia if he is getting social honor and international honor for the post of prime minister. If the salary of CEO is higher, the responsibility should also be higher. The public service of a prime minister is hampering, interrupting, and confusing if he is not ensuring the right service to the PhD scholar if he is assessing the letter of Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain since 2023 if Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is not getting legal support since 2022, if Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is not getting salary since 2022. What is the situation of public service in Australia? Who should take care the public service in Australia? Who should take care the PhD scholar in Australia? Who should take care the legal aid support in Australia? Prime minister of Australia/delegate of prime minister should have a follow-up of Australian higher education should solve the problem of PhD school if he is also the prime minister of Melbourne if he is also the prime minister of RMIT University. If Mr. Anthony Albanese is a legal prime minister of Australia, if he is neglecting to investigate the killing conspiracy in Australian PhD school if he is neglecting the international service if he is neglecting and delaying the public service, if the office of prime minister is neglecting and delaying the public service, he/his office should pay the penalty of 1,00,000 Australian penalty units (M. A. Hossain, 2023bw; M. A. Hossain, 2023c; Hossain, 2025f). Who is the chief executive officer of Australia if Mr. Anthony Albanese is the prime minister of Australia? Nobody should have right to cease the rights of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Nobody should cease the money/salary of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, he also needs living and food allowance. RMIT should not cease single dollar from the pocket of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Nobody should plan to kill the researcher. Nobody should harass the merit growth of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Every Australian PhD scholar should have right to access the office of prime minister, office of Mr. Anthony Albanese. Every Australian PhD scholar should have right to access the legal aid fund/welfare fund/research fund of prime minister of Australia without which PhD scholar policy should be banned in Australia under the assessment support of UN (M. A. Hossain, 2023f, 2023bw). This is not begging to the prime minister, this is not begging to Mr. Anthony Albanese, this is the legal right of the Australian PhD scholar, this is also the beneficiary rights of the PhD scholar (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024j) (M. A. Hossain, 2023f; Hossain, 2025d, 2025f). How many complaint letters did prime minister get/receive in his public service like the request letter from Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, prime minister of Australia should prove to the relevant court to signify his busy schedule/manpower shortage/secretary shortage in his office of public service? If he is doing service offence, he should pay the 'compensation award of prime minister' to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

(Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) (M. A. Hossain, 2023f). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) should have legal rights to use the administrative desk of prime minister of Australia if Mr. Anthony Albanese can claim his self-designation of prime minister if Mr. Anthony Albanese can claim his self-salary of prime minister of Australia. This is the administrative supremacy of democracy and advocacy of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.).

6.2 Symptom of zero responsibility of Mr. Jeremy Bruer, Ms. Nardia Simpson, and Ms. Susan Ryle, high commissioner of Australia in Bangladesh; legal notice to the high commissioners of Australia from the office of Nobel Nominee Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.); RMIT University, Australia (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024j) (M. A. Hossain, 2023f; Hossain, 2025f)

Referred to Bangladeshi newspaper, Ms. Nardia Simpson can do meeting with non-elected political leader in Bangladesh, but she can not solve the international crime, but she can not solve the Australian crime, but she can not talk with Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), but she can not discuss with the foreign ministry/home ministry/education ministry of Australia, but she has no priority to the international complaints. Every political government prioritizes the political leader/political government/elected government. So, Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain notified to the political government of Australia and government of Bangladesh. Ms. Susan Ryle, High Commissioner of Australia in Bangladesh can approach to invest through UN development programme (UNDP) for the election in Bangladesh. But high commissioner can not approach/announce to protect Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain against Australian criminals. But the high commissioner can not invest/approach/recommend legal aid fund/welfare fund to protect Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain against Australian criminals. A high commissioner is an Australian representative in Bangladesh who practically showed zero responsibility. These are the symptom of neglecting the personal liability, official liability, official responsibility, Australian government liability, responsibility of international relation, and Australian public service liability. Online service is the symptom of cheating and/or non-monitoring and/or non-action and/or non-response, 100% neglecting and disobeying the public service of high commissioner. Offline service/physical office is also confusing the public service is also confusing the right service of labour party in Australia. But, there is signboard of high commissioner office at the diplomatic zone of Bangladesh. Every government invests an international allowance for a high commissioner for a high commissioner office for the international service. What is the necessity to communicate with the prime minister of Australia if a high commissioner is also an executive position if a high commissioner is the representative of the prime minister if a high commissioner is also getting salary from the Australian government if high commissioner is also an authorized person of Australian

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.),
Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD²
Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process,
color engg), applied law & criminology
Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)*
Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)*
Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
Former Assis. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg
& Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assis. Registrar (Exam);
Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assis. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and
Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

administration of foreign affairs. A full information and evidence of life-threatening conspiracy and history of long-term harassment was sent to the office of high commissioner of Australia, relevant offices and professional communities. If Mr. Jeremy Bruer, Ms. Nardia Simpson, and Ms. Susan Ryle was/is a high commissioner of Australia, if they are neglecting the international service, if they are neglecting and delaying the public service, if the office of high commissioner is neglecting and delaying the public service; they should pay penalty of 3,00,000 Australian penalty units. Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should have a legal right and legal authorization to access the ready platform of public service. Nobody should have right to cease the rights of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Nobody should cease the money/salary of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, he also needs living and food allowance. RMIT should not cease single dollar from the pocket of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Nobody should plan to kill the researcher. Nobody should harass the merit growth of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain applied to the office of Australian high commissioner and also tried/applied to meet with the high commissioner of Australia in Bangladesh. Every Australian PhD scholar should have right to access the office of high commissioner. Every PhD scholar in Australia should have right to access the legal aid fund/welfare fund/research fund of high commissioner. This is not begging to the high commissioner, this is the legal right of the Australian PhD scholar, this is also the beneficiary rights of the PhD scholar (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024j) (M. A. Hossain, 2023f; Hossain, 2025d, 2025f). How many complaint letters did they get/receive in their public service like the request letter from Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, high commissioners of Australia should prove to the relevant court to signify their busy schedule/manpower shortage/secretary shortage in his/her office of the public service? Every foreign minister should have a follow-up to the right functions/right duties of a high commissioner. If a prime minister should execute the duties of a high commissioner, the post of Australian high commissioner in Bangladesh is invalid. If the office of prime minister is delaying the service of investigation of life-threatening conspiracy, if the relevant office is also delaying the service of investigation of life-threatening conspiracy; office of prime minister should ensure should recommend every compensation and salary to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024j) (M. A. Hossain, 2023e; M. A. Hossain, 2023b). If high commissioners are doing service offence, they should pay the 'compensation award' to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) (M. A. Hossain, 2023f). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) should have legal rights to use the administrative desk of high commissioner of Australia if high commissioner can claim his/her self-designation of high commissioner of Australia if high commissioner can claim his/her self-salary of high commissioner of Australia. This is the administrative supremacy of democracy

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

and advocacy of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.).

6.3 Symptom of zero responsibility of Mr. António Guterres, Secretary General, United nations; legal notice to the UN secretary general from the office of Nobel Nominee Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.); RMIT University, Australia (M. A. Hossain, 2023bu; Hossain, 2025g)

Page | 16

A full information and evidence of life-threatening conspiracy and history of long-term harassment was sent to the office of UN secretary general, UN human rights commission, UN office of Bangladesh, administration of Bangladesh, administration of Australia, prime minister of Australia, prime minister/chief advisor of Bangladesh, president of Bangladesh, president of United States of America, lawyer/bar association of Bangladesh, lawyer/bar association of Australia, lawyer/bar association of India, lawyer/bar association of United Kingdom, lawyer/bar association of United States of America, relevant offices and professional communities, and administration of international court to seek welfare support to international victim against international criminal against Australian criminal. Mr. António Guterres, UN Secretary General and Professor h.c Rafal Marcin Wasik, Chairman, UN human rights commission should pay the penalty of 2,00,000 Australian penalty units if they are neglecting the international service, if they are neglecting and delaying the public service, if the office of UN secretary general is neglecting and delaying the public service (M. A. Hossain, 2023f, 2023bu; Hossain, 2025g). Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also notified, requested, and sent a letter to the UN president who also showed zero responsibility. Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should have a legal right and legal authorization to access the ready platform of public service of UN. Nobody should have right to cease the rights of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Nobody should cease the money/salary of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, he also needs living and food allowance. RMIT should not cease single dollar from the pocket of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Nobody should plan to kill the researcher. Nobody should harass the merit growth of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Mr. António Guterres, UN Secretary General came to Bangladesh on 13-16 March, 2025. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain wrote a letter to UN Bangladesh office and foreign ministry of Bangladesh to meet with Mr. António Guterres, UN Secretary General. Mr. António Guterres can meet Rohingya community, but he can not meet with Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) and/or relevant offices of public service can not manage the meeting. Bangladesh acknowledges to UN for the support of Rohingya community. Bangladesh should get proper administrative allowance, education allowance, baby allowance, and crime management allowance for the support of Rohingya community. If Rohingya community in Bangladesh is not a baby production unit, UN should take care the baby, UN should take care the baby schooling.

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Former Assit. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assit. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assit. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assit. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	--	--

UN has also a scope to distribute to accommodate Rohingya to different countries and/or their mother countries. Australia is not a populated country like Bangladesh. UN may accommodate, train, and educate a percentage of Rohingya in Australia to minimize the crime in Bangladesh. UN should convince/force the government of Australia to provide personal safety, earning safety, professional safety, earned salary, and every compensation to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should get the access rights of international public service of UN, international public service of Australia, and international public service of Bangladesh. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain got the offer letter of research fund through the UN job (20,000USD/month), UNDP (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024i); but it was also a symptom of international crime and international criminal involvement. UN secretary should assess and scrutiny. When Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain has no living and food allowance, he can not access the support of UN, Bangladesh government, and Australian government. UN is caring to Rohingya community, similarly UN should have a support to professor should have a support to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Without which Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should believe, people should believe, public should believe that that the maximum government service and/or public services are relevant to the personal benefit and/or professional benefit and/or political benefit and/or additional benefit (Hossain, 2025d) (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024i; Hossain, 2025g). Every citizen should have right to access the office of UN. Every citizen should have right to access the legal aid fund/welfare fund/research fund of UN. This is not begging to the secretary general, this is the legal right of the citizen, this is also the beneficiary rights of the citizen (Hossain, 2025d). Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also tried to meet with UN authority/UN representative at UN Bangladesh office at house: 1, road: 86-88, Gulshan-2, Dhaka-1212, Bangladesh on 22 September 2025. It was a self-funded communication of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain with UN office. Mr. Afser, ASF security team told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in Bengali language, “UN Bangladesh office has no policy/way to discuss with UN representative/UN authority, this is not the office of UN secretary general”. These are the symptoms of public service of UN in Bangladesh. What is the public service of UN? What should be the purpose of UN office in Bangladesh? Who should communicate with UN authority? What should be the process to communicate with UN authority? Online service is the symptom of cheating and/or non-monitoring and/or non-action and/or non-response, 100% neglecting and disobeying the public service or UN service. Offline service/physical office is also confusing the public service. But, there is signboard of UN office at the diplomatic zone of Bangladesh. What is the necessity to have an expensive physical office of UN in Bangladesh if there is no benefit of public service, public meeting, and public complaint. Possibly, UN money is not currency, UN money is the printed paper of different countries. What is the source of salary and office rents of UN public servants? What is the source of printed money for the UN public servants? Who is paying the salary to the office of UN? There is scope of right

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

campaign to the public to the countries to the public service officers of UN. What is happening in the world in the name of UN service, UN care, UN nursing, UN legal rights, UN human rights, UN leadership, UN investment, UN countries, and UN office? How many complaint letters did UN secretary general get/receive in his public service like the request letter from Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, UN secretary general should prove to the relevant court to signify his busy schedule/manpower shortage/secretary shortage in his office of public service? Mr. António Guterres, UN Secretary General should circulate the whole letter to the whole president of the whole countries of UN for the support of citizen for the support of democracy and advocacy for the support of international legal rights and human rights for the support of public service for the support of president community for the support of international community. International criminals in Australia and expert criminals in Australia tried to misguide the family people, professional people, and surrounding people of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in Australia and Bangladesh. But these people can not easily understand the right intentions of the expert criminals, but these people have no self-understanding capability of the right intention of the expert criminals or gang of the criminals; when the international criminals in Australian PhD school have the academic, professional, and life-harming tendency to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Expert criminals have techniques to spread/twist the international crimes and confuse the organized crimes. Government of Australia and/or international court should carefully assess the occurrence in Australian PhD school. Mr. António Guterres, UN Secretary General should ensure the safety to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain against Australian criminals against international criminals. Every parliament member/administrative officer of the countries of UN should get the zero-crime message of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Possibly, some governments are caring the international criminals. Possibly, some governments/relevant peoples can not run/continue their business without international criminals. Possibly, the government is not paying to the international criminals; so, the criminals are doing crimes to earn money under the direct/indirect support of the government. If it is necessary to have international criminal, government can appoint for the 'post of international criminal'. Everything should be transparent for the peace surviving and peace caring. Possibly and indirectly, government may invest/support for the criminals, criminals may invest their illegal source of money to execute the crimes. But the government can not invest for the protection of professor. What is the ugly situation of policy, democracy and advocacy? There is scope of right guidelines, right action and support of UN, and right understanding for the right surviving for the peace surviving in the planet (Hossain, 2025g). If UN secretary general and chairman of international human rights commission are doing service offence, they should pay the 'compensation award of United Nations' to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) (M. A. Hossain, 2023f). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) should have legal rights to use the administrative desk of

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anwar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assisit. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assisit. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assisit. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anwar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anwar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	---	--

UN secretary general if secretary general can claim his self-designation of secretary general of UN if secretary general can claim his self-salary of secretary general of UN. This is the administrative supremacy of democracy and advocacy of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.).

6.4 Symptom of zero responsibility of Mr. M. Allama Siddiki, former high commissioner of Bangladesh in Australia; Mr. F.M. Borhan Uddin, high commissioner of Bangladesh in Australia; legal notice to the high commissioners of Bangladesh in Australia from the office of Nobel Nominee Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.); RMIT University, Australia (M. A. Hossain, 2023bc; Md. Anwar Hossain, 2024k; Hossain, 2025f)

A full information and evidence of life-threatening conspiracy and history of long-term harassment was sent to the office of high commissioner of Bangladesh in Australia, relevant offices and professional communities. Mr. M. Allama Siddiki, former high commissioner of Bangladesh in Australia; and Mr. F.M. Borhan Uddin, high commissioner of Bangladesh in Australia should pay the penalty of 2,00,000 Australian penalty units if they are neglecting the international service, if they are neglecting and delaying the public service, if the office of high commissioner is neglecting and delaying the public service (M. A. Hossain, 2023f, 2023bc; Md. Anwar Hossain, 2024k; Hossain, 2025f). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain should have a legal right and legal authorization to access the ready platform of public service. Nobody should have right to cease the rights of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain. Nobody should cease the money/salary of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, he also needs living and food allowance. RMIT should not cease single dollar from the pocket of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain. Nobody should plan to kill the researcher. Nobody should harass the merit growth of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain. Every citizen should have right to access the office of high commissioner. Every citizen should have right to access the legal aid fund/welfare fund/research fund of high commissioner of Bangladesh in Australia. This is not begging to the high commissioner, this is the legal right of the citizen, this is also the beneficiary rights of the citizen(Hossain, 2025d). How many complaint letters did high commissioners get/receive in their public service like the request letter from Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, high commissioners should prove to the relevant court to signify their busy schedule/manpower shortage/secretary shortage in their office of public service? Every foreign minister should have a strong follow-up to the right functions/right duties of a high commissioner (Md. Anwar Hossain, 2024k; Hossain, 2025f). If high commissioners are doing service offence, they should pay the ‘compensation award’ to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) (M. A. Hossain, 2023f). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) should have legal rights to use the administrative desk of high commissioner of Bangladesh in Australia if high commissioners can

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia
Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anwar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

claim their self-designation of high commissioner of Bangladesh if high commissioner can claim their self-salary of high commissioner of Bangladesh. This is the administrative supremacy of democracy and advocacy of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.).

6.5 Symptom of zero responsibility of Mr. Jason Clare, MP, Education Minister of Australia; legal notice to the education minister of Australia from the office of Nobel Nominee Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.); RMIT University, Australia (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024e; Hossain, 2025f)

A full information and evidence of life-threatening conspiracy and history of long-term harassment in Australian PhD school was sent to the office of education minister of Australia, RMIT University of Australia, ministry of home affairs of Australia, local police station, relevant offices and professional communities. Mr. Jason Clare, MP, Education Minister of Australia should pay the penalty of 1,00,000 Australian penalty units if he is neglecting the international service, if he is neglecting and delaying the public service, if the office of education minister is neglecting and delaying the public service (M. A. Hossain, 2023f; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024e; Hossain, 2025f). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should have a legal right and legal authorization to access the ready platform of public service. Nobody should have right to cease the rights of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Nobody should cease the money/salary of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, he also needs living and food allowance. RMIT should not cease single dollar from the pocket of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Nobody should plan to kill the researcher. Nobody should harass the merit growth of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Every Australian PhD scholar should have right to access the office of education minister. Every PhD scholar should have right to access the legal aid fund/welfare fund/research fund of education minister. This is not begging to the minister, this is the legal right of the Australian PhD scholar, this is also the beneficiary rights of the PhD scholar (Hossain, 2025d). How many complaint letters did education minister get/receive in his public service like the request letter from Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, education minister should prove to the relevant court to signify his busy schedule/manpower shortage/secretary shortage in his office of public service? If he is doing service offence, he should pay the 'compensation award' to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) (M. A. Hossain, 2023f). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) should have legal rights to use the administrative desk of education minister of Australia if education minister can claim his self-designation of education minister of Australia if education minister can claim his self-salary of education minister of Australia. This is the administrative supremacy of

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India, Australia, Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	--	---

democracy and advocacy of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.).

6.6 Symptom of zero responsibility of Mr. Tony Burke, MP, Minister of Home Affairs of Australia; legal notice to the minister of home affairs of Australia from the office of Nobel Nominee Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.); RMIT University, Australia (A. Hossain, 2023; M. A. Hossain, 2023e; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024j; Md.. Anowar Hossain, 2024)

A full information and evidence of life-threatening conspiracy and history of long-term harassment in Australian PhD school was sent to the office of minister of home affairs of Australia, education ministry of Australia, RMIT University of Australia, St. Vincent hospital of Australia, local police station of Australia, relevant offices and professional communities. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain filled a form and submitted a lot of information for the assessment and consideration of ministry of home affairs. Mr. Tony Burke, MP, Minister of Home Affairs of Australia should pay the penalty of 1,00,000 Australian penalty units if he is neglecting the international service, if he is neglecting and delaying the public service, if the office of minister of home affairs is neglecting and delaying the public service (A. Hossain, 2023; M. A. Hossain, 2023f; M. A. Hossain, 2023e; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024j; Md.. Anowar Hossain, 2024). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should have a legal right and legal authorization to access the ready platform of public service. Nobody should have right to cease the rights of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Nobody should cease the money/salary of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, he also needs living and food allowance. RMIT should not cease single dollar from the pocket of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Nobody should plan to kill the researcher. Nobody should harass the merit growth of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Every Australian PhD scholar should have right to access the office of home affairs. Every Australian PhD scholar should have right to access the legal aid fund/welfare fund/research fund of home affairs. This is not begging to the minister, this is the legal rights of the PhD scholar, this is also the beneficiary rights of the PhD scholar(Hossain, 2025d). How many complaint letters did minister get/receive in his public service like the request letter from Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, minister of home affairs should prove to the relevant court to signify his busy schedule/manpower shortage/ secretary shortage in his office of public service? If he is doing service offence, he should pay the ‘compensation award’ to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) (M. A. Hossain, 2023f). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) should have legal rights to use the administrative desk of minister of home affairs if minister can claim his self-designation of home affairs in Australia if minister can claim his self-salary of minister of home affairs. This is the administrative

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

supremacy of democracy and advocacy of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.).

6.7 Symptom of zero responsibility of Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President of Bangladesh; legal notice to the president of Bangladesh from the office of Nobel Nominee Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.); RMIT University, Australia (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k; Hossain, 2025d, 2025f).

Page | 22

Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain tried to knock the condition of submitted letter and situation of assessment. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also sent e-mail letters, but the e-mail address of website was invalid to send to the e-mail address of the website of president office. Similarly, he also tried to send on 2 September 2025 (evidence attached), but it was the failure notice of e-mail address mentioned in the website but the government invests for the website but the government is an active organization. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also tried to send e-mail letters to the attorney general's department of Bangladesh on 2 September 2025 (evidence attached), but it was the failure notice of e-mail but the government invests for the website but the government invests money for the office of president but the government/citizen invests salary for the office of president but the government neglects/dislikes the rights of the citizen. The e-mail address of attorney general's department of Bangladesh was also fully invalid with the outcomes of failure notice of the sent e-mails. A full information of life-threatening conspiracy and history of long-term harassment in Australian PhD school was sent to the office of president, chancellor, foreign ministry, university grant commission, high commissioner of Bangladesh in Australia, high commissioner of Australia in Bangladesh, human rights commission in Australia and Bangladesh, attorney general's department of Bangladesh, relevant offices and professional communities. Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President of Bangladesh should pay the penalty of 1,00,000 Australian penalty units if he is neglecting the international service, if he is neglecting and delaying the public service, if the office of president is neglecting and delaying the public service (M. A. Hossain, 2023f; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k; Hossain, 2025d, 2025f). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should have a legal right and legal authorization to access the ready platform of public service. Nobody should have right to cease the rights of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Nobody should cease the money/salary of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, he also needs living and food allowance. RMIT should not cease single dollar from the pocket of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Nobody should plan to kill the researcher. Nobody should harass the merit growth of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain applied to the office of president and also tried/applied to meet with the president of Bangladesh. Every president should have a meeting time with the citizen. Every citizen should have right to access the office of president. Every citizen

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder, Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	--	--

should have right to access the legal aid fund/welfare fund/research fund of the president office. This is not begging to the president, this is the legal right of the citizen, this is also the beneficiary rights of the citizen (Hossain, 2025d). How many complaint letters did president get/receive in his public service like the request letter from Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain; president of Bangladesh should prove to the relevant court to signify his busy schedule/manpower shortage/secretary shortage in his office of public service? If he is doing service offence, he should pay the ‘compensation award of president’ to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) (M. A. Hossain, 2023f). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) should have legal rights to use the administrative desk of president if Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin can claim his self-designation of president of Bangladesh if president can claim his self-salary of president of Bangladesh. This is the administrative supremacy of democracy and advocacy of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.).

6.8 Symptom of zero responsibility of Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Mohammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh; legal notice to the chief advisor of Bangladesh from the office of Nobel Nominee Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.); RMIT University, Australia (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k, 2024aa; Hossain, 2025f)

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also tried to knock the condition of submitted letter and situation of assessment. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also sent e-mail letters, but the e-mail address of website was invalid to send to the e-mail address of the website. Similarly, he also tried to send on 2 September 2025 (evidence attached), but it was the failure notice of e-mail but the government invests for the website. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also tried to send e-mail letters to the attorney general’s department of Bangladesh on 2 September 2025 (evidence attached), but it was the failure notice of e-mail but the government invests for the website but the government invests money for the office of chief advisor but the government/citizen invests salary for the office of chief advisor but the government neglects/dislikes the rights of the citizen. A failure notice of an e-mail is reflecting the symptom of official non-responsibility of a government. A full information and evidence of life-threatening conspiracy and history of long-term harassment in Australian PhD school was sent to the office of chief advisor, office of president, office of chancellor, attorney general’s department, foreign ministry, high commissioner of Bangladesh in Australia, high commissioner of Australia in Bangladesh, RMIT University of Australia, university grant commission of Bangladesh, relevant offices and professional communities. Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Mohammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh should pay the penalty of 1,00,000 Australian penalty units if he is neglecting the international service, if he is neglecting and delaying the public service, if the office of chief advisor is neglecting and delaying the public service (M. A. Hossain, 2023f; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k, 2024aa; Hossain, 2025f). Who is the

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia
Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

chief executive officer of Bangladesh if Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Mohammad Yunus is the chief advisor of Bangladesh? In the present situation of interim government, chief advisor is the equivalent post of prime minister/chief minister. Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should have a legal right and legal authorization to access the ready platform of public service in Bangladesh. Nobody should have right to cease the rights of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Nobody should cease the money/salary of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, he also needs living and food allowance. RMIT should not cease single dollar from the pocket of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Nobody should plan to kill the researcher. Nobody should harass the merit growth of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain applied to the office of chief advisor and also tried/applied to meet with the chief advisor of Bangladesh. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain applied to the director office of university grants commission (UGC) of Bangladesh and chairman of UGC for the relevant support and relevant recommendation of Bangladesh (Hossain, 2025f). Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also tried to meet with Professor Dr. SMA Faiz, Chairman of UGC, Bangladesh. UGC chairman should/may approve/recommend the professor crisis fund of Bangladesh if UGC is a higher education wings of education ministry and foreign ministry. Every citizen should have right to access the office of chief advisor. Every citizen should have right to access the legal aid fund/welfare fund/research fund of chief advisor. This is not begging to the chief advisor of Bangladesh, this is the legal right of the citizen, this is also the beneficiary rights of the citizen(Hossain, 2025d). How many complaint letters did chief advisor get/receive in his public service like the request letter from Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain; chief advisor of Bangladesh should prove to the relevant court to signify his busy schedule/manpower shortage/secretary shortage in his office of public service? If he is doing service offence, he should pay the ‘compensation award of chief advisor’ to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) (M. A. Hossain, 2023f).

6.9 Symptom of zero responsibility of Mr. Md. Touhid Hossain, Foreign Minister of Bangladesh; Mr. Md. Jashim Uddin, Foreign Secretary of Bangladesh; and Mr. Asad Alam Siam, Foreign Secretary of Bangladesh; legal notice to the foreign minister and foreign secretaries of Bangladesh from the office of Nobel Nominee Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.); RMIT University, Australia (M. A. Hossain, 2023bc; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k; Hossain, 2025f)

A full information and evidence of life-threatening conspiracy and history of long-term harassment in Australian PhD school was sent to the office of foreign minister of Bangladesh, high commissioner of Bangladesh in Australia, university grants commission (UGC), relevant offices and professional communities. Mr. Md. Touhid Hossain, Foreign Minister of Bangladesh; Mr. Md.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.). Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assisit. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assisit. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assisit. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	---	--

Jashim Uddin, Foreign Secretary of Bangladesh; and Mr. Asad Alam Siam, Foreign Secretary of Bangladesh should pay the penalty of 3,00,000 Australian penalty units if they are neglecting the international service, if they are neglecting and delaying the public service, if the office of foreign minister is neglecting and delaying the public service (M. A. Hossain, 2023f, 2023bc; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k; Hossain, 2025f). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should have a legal right and legal authorization to access the ready platform of public service. Nobody should have right to cease the rights of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Nobody should cease the money/salary of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, he also needs living and food allowance. RMIT should not cease single dollar from the pocket of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Nobody should plan to kill the researcher. Nobody should harass the merit growth of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also met and discussed with the welfare administration of foreign ministry. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain applied to the office of foreign ministry and also tried/applied to meet with Mr. Md. Jashim Uddin, foreign secretary of Bangladesh (Hossain, 2025f). Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain applied to the office of UGC of Bangladesh and chairman of UGC for the relevant support and relevant recommendation of Bangladesh. Parallelly, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also tried to meet with the UGC chairman (Hossain, 2025f). Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain sent many letters/cc letters to the e-mail address of foreign ministry, UGC, and high commissioner of Bangladesh in Australia. Every citizen should have right to access the office of foreign minister. Every citizen should have right to access the legal aid fund/welfare fund/research fund of foreign minister. This is not begging to the minister, this is not begging to the secretary, this is the legal rights of the citizen, this is also the beneficiary rights of the citizen(Hossain, 2025d). How many complaint letters did foreign minister/secretary get/receive in their public service like the request letter from Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, foreign minister/foreign secretary of Bangladesh should prove to the relevant court to signify their busy schedule/manpower shortage/ secretary shortage in their office of public service? A front gate receptionist of foreign ministry told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, “foreign ministry of Bangladesh has around 250 secretary/assistant secretary graded persons”. If foreign minister and foreign secretaries are doing service offence, they should pay the ‘compensation award’ to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) (M. A. Hossain, 2023f). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) should have legal rights to use the administrative desk of foreign minister and foreign secretary if foreign minister and foreign secretary can claim their self-designation of foreign ministry of Bangladesh if foreign minister and foreign secretary can claim their self-salary of foreign ministry of Bangladesh. This is the administrative supremacy of democracy and advocacy of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.).

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

6.10 Symptom of zero responsibility of Ms. Penny Wong, Foreign minister of Australia; Ms. Paula Ganly, First Assistant Secretary, Consular and Crisis Management Division, Department of Foreign Affairs and Trade; legal notice to the foreign minister and foreign secretary of Australia from the office of Nobel Nominee Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.); RMIT University, Australia (M. A. Hossain, 2023f)

A full information and evidence of life-threatening conspiracy and history of long-term harassment in Australian PhD school was sent to the office of foreign minister of Australia, relevant offices and professional communities. Ms. Penny Wong, Foreign minister of Australia; and Ms. Paula Ganly, First Assistant Secretary, Consular and Crisis Management Division, Department of Foreign Affairs and Trade should pay the penalty of 2,00,000 Australian penalty units if they are neglecting the international service, if they are neglecting and delaying the public service, if the office of foreign minister in Australia is neglecting and delaying the public service (M. A. Hossain, 2023f). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should have a legal right and legal authorization to access the ready platform of public service. Nobody should have right to cease the rights of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Nobody should cease the money/salary of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, he also needs living and food allowance. RMIT should not cease single dollar from the pocket of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Nobody should plan to kill the researcher. Nobody should harass the merit growth of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Every Australian PhD scholar should have right to access the office of foreign minister of Australia. Every Australian PhD scholar should have right to access the legal aid fund/welfare fund/research fund of foreign minister. This is not begging to the minister and secretary, this is the legal rights of the Australian PhD scholar, this is also the beneficiary rights of the citizen (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024b; Hossain, 2025d). How many complaint letters did they get/receive in her public service like the request letter from Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, foreign minister and foreign secretary of Australia should prove to the relevant court to signify their busy schedule/manpower shortage/secretary shortage in their office of public service? If they are doing service offence, they should pay the 'compensation award' to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) (M. A. Hossain, 2023f). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) should have legal rights to use the administrative desk of foreign minister and foreign secretary if foreign minister and foreign secretary can claim their self-designation of foreign ministry of Australia if foreign minister and foreign secretary can claim their self-salary of foreign ministry of Australia. This is the administrative supremacy of democracy and advocacy of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.).

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assisit. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assisit. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assisit. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	---	--

6.11 Symptom of zero responsibility of Ms. Michelle Rowland, MP, Attorney General/Law Minister of Australia; and Mr. Mark Dreyfus, KC, MP, Attorney General/Law Minister of Australia; legal notice to the law ministers and attorney general of Australia from the office of Nobel Nominee Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.); RMIT University, Australia (M. A. Hossain, 2023f; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024b)

A full information and evidence of life-threatening conspiracy and history of long-term harassment in Australian PhD school was sent to the office of attorney general, law minister, education minister, home affairs minister, Victoria legal aid, high commissioner of Australia in Bangladesh, prime minister of Australia, relevant offices and professional communities. Ms. Michelle Rowland, MP, Attorney General/Law Minister of Australia; and Mr. Mark Dreyfus, KC, MP, Attorney General/Law Minister of Australia should pay the penalty of 2,00,000 Australian penalty units if they are neglecting the international service, if they are neglecting and delaying the public service, if the office of law minister is neglecting and delaying the public service (A. Hossain, 2023; M. A. Hossain, 2023f; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024b). Who is the chief legal advisor of Australia if Ms. Michelle Rowland is the attorney general of Australia? Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should have a legal right and legal authorization to access the ready platform of public service. Nobody should have right to cease the rights of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Nobody should cease the money/salary of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, he also needs living and food allowance. RMIT should not cease single dollar from the pocket of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Nobody should plan to kill the researcher. Nobody should harass the merit growth of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Every Australian PhD scholar should have right to access the office of law minister and attorney general. Every Australian PhD scholar should have right to access the legal aid fund/welfare fund/research fund of law minister. This is not begging to the minister, this is the legal rights of the citizen, this is also the beneficiary rights of the citizen (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024b; Hossain, 2025d). How many complaint letters did law minister get/receive in his public service like the request letter from Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, law minister should prove to the relevant court to signify his/her busy schedule/manpower shortage/secretary shortage in his/her office of public service? If they are doing service offence, they should pay the 'compensation award' to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) (M. A. Hossain, 2023f). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) should have legal rights to use the administrative desk of law ministers if law ministers can claim their self-designation of law ministry of Australia if law ministers and attorney generals can claim their self-salary of law ministry of Australia. This is the administrative supremacy of democracy and advocacy of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.).

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

6.12 Symptom of zero responsibility of Dr. Kamal Uddin Ahmed, Chairman, Human Rights Commission, Bangladesh; legal notice to the chairman of human rights commission from the office of Nobel Nominee Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.); RMIT University, Australia (M. A. Hossain, 2023f; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024b)

Page | 28

A full information and evidence of life-threatening conspiracy and history of long-term harassment in Australian PhD school was sent to the office of human rights commission of Bangladesh, prime minister/chief advisor of Bangladesh, president of Bangladesh, attorney general's department of Bangladesh, ministry of foreign affairs in Bangladesh, high commissioner of Bangladesh in Australia, high commissioner of Australia in Bangladesh, relevant offices and professional communities. Dr. Kamal Uddin Ahmed, Chairman, Human Rights Commission, Bangladesh should pay the penalty of 1,00,000 Australian penalty units if he is neglecting the international service, if he is neglecting and delaying the public service, if the office of human rights commission is neglecting and delaying the public service (M. A. Hossain, 2023bw) (M. A. Hossain, 2023f; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024b, 2024k). What is the purpose of human rights commission? What should be the purpose of human rights commission? Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should have a legal right and legal authorization to access the ready platform of public service. Nobody should have right to cease the human rights of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Nobody should cease the money/salary of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, he also needs living and food allowance. RMIT should not cease single dollar from the pocket of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Nobody should plan to kill the researcher. Nobody should harass the merit growth of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Every citizen should have right to access the office of chairman. Every citizen should have right to access the legal aid fund/welfare fund/research fund of chairman. This is not begging to the chairman, this is the legal rights of the citizen, this is also the beneficiary rights of the citizen (Hossain, 2025d). How many complaint letters did chairman get/receive in his public service like the request letter from Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain; chairman of human rights commission should prove to the relevant court to signify his busy schedule/manpower shortage/secretary shortage in his office of public service? If he is doing service offence, he/she should pay the 'compensation award' to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) (M. A. Hossain, 2023f). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) should have legal rights to use the administrative desk of chairman of human rights commission if chairman can claim his self-designation of chairman of human rights commission of Bangladesh if chairman can claim his self-salary of human rights commission of Bangladesh. This is the administrative supremacy of democracy and advocacy of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.).

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anwar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCME College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anwar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anwar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	--	--

6.13 Symptom of zero responsibility of Mr. Hugh de Kretser, President, Human Rights Commission, Australia; legal notice to the president of human rights commission from the office of Nobel Nominee Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.); RMIT University, Australia (M. A. Hossain, 2023f; Md. Anwar Hossain, 2024b)

A full information and evidence of life-threatening conspiracy and history of long-term harassment in Australian PhD school was sent to the office of human rights commission of Australia, prime minister of Australia, governor general of Australia, law minister of Australia, attorney general of Australia, high commissioner of Bangladesh in Australia, high commissioner of Australia in Bangladesh, RMIT university of Australia, local police station of Australia, local ministerial cabinet of Melbourne/Victoria, St. Vincent hospital in Melbourne, relevant offices and professional communities. Mr. Hugh de Kretser, President, Human Rights Commission, Australia should pay the penalty of 1,00,000 Australian penalty units if he is neglecting the international service, if he is neglecting and delaying the public service, if the office of human rights commission is neglecting and delaying the public service (M. A. Hossain, 2023bw) (M. A. Hossain, 2023f; Md. Anwar Hossain, 2024b, 2024k). What is the purpose of human rights commission? What should be the purpose of human rights commission? Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain should have a legal right and legal authorization to access the ready platform of public service. Nobody should have right to cease the rights of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain. Nobody should cease the money/salary of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, he also needs living and food allowance. RMIT should not cease single dollar from the pocket of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain. Nobody should plan to kill the researcher. Nobody should harass the merit growth of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain. Every Australian PhD scholar should have right to access the office of president of human rights commission. Every Australian PhD scholar should have right to access the legal aid fund/welfare fund/research fund of president. This is not begging to the president, this is the legal rights of the PhD scholar, this is also the beneficiary rights of the PhD scholar(Hossain, 2025d). How many complaint letters did president get/receive in his public service like the request letter from Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain; president of human rights commission should prove to the relevant court to signify his busy schedule/manpower shortage/secretary shortage in his office of public service? If he is doing service offence, he should pay the ‘compensation award’ to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) (M. A. Hossain, 2023f). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) should have legal rights to use the administrative desk of president of human rights commission if president can claim his self-designation of president of human rights commission of Australia if president can claim his self-salary of human rights commission of

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia
Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anwar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Australia. This is the administrative supremacy of democracy and advocacy of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.).

6.14 Symptom of zero responsibility of Professor Dr. Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University, Australia; Professor Dr. Calum Drummond, Deputy Vice Chancellor, Research & Innovation, and Vice president, RMIT; Dr. Karien Dekker, Associate Professor and HDR Director, RMIT; Professor Dr. Robyn Healy, Former Dean, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT; Professor Dr. Alice Payne, Dean, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT; Dr. Andrea Eckersley, HDR Coordinator, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT; Dr. Scott Mayson, Associate Dean, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT; Dr. Sean Ryan, ethics and integrity concern/officer, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT; Professor Dr. Lijing Wang and Emeritus Professor Dr. Robert Shanks, PhD supervisor, RMIT; legal notice to them to the administrative officers/professors of RMIT University from the office of Nobel Nominee Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.); RMIT University, Australia (M. A. Hossain, 2023f; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024b)

Page | 30

A full information and evidence of life-threatening conspiracy and history of long-term harassment in Australian PhD school was sent to Professor Dr. Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University, Australia; Professor Dr. Calum Drummond, Deputy Vice Chancellor, Research & Innovation, and Vice president, RMIT; Dr. Karien Dekker, Associate Professor and HDR Director, RMIT; Professor Dr. Robyn Healy, Former Dean, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT; Professor Dr. Alice Payne, Dean, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT; Dr. Andrea Eckersley, HDR Coordinator, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT; Dr. Scott Mayson, Associate Dean, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT; Dr. Sean Ryan, ethics and integrity concern/officer, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT; Professor Dr. Lijing Wang and Emeritus Professor Dr. Robert Shanks, PhD supervisor, RMIT. Everyone should pay the penalty of 1,00,000 Australian penalty units if they are neglecting the international student service and research service, if they are neglecting and delaying the student service, if the office of PhD school is neglecting and delaying the public service, if the office of PhD school is cheating with the student service (M. A. Hossain, 2023bc, 2023bx; M. A. Hossain, 2023c). What is the purpose of school administration? What should be the purpose of school professors? Who should take care School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT? What should be the purpose of the prestigious designations in PhD school? These are not the posts of joking and joking, display and display, and showcase and showcase. These are not only the posts of public service; these are the posts of researcher and scientist service. Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should have a legal right and legal authorization to access the ready platform of public service in Australian PhD school. Nobody should have right to cease the rights of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain.

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.). Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.348831</p>	
---	--	--

Nobody should cease the money/salary of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, he also needs living and food allowance. RMIT should not cease single dollar from the pocket of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Nobody should plan to kill the researcher. Nobody should harass the merit growth of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.). Every Australian PhD scholar should have right to access the office of administration in Australian PhD school. This is not begging to the school administration/university administration; this is the legal rights of the PhD scholar. How many complaint letters did they get/receive in their public service like the request letter from Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain; school administration and university administration should individually prove to the relevant court to signify their busy schedule/manpower shortage/secretary shortage in their office of public service? If they are doing service offence, they should pay the ‘compensation award of RMIT’ to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) (M. A. Hossain, 2023f). A scientist requested safety support to Professor Dr. Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor of RMIT University. A scientist requested safety against international criminal against Australian criminal. What was the duty of vice chancellor and delegates? Professor Dr. Alec Cameron should convince, notify, clarify, and glorify to the global community. Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) should have legal rights to use the administrative desk of administrative officers/professors if administrative officers/professors can claim their self-designation of RMIT University if administrative officers/professors can claim their self-salary of RMIT University if administrative officers/professors can claim their self-prestige of RMIT University. This is the administrative supremacy of democracy and advocacy of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.).

6.14.1 Recommendation of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) (M. A. Hossain, 2023g, 2023bx; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x) to the ministerial cabinet of Australia, prime minister of Australia, government of Australia; United Nations

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain will not approve single PhD thesis of RMIT Professor if they can not ensure the quality of PhD thesis and quality of PhD evidence like the PhD thesis of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain will not approve single promotion of RMIT Professor if they can not ensure the quality of research and quality of evidence like Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Moreover, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is not getting the access of any promotion law of the website of RMIT University. What is the disgusting situation in RMIT academia? Who should take care the RMIT academia? Every RMIT professor should display and display their PhD thesis, PhD evidence, and promotion evidence to their researcher community, without which their PhD and promotion should

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia
Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

be banned, without which the whole occurrence should be treated as the cheating with their public service with their researcher community with their student community with the government of Australia with the prime minister of Australia with the ministerial cabinet of the Australia, without which the assessment service should be treated as the cheating with their public service with their researcher community with their student community in Australia, without which the offence should be punishable of 1,00,000 Australian penalty units. Therefore, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is urgently requesting to the ministerial cabinet of Australia to assess the whole professor/Dr. of RMIT University in terms of their PhD thesis, PhD evidence, and promotion evidence (M. A. Hossain, 2023g, 2023bx; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x). Moreover, every RMIT Professor/Dr. who are owning and controlling the RMIT administration should send their bachelor, master, and PhD thesis, quality evidence of their research degree, quality evidence of RMIT promotion to the office of Chief Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, RMIT, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com) as Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is not getting the evidence in their website in the RMIT website. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is attaching and publicly submitting his sole author and sole funded contribution at RMIT University, Australia (M. A. Hossain, 2023g, 2023au, 2023bx; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024f, 2024o, 2024p, 2024t, 2024u, 2024v, 2024x, 2024z; Hossain, 2025a, 2025b, 2025c; Nobel Nominee Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, 2025). Similarly, the whole evidences of promotion and PhD thesis should be submitted by the next month. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is also planning to submit the assessment report to the high court of Australia and/or international court. Every promotion file should be/will be peer reviewed under the scholarly evidence and quality evidence. If they had no PhD at RMIT, if their PhD quality is poorer than PhD at RMIT quality, they should not continue single day at RMIT. Single PhD at RMIT should not pass at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University without the valid approval/peer review of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain since 2021. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should not take the lifelong professional liability of RMIT brand, figure 2. He is tired and tried to take/establish the liability of brand value(Hossain, 2025f). Presently, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is more qualified than the brand of RMIT University. Every RMIT professor should respect the peer review process, transparency of research degree, genuine performance, and genuine practice of research excellency. Until the final assessment report of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain; their degree, promotion, and PhD thesis should be suspended and suspended. Until the final decision of court; their degree, promotion, and PhD thesis should be suspended and suspended. Nobody should cheat with the brand value of RMIT. Nobody should expect single benefit/additional benefit for the research degree and research promotion. Nobody should imagine single benefit for the research degree and research promotion. Nobody should misguide the RMIT students and researchers. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is writing and writing, debating and debating with the ministerial cabinet of Australia to ensure the right

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	---	--

support, food support, living cost support, marriage/sex support to the professor community. Nobody should think to misguide the RMIT students and researchers. Professor Dr. Alec Cameron is the registered administrative chief of RMIT University, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is not the administrative chief of RMIT University, but Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is serving and serving on behalf of the chief administrative ethics and morality of RMIT University, but Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is getting the award of ‘killing conspiracy and conspiracy of killing’ instead of monthly salary instead of monthly allowance instead of monthly stipend. What is the ugly situation of a knowledge industry in Australia at RMIT? Who should ensure the protection to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain? If Professor Dr. Alec Cameron is getting salary from RMIT University, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should also get salary from RMIT University. Therefore, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.); Chief Director and Founder, Textile, Defence, and Law Research Centre, RMIT; Chief Defence Scientist, Textile, Defence, and Law Research Centre, RMIT; Chief Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain’s Knowledge Industry, RMIT, Australia is self-nominating the next vice chancellor of RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x). Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was the chief qualified person at RMIT when former vice chancellor nominated for the Nobel nominee of vice chancellor, RMIT University since 2021(M. A. Hossain, 2023g, 2023bx). Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is shouting and shouting to the prime minister and education minister of Australia and UN.

Let’s build the RMIT.

Let’s protect the RMIT.

Let’s make a criminal free RMIT.

Let’s make a snake and tiger free RMIT.

Let’s force to make a criminal free RMIT.

Let’s show weapon and weapon to make a criminal free RMIT.

Let’s destroy and dispose the criminal gang of RMIT.

Let’s make a quality platform of quality higher education centre at RMIT.

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

6.14.2 RMIT University and/or education department of Australia and/or Australian government should pay the secretary allowance and/or twin PhD allowance of 20,000 USD per month to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) since 6 July 2022 (M. A. Hossain, 2023f, 2023bc; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024i)

Page | 34

Every public service is run by secretary. Every office is operated by secretary. Every office of CEO is executed by secretary. Every office of prime minister is run by secretary. Every office of president is run by secretary. Equationally it is being established that no secretary = no service. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain wrote numerous letters to attract to ensure to motivate to convince the public service of Australian government. These are not major duties of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain at RMIT University. Education department of Australia should pay the international standard allowance to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Education department of Australia should pay the secretary allowance and/or twin PhD allowance of 20,000 USD per month (in words: twenty thousand USD) to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024i). Education department should pay the senior professor category secretary allowance and/or twin PhD allowance. It should be the additional income support of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain except the genuine salary of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain except the senior professor/chief professor graded salary of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in Australia. Practically and possibly; every chief executive officers have no time to read/reply the letters of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain to satisfy the public service to satisfy the action and support to satisfy the judicial support to the citizen. This letter is the evidence of ministerial performance of the Australia. Practically and possibly, secretary reads/replies based on personal benefit/professional benefit/follow-up of the political leaders/follow-up of the CEO/campaign of the journalists/the campaign of newspapers rather than personal salary. Practically and possibly, personal salary of executive officer has no priority in the job of public service, personal salary is an automatic income of public service, monthly salary has no value, yearly salary has no value. Possibly, there is vigorous priority of functions in public service, such as: personal benefit, professional benefit, additional benefit, political benefit, follow-up of political leaders, follow-up of the CEO, the campaign of journalists, bamboo showing and campaign or slogan of the public, banner showing and campaign/slogan of the public, newspaper campaign, campaign/slogan of harming attitude of public, bloody campaign/slogan of public. Therefore, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should get the full office allowance of an administrative office of an international category professor when Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was sacrificing and sacrificing the quality of lifestyle to satisfy the public service of Australian government (M. A. Hossain, 2023bx, 2023cf; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024i).

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominer Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assisit. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assisit. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assisit. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	---	--

6.15 Legal approach of death penalty of Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye in public place, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Australia; a victim impact statement is quoted from the article of Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x) (M. A. Hossain, 2023f)

This is a remarkable and hyper contribution of doctoral research of Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in applied law. This is a notice of research summery to Australian high court and/or international court for the judicial assessment, recommendation, and administrative approval in Australia. The criminal conspiracy was officially registered and/or notified and/or submitted to the office of prime minister of Australia, president and chief advisor of Bangladesh (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k) (M. A. Hossain, 2023bw), president of United States of America (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k); office of vice chancellor, dean, and professor community, RMIT University, Australia (M. A. Hossain, 2023bc); office of relevant ministers and ministries in Australia and Bangladesh (M. A. Hossain, 2023bc); office of high court of Australia (M. A. Hossain, 2023a, 2023c); office of secretary general and president of UN (Hossain, 2025g); international lawyer's communities; international human rights communities; officials of international court; international professor communities; and relevant judicial and non-judicial authorities in Australia, Bangladesh, and other countries. Recorded, registered, and postered the crimes and keywords at the defence project of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Australia. Recorded and listed the functions and symptoms of death penalty for routine harming to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, such as: academic injury; brain injury; professional injury; reputation injury in profession; injury of quality of lifestyle; injury of family life; injury of normal life; targeted Bangladeshi scholar and/or scholars; harmed the knowledge culturing of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in RMIT PhD school in Australian PhD school; police harassment; sex harassment; mental health harassment; home laboratory harassment; PhD laboratory harassment; tried to make artificial relationship injury between PhD researcher and PhD supervisor; tried to make confuse the PhD supervisors; tried to make confuse the PhD outcomes, scholarly outcomes, and PhD contributions; research harassment and harming; tried to damage/kill the research blossoming of Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain; student rights harassment and harming; researcher rights harassment and harming; applying the practice and target of human limitation and routine harming; PhD friendship harassment; life-long safety harassment; PhD conspiracy forwarded to Bangladesh; Bangladeshi criminal; Australian criminal; international crime offender; laptop and mobile phone IP tracking and monitoring (a mobile phone and laptop are dangerous for a person when hackers or professional criminals can track the mobile phone and/or phone number and/or laptop to identify the location); personal life tracking of PhD researcher; hacking laptop during the presentation of confirmation of PhD candidature at RMIT PhD school; mobile phone hacking; communication monitoring; high-risk gang against the life-time safety and income of Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain; high-risk gang against the human peace;

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

academic/professional file missing alarm/information/notification from the residence of Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in Bangladesh; tried to confuse the reputation and achievement from nursery schooling to Postdoc schooling; tried to confuse the reputation and achievement in the name of sex harassment and family harassment; clamorous practice in RMIT PhD school in Australian PhD school; critically monitored the family relation and attacked in multidimensional way of harassment; critically monitored the official relation and attacked in multidimensional way of harassment; acted against the service aim and research goal of RMIT University; acted against the service aim of Australian government and/or Australian education department; sincerely or dishonestly served opposition of the reputation of RMIT University; acted opposition of PhD suspension policy; acted opposition of RMIT action and support policy; acted opposition of RMIT research support policy; targeted to Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain to make a physically, socially, officially, internationally, professionally, and financially challenged person; locked the PhD finance and PhD service when necessary; locked the health insurance when necessary; sincerely, officially, and professionally harassed, confused, neglected, and bulleted the general relation between PhD student and PhD professor, between PhD student and PhD colleague in PhD school; applied professional technique to confuse the people and continuing the crimes; served against the Australian PhD compliance at RMIT; served against the reputation of Australian higher education; served against the reputation of professor community; acted opposition of research service at RMIT University; acted opposition of RTP in PhD school; unofficially and illegally showed the directorship of School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University against the central chain of administrative command or service of RMIT and/or education department of Australian government; high-risk gang against the peace in PhD school; high-risk misconduct in PhD school; life-time income harassment of Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain; research laboratory harassment; administrative blackmail in PhD school; hacking normal life journey; relationship hacking in PhD school; showed robbery attitude; showing force and threatening attitude in PhD school; intentional target; intentional crime; sole author crime in PhD school; PhD scholarship target; PhD funding target; Australian bank account target and monitoring; Bangladeshi bank account target and monitoring; family target; quality brainstorming harassment in PhD journey; research location and study place harassment and official target; PhD school harassment; PhD quality harassment; tried and talked to involve thesis writing of another research student in RMIT PhD school; PhD supervisor harassment; PhD material harassment; PhD achievement harassment; human rights harassment; targeted PhD (RMIT), Australia; targeted RMIT earning; PhD climbing harassment; relationship conspiracy; cyber-attack; mobile phone call and mobile phone message monitoring; possibility of duplicate phone call and/or duplicate introducing and/or duplicate way of convincing to surrounding people in different way; e-mail monitoring and negatively action; laptop monitoring and artificial harassing; family connection, monitoring, and harming; relationship monitoring; mastering in confusing; mastering in crimes in RMIT PhD school; executed slavery writing in non-

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assis. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assis. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assis. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assis. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	---	--

paid duty at RMIT in PhD³, unethical directorship in PhD school; director of professional criminals or gang; crimes in thinking; crimes in verbal techniques; practiced directorial technique of killing PhD study; practiced directorial technique of killing PhD researcher; practiced Australian government technique of killing PhD researcher; practiced directorial technique of killing PhD motivation; Australian gang connection; Bangladeshi gang connection; possibly the gang is well oriented and well administrative (non-government); neglected and confused the student service and/or research service at RMIT University; journal and publication harassment; financial harassment; chain crime; education crime; chain education crime; sex crime; chain and chain sex crime; sex business; chain and chain sex business; tried to make blackmail to researcher/researchers in the name of sex in the name of sex talking; crime of verbal threatening; movement tracking in Melbourne city; movement tracking in Dhaka city; residential tracking in Melbourne and Dhaka City and negatively action and harming to PhD candidate at RMIT; long-term administrative conspiracy in RMIT PhD school; ‘mother bullying’ in RMIT PhD school; ‘sex bullying’ in PhD school; ‘wife bullying’ in RMIT PhD school; ‘supervisor bullying’ in PhD school; Dr. Saniyat Islam talking/bullying in PhD school; Dr. Abdur Rahman talking/bullying in PhD school; Dr. Abu Shaid talking/bullying in PhD school; Bangladeshi teacher talking/bullying in PhD school; vice chancellor, City University talking/bullying in PhD school; Mr. Ravi talking/bullying in PhD school; Mr./Ms. Sharif talking/bullying in PhD school; Mr./Ms. Arif talking/bullying in PhD school; connected with Bangladeshi and Indian researcher/colleagues and spreading the illegal approach and bullying; ‘publication authorship bullying to put name’ in sole author PhD publication of Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain; ‘illegal bullying to put name’ in sole author PhD publication of Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain; ‘force attitude of bullying to put name’ in sole author PhD publication of Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain; a powerful, illegal, and administrative disturbance in PhD school; Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain had almost zero problem in PhD school, but Professor Rajiv Padhye artificially created a lot of problems in RMIT PhD school in Australian PhD school in life time journey; executed crimes of few death penalty in Australian PhD school; crimes of high penalty units in Australian PhD school; crimes of few life time prison in Australian PhD school; silence of RMIT vice chancellor; silence of RMIT PhD supervisor; marriage life harassment in RMIT PhD school; tried to cease Australian VISA rights; tried to cease Australian rights; tried to cease Bangladeshi rights; tried to cease Australian PhD rights; tried to cease sole author PhD publication rights, tried to cease PhD and Postdoc dream in Australia; created disaster symptom in RMIT PhD school in Australian PhD school instead of mastering in technology; tried to cease PhD and Postdoc rights; tried to cease sole author research recognition in PhD school; possibly connected with Australian citizen/Bangladeshi citizen/permanent residence Australian VISA holder; tried to cease personal goal and ambition rights; forced to defence scientist to be camouflage; forced to the director of defence project to be camouflage scientist; forced to the director of PhD research to be camouflage; forced to the Nobel

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Nominee to be camouflage; forced to the PhD scholar to be camouflage; crimes of PhD colleagues connection in PhD school; crimes of medical practitioner connection in Australia and Bangladesh; connection with mental health practitioner in Australia and Bangladesh; crimes and conspiracy in the name of mental health support; Professor connection; official demotivation to PhD researcher; financial injury in PhD journey; financial harassment during the pregnant moment of PhD invention; killing conspiracy in the pregnant moment of PhD invention; killing conspiracy in knowledge culturing moment in RMIT PhD school; PhD material conspiracy in the pregnant moment of PhD invention; life time target and harassment of mobile phone call recording and e-mail monitoring, it is highly embarrassing, disturbing and routine harming to lead a normal life of any person; harming to Bangladesh; harming to Australia; harming to scholar community; routine breach of PhD rules and regulations; routine breach of researcher rules and regulations; neglected the long term PhD investment of Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain; routine breach of Australian quality of research framework in RMIT PhD school in Australian PhD school; routine breach of academic and professional behavior; long-term harassment in Australian residency; scholarship injury in PhD journey; critical brain engineering practice against the normal thinking; having expertise to find out human limitations to apply brain engineering and practicing crimes; critical brain engineering against the peace in PhD school; illegal PhD suspension and artificial tendency of PhD killing; destroyed, damaged, and massacred the economy of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain; created food crisis of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain; created residential crisis of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain; created the crisis of PhD education of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain; created the crisis of medical support of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain; created the crisis of clothing of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain; created the crisis of recreation of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain; simultaneous attack with multidimensional philosophy of intentional crimes, professional, directorial, and official sincerity in crimes, phone crimes, connection with different peoples and showing illegal benefits in different motivation; motivating surrounding peoples of target person under different beneficial angle of talking and/or other unknown business support; showed crime engineering in talking; motivating and managing official peoples in Bangladesh and Australia under different beneficial angle of engineering and talking and/or other unknown business support; the penalty for long term intentional conspiracy (cool brain engineering) in academic, profession, family, personal, criminal conspiracy, and hidden conspiracy of life-threatening; symptom of tragedy in RMIT PhD school in Australian PhD school; talking with engineering/crimes between Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain and Dr. Abu Shaid; talked with engineering/crimes between Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain and Dr. Saniyat Islam; talked with engineering/crimes between Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain and Dr. Engr. Md. Abdur Rahman Bhuiyan; talked with engineering/crimes between Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain and Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang; approached or told about 'sex ID card policy' (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024s) in RMIT PhD school in Australian

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	--	--

PhD school (Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was not a relevant committee member); officially harassed and officially conspired to get Australian medical support in Melbourne; verbal threatened about action and support in PhD school, successfully and sincerely applied about the negative impact of action and support at RMIT; talked to include Bangladeshi PhD supervisor; talked to marry three ladies of different countries like one Bangladeshi lady and one Bangladeshi wife in Bangladesh, one Indian lady and one Indian wife in India, one Australian lady and Australian wife in Australia; St. Vincent hospital/nurse/Dr./ambulance connection to kill Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in emergency patient service centre; conspiracy to cease intellectual property of PhD research outcomes and/or PhD scholar and/or PhD scholars; harmed simultaneously, parallelly, psychologically, academically, and professionally to kill PhD candidate, Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in RMIT PhD school; artificially generated parallel risk for the safety and employment of Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in Bangladesh and Australia; friendship harassment in RMIT PhD school; Professor Rajiv Padhye verbally approached new PhD supervisor in PhD school; connection with Coburg family medical centre in Melbourne; possibly open a duplicate e-mail address (hossains3820066@student.rmit.edu.au) in RMIT PhD school, but Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is the owner of e-mail address (s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au) since 2020 in RMIT PhD school; misguided to PhD supervisors; Bangladesh connection; possibly the brain of Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye is dissolved in the crime bath; connection with international criminal group; sincere conspiracy opposing to professional climbing of Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in PhD school; administrative controlling and harassment against the peace of a PhD candidate against the research climbing of a PhD candidate against the life-safety of a PhD candidate against the academic surviving of a PhD candidate against the professional surviving of a PhD candidate against the peace in RMIT PhD school in Australian PhD school; and relevant crimes and numerous harassment in research and development in RMIT PhD school in Australian PhD school for legal claiming and approaching of death penalty of Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University. Accordingly, the whole gang should get death penalty who practiced or involved crimes with Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye (M. A. Hossain, 2023f, 2023g). Ten-point grading (1-10) of criminal conspiracy of Professor Rajiv Padhye is 10 (1 mean minimum crime grading and 10 mean maximum crime grading). It is also claimed to implement multidimensional penalty units and compensations in addition to highest punishment in Australia. For example of Australian criminal target, it can be said that “a forest tiger or predator goes away and goes away when the target animal is camouflage and camouflage, but the Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye does not go away when the PhD researcher is camouflage and camouflage.”

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Figure 2. Picture of Professor Rajiv Padhye, RMIT University

6.15.1 Recommended the type of death penalty to Professor Rajiv Padhye

Physical punishment in public place (grade 5) + death penalty in public place (grade 5); grade 0 = normal punishment, grade 5 = extreme punishment. Professor Rajiv Padhye planned and executed 5 graded intentional conspiracies/extreme graded conspiracies of life-threatening in Australian PhD school. Grade 0 = normal conspiracy, grade 5 = extreme conspiracy of killing conspiracy. Catching and understanding the conspiracy is so tough for the department of criminal investigation/lawyers/justice/country/UN. The symptoms of life-threatening conspiracy are extreme conspiracy, habitual conspiracy, professional conspiracy, bloody conspiracy, and found connection with the international gang to attempt repeated murder to attempt repeated crimes. Figure 2, RMIT University, Australia should delete the name of Professor Rajiv Padhye from the website of School of Fashion and Textiles under the assessment support of vice chancellor nominated committee of RMIT University and/or Australian court and/or international court. The complaint of life-threatening conspiracy was submitted in parallel to the administration of Vice Chancellor and school administration on 24 January 2022. The complaint of life-threatening conspiracy was submitted in parallel to Australia, Bangladesh, and UN. This picture was cited from the website of RMIT University on 21 August 2025. Therefore, RMIT University and school administration showed zero responsibility about the complaint of life-threatening conspiracy to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.). These are the symptom and long-term practice of high-risk misconduct and non-administrative culture of RMIT University, Australia when the university had/has an active post of vice chancellor and administrative formulation of RMIT University (M. A. Hossain, 2023f, 2023as, 2023bc; M. A. Hossain, 2023c).

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.),
Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*}
Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
M.Tech Textile Engg (CU, India), B.Sc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process,
color engg), applied law & criminology
Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)*
Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)*
Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg
& Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam);
Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and
Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.348831>

6.16 Legal approach of ‘PhD compensation award of Australian government’ of 8390000 Australian penalty units (230,72,50,000AUD) and billionaire (Australia); quoted from the article of Barrister (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain (M. A. Hossain, 2023f; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x)

This is a contribution of doctoral research of Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in applied law. This is a notice of research summary to Australian high court and/or international court for the judicial assessment, recommendation and approval. The ‘PhD compensation award’ was officially registered and/or notified and/or submitted to the office of prime minister, Australia (M. A. Hossain, 2023bw), office of president of Bangladesh (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k), office of president of United States of America (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k); office of vice chancellor, Dean, and professor community, RMIT University (M. A. Hossain, 2023bc); office of relevant ministers and ministries in Australia and Bangladesh; office of high court of Australia; office of secretary general and president of UN; international human rights communities; officials of international court; international professor communities; international lawyer’s communities; and relevant judicial and non-judicial authorities in Australia, Bangladesh, and other countries. Recorded, registered, and postered the compensations and keywords at the defence project of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain at RMIT University, Australia. Recorded the indications of ‘PhD compensation award of Australian government’ of 8390000 Australian penalty units (230,72,50,000AUD). The proposed award to Australian government for numerous research and development; life-time safety (100 years) support; life-time income support; PhD research harassment in RMIT PhD school in Australian PhD school; neglecting of legal rights for the legal review of hidden life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT University; neglecting of legal funding and legal insurance for the legal action of hidden life-threatening conspiracy; neglecting of human rights for the legal review of hidden life-threatening conspiracy; fees of self-barristering, legal fees, legal convincing, scholarly convincing, long term crime analysis charges, long term duration crime reporting charges; contribution to Australian government to eliminate academic crimes; contribution to Australian legal rights; contribution to Australian human rights; contribution to Australian PhD rights; contribution to Australian PhD community; contribution to Australian crime investigation department; contribution to Australian police; contribution to Australian defence; contribution to Australian law implementation department, such as: claimed compensation and death penalty; contribution to Australian higher education; contribution to RMIT University, Australia; contribution to Australian professor community; contribution to Australian researcher and scientist community; contribution to Australian PhD quality; contribution to Australian quality of research framework; contribution to Australian home affairs; contribution to Australian foreign affairs; contribution to Australian public administration; contribution to international students in Australia; contribution to Australian education service; contribution to education conspiracy in Australia; contribution to Australian peace in education;

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

contribution to Australian cyber-crimes; contribution to scholarship motivation in Australia; contribution to Australian PhD salary or PhD stipend; contribution to life-style of Australian PhD researchers; contribution to Australian courts; contribution to Australian organizations of education quality assessment; contribution to legal aid support in Australia; contribution to Australian RTP scholars; contribution to international legal aid support in Australia to RTP scholars; contribution to the negative impact of student killing in the name of psychologist support in academia; contribution against the professional confusing against professional ethics of psychologists; contribution against the professional confusing against professional ethics of professors; contribution against the professional confusing of medical practitioners, nurses, and hospital; contribution against the professional confusing of police; contribution to PhD mark sheets and certification process in Australian higher education; contribution to ministries and ministering in Australia, contribution to education compliance in Australia; contribution to student VISA harassment in Australia; contribution to the personal target and target killing in Australia; contribution to School of Fashion and Textiles of RMIT University; contribution to legal stipend to RTP scholars; contribution to google drive support to RTP scholars; contribution to research material support to RTP scholars; contribution to research support to RTP scholars; contribution to bank statement requirement of student VISA for RTP scholars; contribution to free-of-cost medical support and emergency medical support to RTP scholars; contribution to home safety support to RTP scholars; contribution to office safety support to RTP scholars; contribution to global talent permanent visa fees exemption to RTP scholars; contribution to PhD assessment policy to RMIT University; contribution to legal insurance support to RTP scholars; contribution to approach of standard fellowship support or financial support or safety support to 'Nobel nominee' of RMIT University; contribution to standard dress code to RMIT student and professor community; contribution to family history notification and official recording to PhD school to pursue PhD in Textile Technology; invention of Australian gang; contribution to eliminate Australian gang; contribution to official history notification and official recording to PhD school to pursue PhD in Textile Technology; contribution to PhD history notification and official recording to PhD school to pursue PhD in Textile Technology; contribution to convince critical biological factors of human sex and sex privacy in PhD school to pursue PhD in Textile Technology; contribution to the critical human factors for legal act, applied law and criminology to pursue PhD in Technology; self-investment and contribution for notification to UN and relevant offices to pursue PhD in Textile Technology; contribution to self-funded PhD and Postdoc in law and criminology at RMIT University; contribution to 'twin PhD & twin Postdoc in applied law and criminology' to pursue PhD in Textile Technology; contribution for the protection of Australian higher education; sacrificed quality of life; invention of criminal/criminals and approaches of relevant penalties in relevant articles of public administration in Australia to pursue PhD in Textile Technology (M. A. Hossain, 2023f, 2023g).

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anwar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCME College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anwar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	---	---

7 Discussion

7.1 Alarming of common mistake for the assessment of brand value of a university

Figure 3, by mistake, people honor the basket rather than gold inside the basket; a foolishness, blindness, and childness. For example, a basket has one Kg gold of Saudi Arabia. The gold is removed and replaced by one Kg Australian sand. So, what will be the value of the basket without having the gold inside the basket? If Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain tries to convince the customer that there was gold inside the basket, but the gold was replaced by the Australian sand. No customer will pay the value of the gold of Saudi Arabia; the customer will pay the value of Australian sand. Similarly, some universities may have high quality basket rather than scientists, researchers, and professors inside the university. So, if people respect the basket rather than scientist, researcher, and professor inside the university; this is a foolishness, blindness, and childness in academia, this is a drama in academia. Some people have a degree of gold basket, but they are not gold, but they are reciting the name of basket. For example, in the year 2021, there was a famous scientist/professor in the university, so the university brand is popular and famous in the branding after the death of the scientist after the death of the researcher, it is the wrong concept of the people for the person in the professor community; it is the concept of mistake, this is the concept of eye washing for the person in the professor community. So, every university and ministerial cabinet should take care and motivate the present scientist, present researcher, and present reputation of the university. So, every university and ministerial cabinet should take care to increase the safety/lifetime of the scientist. Nobody should keep a snake inside the basket. Snake will grow/produce snake and snake, knowledge will grow/produce knowledge and knowledge, ethical professor will grow/produce ethical professor and ethical professor. Therefore, every RMIT talent should shout and shout should afraid and afraid to snake for their self-protection, self-surviving, and self-climbing. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain is more qualified than the brand of RMIT University than the basket of RMIT. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain enrolled his name at RMIT for one PhD, but now he is the ambassador, he is the achiever of hundred and hundred PhD. University may have goat, cow, and snake beside the scholar behind the scientist. In general, everyone should not get the brand value of university. But practically, everyone gets the brand value of university. The brand value of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain is higher than RMIT brand value.

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Figure 3. *By mistake, people honor the basket rather than gold inside the basket; a foolishness, blindness, and childness.*

7.2 Every educated citizen/public servant/chief executive officer (CEO) should get a basic training in law, criminology, and bombing protocol

Certified and educated persons are numerous, but the genuine lighting of knowledge is comparatively minor and minor. People are just civilized by cloth and cloth, by textile and textile (M. A. Hossain, 2023as). People are just educated by certificate and certificate. People are civilized and educated by certificate. But people should be civilized and educated by law and ethics. But people should be civilized and educated by legal rights, human rights, ethical rights, thinking capability, humanitarian, public service, and zero-crime approach for the peace surviving in the planet for the right beauty and beauty of human being. Although human civilization is also a matter of natural psychophysics of human brain whatever can not be developed by training. People are doing crimes by habit by nature by psychology by addiction by situation by intention by planning by profit-loss policy of psychophysics. Every country should have a common course of basic training of law in secondary schooling and higher secondary schooling. Different government, non-government job, public service officer, CEO, prime minister, minister, president, high

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology</p> <p>Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia</p> <p>International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva</p> <p>Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	--	--

commissioner, and political leaders should have the pre-requirement of basic training in law and/or ministerial training in law. Without which a CEO graded person and educated citizen can not well understand the liability and accountability of the public service and public nursing. Possibly, everyone can understand the self-prestige of the self-designation, but everyone can not understand the right service against the self-designation. Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is recommending the right training of the CEO graded officials of the country/countries. UN may ensure the right training of public service officer, CEO, prime minister, minister, presidents, king/queen of the countries for the peace of mankind for the peace surviving on the planet. A specific credit hour of training should be completed by the CEO graded professionals of the countries/UN. An advanced training should be required to be minister, prime minister, and president of the country. An achievement of minimum grade point should be prerequisite of UN (M. A. Hossain, 2023f, 2023au; M. A. Hossain, 2023f, 2023g; M. A. Hossain, 2023ch, 2023ci).

7.3 A ministry should not be a service centre of politicians, a ministry should be the service centre of the public of the citizen

A ministry should not be a service centre of politicians; ministry should also be a service centre of public. A ministry should also be the service centre of a professor/scientist/researcher. Every labour get salary for their service. Similarly, professor, scientist, researcher should also get their right salary for their service and contribution. They also need living and food allowance. They also need marriage/sex allowance. They are also the unit of human being. The financial outcomes of a scholarly contributor should be higher than the financial outcomes of a criminal and/professional criminal. The scenery and situation should be globally designed, proved, established, activated, and displayed. The labour party of Australia should have a priority about the salary of scholarly service or scholarly profession in Australia. Practically, a writer may get an award of negligible price, a professor/researcher may get an award of negligible price, but the contributor spends thousands and thousands of hours for an award. No ministry, no government pay for the thousands and thousands of hours. These are the common scenery in the global platform. Award means the honor to the contributor. Maximum case, the award does not mean the actual financial support to the contributor. These are the drawback of the award and/or salary. But the contributor also needs the living and food allowance. As a results; writers, professors, scientists, and researchers suffer and suffer in lifetime and lifetime, they don't get genuine support of medical treatment, they should not continue their marriage life/sex life/family life due to the financial crisis; because they are not criminal, because they have no weapon, because they have no control of weapon, because their brain is reserved for the service and service, because their brain is reserved for the development and development, because their brain is reserved for the contribution and contribution. Moreover, they can not ensure their self-quality of their self-life due to the government limitation, but they also think and develop the technology and society but they also serve to develop the quality of life to develop the global surviving. A salary of a senior professor, a salary of a research category

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia
Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

professor should be higher than the prime minister/president/chief commander/secretary of any country under the legal act of UN. There are scope of research and development, right understanding, and right campaign. Possibly, a CEO have no time to read this letter of a professor, letter of life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school although a CEO is a public servant is a public chief but Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain invested his self-resource, self-planning, self-administration, non-government resource, self-risk, ongoing self-risk, self-thinking to write this letter to submit this letter to the office of CEO to the office of prime minister of Australia to the office of UN secretary general (M. A. Hossain, 2023f).

Page | 46

7.4 A robbery policy of a government should not be a standard policy of the government.

A robbery policy of a government should not be approved by the ministerial cabinet. There are enormous limitations in the name of standard policy of a government. Everywhere is robbery and robbery, robbery in Australia, robbery in Bangladesh, everywhere is weapon therapy, everywhere is threat and threat to the citizen. A ministry should be a symptom of peace and peace rather than robbery and robbery, threat and threat to the citizen. Who should take care the public service? Therefore, every parliament/ministerial cabinet should have ethical category person and professor (Dr.) category non-political person. Possibly, practically, and unfortunately; the number of ethical category professor (Dr.) is around 0-5%. Possibly, practically, and unfortunately the number of ethical category politician is around 0-5%. By chance, planet gets the ethical category person but the surrounding people tries to kill/conspire to ethical person for their self-protection for their self-establishment and self-achievements of crimes and climbing in the profession. Who should take care the situation? These are the major limitation of zero crime approach and zero crime theory of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.). In general, people should not respect the political party/community; people should respect a political person if he is an ethical if he is not a criminal. In general, people should not respect the professor community/university; people should respect a professor if he is an ethical if he is not a criminal. In general, people should not respect the researcher community/university; people should respect a researcher if he is an ethical if he is not a criminal.

7.5 Every CEO should have a reading room (M. A. Hossain, 2023f)

Every CEO has a tendency to rely to depend on newspaper, television, journalists, and different media of communication. Researchers are also serving accordingly. Delaying in assessment of public appeal may have the reason of shortage of manpower and/or personal negligence and/or stuff negligence and/or secretary negligence and/or negligence in chain of command and/or self-prestige to deny the citizen. Every CEO graded person and/or relevant office should pay the penalty due to self-negligence in international investigation. No CEO should deny their penalty, no CEO should apply their force to deny their penalty, no CEO should think to deny their penalty. If a person knows the exact meaning and responsibility of a CEO, he/she will not be interested to be a

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology</p> <p>Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia</p> <p>International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	---	--

CEO or a president or a prime minister or chief of the organization or chief of the community. Sometimes, CEO may forget the word of public service. These are the symptom of punishable offence and penalty. Sometimes, CEO may forget the word meaning of CEO. But the CEO is still saying and saying, showing and showing “I am the CEO, I am the president, I am the prime minister, I am the chairman, I am the secretary”. But the CEO is getting honour and privacy in terms of the designation. What is the meaning of CEO? What is the meaning of prime minister? What is the meaning of president? These are the post of action and support in special circumstances in critical circumstances. These are the post of a critical decision making when the subordinate stuffs are failing and failing when the colleagues are failing and failing when the members are failing and failing to make a comment. So, these are the post of VIP. So, VIP is VIP. So, these are not the designation of the general administrative officer. These are the post of highest commanding officer of any country. So, these are very prestigious designation. It seems that the CEO is a post of prestige and prestige, honour and honour; but the CEO is not accountable for the post of service; but nobody should complaint against the CEO against the prestige. There is scope of research, right thinking capability, psychological development, psychological adapting and obeying, real-life practice, and peace practice. Every political leader is a public service holder. Every public servant should continue the job for the salary for the public service for the well-being in the service for the self-respect in the service for the addiction in the service. They should not have any intention of additional income and/or personal benefit and/or deny the situation. If there is any hidden plan to earn additional money, this is the symptom of cheating with the citizen with the country with the community with the organization with the self-confidence with the self-prestige. The country/organization will destroy and destroy. So, every political campaign of election should be government paid. Every election and selection campaign should be government paid should be citizen paid. Every election and selection campaign should not be self-paid of the political leaders/community. These are the alarming situation to protect the scholarly dream and scholarly service of a politician. People can easily understand the self-prestige of the designated post of the top management, but people can not understand the public service. This is the critical attitude of the people of chief administration. Administration can force the citizen, but the administration can not serve the citizen. What is the addiction principle of administration? But everyone can not understand the self-accountability and self-responsibility. Every CEO is a post of nursing to the citizen. A CEO is not a post of forcing to the citizen. A CEO should serve to the citizen like a doctor/nurse is nursing to the patient but the patient is not afraid to the doctor/nurse. Australia should have a legal fund and research fund to eliminate crimes in Australia if Australia is Australia if Australia will be Australia if Australia is a member of UN. Australia should not patronize the criminal. Australia should not patronize the criminal in university in knowledge industry. Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should get a joint support of Australia, Bangladesh, UK, and UN. It seems that Bangladesh, Australia, and UN have no fund for

international legal aid-support for the person of financially victim for the person of officially victim for the person of long-term sufferer. Every government should have a support of international legal support and welfare fund/research fund without which the country policy is failing without which the UN policy is failing without which the international relation is failing without which the international platform is failing and failing without which the policy of international education is failing. Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is searching fund to offer 'ministerial research and training centre' at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia under the support of UN and/or Australia (M. A. Hossain, 2023bv; Hossain, 2025h). 100-150 hours training is necessary to serve as the member of a ministerial cabinet. These are the important post of decision making and implementing. So, the advanced training should be prerequisite to be a professional member of a ministerial cabinet of any country. These are not the post of joking; these are the post of surviving technique in the planet. All professional peoples are doing lifelong training in their profession. Similarly, ministerial peoples should also have training in profession for the support of their public service.

7.6 Practicing study room versus ministerial performance

Education and certificate mean the spending time in the reading room. But people forget the reading room after having the certificate. But people run and run, swim and swim, struggle and struggle in the life journey in the profession. But people forget the right meaning of education. But people still write the name of university in the profile. When a person is studying at University of Sydney/RMIT University, he/she is occupying a study room or reading room to satisfy the teachers to satisfy the gradation to satisfy the graduation to satisfy the employee of an organization. The person cites the name of university in his profile in his/her life long journey, but he/she may forget the practice of study room or reading room. If he/she can not practice the study room, he/she should not write the name of graduated university to confuse the community to confuse the profession to confuse the education. A degree is fulfilled after the practice in study room in profession. A degree is glorified and glorified after the practice in study room in profession. A study record or publication should also be very important part for the promotion in the public service for the ministerial promotion. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is searching research fund to analyze the ministerial promotion to analyze the ministerial performance to analyze the ministerial family of the political leaders of the public servants of different countries. What is the exact philosophy of the ministerial cabinet? Who is called educated person? Who is called university graduate? A person who can self-study and self-practice after the graduation who can access the reading room after the graduation who can enjoy the reading room after the graduation who can make a significant impact for the peace surviving after graduation who have no intention of cheating with the service or citizen. Every ministerial record in daily newspaper is

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology</p> <p>Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)³ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁴ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia</p> <p>International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva</p> <p>Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	--	--

not only the performance of a political leader or a public servant; these are also the scholarly performance of the journalists.

7.7 CEO is the CEO

Few responses of letters in the office desk of CEO may be self-remarked, self-follow up, self-planned, self-drafted, and self-edited by the CEO. These are also the scholarly performance of a CEO. Every letter should not be drafted by the secretary, so the secretary is not a CEO, so the prestige of a CEO is higher than the secretary. But every letter should be edited by the CEO if the CEO is the CEO if the CEO is an active CEO if the CEO is also liable for the office of CEO if the CEO is not a post of joking if the CEO is a post of honour if the CEO is a post of responsibility if the CEO is a post of prestige if the CEO is a post of ethics if the CEO is a post of chief administration if the CEO is a post of self-dedication if the CEO is a post of zero crime if the CEO is a post of biological morality if the CEO is a post of chief commanding officer if the CEO is a post prime minister if the CEO is a post of president if the CEO is a post of king/queen. In general, A CEO should be more qualified, more educated, more scholarly performer, more independent performer, more ethical than the secretary in the office in the organization in the country. So, the prestige of a CEO is higher than the secretary.

7.8 People/citizen salute to the VIP and CEO

Salary of a CEO is higher/should be higher. So, the responsibility of a CEO is also higher. Some CEO are playing football and football, but nobody is shooting to the goalkeeper for the genuine action and support to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, so nobody is the actual player in the playground of the CEO. Possibly, there is a matter of habitual trend of the time. This study tends that the bamboo slogan and destructive communication is more beneficial than the written request to satisfy the administration of a country to attract the administration of a country. If there was bamboo slogan or bloody slogan at Swanston Street or Sydney Road, Melbourne, Australia it was supposed to be a matter of government follow-up and government broadcasting. Possibly, top administration of a country prioritizes the bamboo slogan, bloody campaign, newspaper writing, journalist support, and media campaign. So, who will pay for the costs of bamboo slogan, bloody campaign, and journalists. These are also expensive way and destructive way of communication with the VIP and CEO. These are also the way of blood flowing communication with the VIP and CEO. A drop of blood is also a symptom of painful salute to the VIP and CEO. A drop of tear is also a symptom of painful salute to the VIP and CEO. A hungry moment of a researcher is also a symptom of painful salute to the VIP and CEO. A hungry moment of a professor is also a symptom of painful salute to the VIP and CEO. A crisis moment of a researcher is also a symptom of painful salute to the VIP and CEO. A writing moment of a researcher is also a symptom of painful salute to the VIP and CEO. An approaching a penalty unit to the VIP is also a symptom of painful salute to the VIP and CEO. Drafting and editing this legal notice to the VIP is also a symptom of painful

salute to the VIP and CEO. A moment of disease is also a symptom of painful salute to the VIP and CEO. But possibly, these are the established way of communication with VIP and CEO when administration has no urge/function/action and support of numerous written reports/appeals of a researcher when administration has no urge/function/action of a polite report of a researcher. The costs/investments of a researcher have no value. People try to kill/shoot researcher like shooting to bird. Possibly, a VIP respects/follow the bamboo slogan and destructive slogan rather than the written slogan than the written request. But the government can not take the full liability of a destructive communication of the citizen, but the citizen suffers and suffers. The global history and scenery are practically teaching to the people. A VIP should have an intention to stop the bamboo slogan to dislike the bamboo slogan to dislike the bloody slogan. Every bloody slogan is the destructive way of communication with the VIP. Prime minister is a VIP. President is a VIP. Chief advisor is a VIP. Ministers are VIP and VIP. High commissioners are VIP and VIP. Secretaries are VIP and VIP. So, everyone is VIP and VIP. So, VIP has no accountability and liability, this is the self-understanding of a VIP. These are not the post of display and showcase in the ministerial cabinet in the cabinet. But every VIP has secretaries and sectaries. So, VIP should not read the letter. So, this is not duty of a VIP. Subordinates of VIP/secretaries of VIP should read the letter should decide the letter for the action and support of the citizen. But professor dr. is not a VIP, but professor dr. is also a valid citizen of local community and global community. So, he should not get the food allowance and legal support, because he doesn't directly serve for the political leaders and/or professional criminals, he serves for the knowledge industry, he serves for the university. This letter is also a practice of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's knowledge industry, RMIT. If Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia can not serve to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Mr. Anthony Albanese should resign from the post of prime minister of Australia (M. A. Hossain, 2023f, 2023bw). Mr. Anthony Albanese should not play/drama with the reputation of Australia with the reputation of Australian higher education.

7.9 Citizen value is proportional to the value of prime minister and president of a country in the global platform

If the rights of citizen decline, the value of the post of prime minister and president also declines, the genuine value of the post of CEO also declines, the genuine value of the country also declines. Similarly, if the rights of citizen increase, the value of the post of prime minister and president also increase, the genuine value of the post of CEO also increase, the genuine value of the country also increase. So, a prime minister and president are not a post of display and showcase in the ministerial cabinet in the cabinet. These are the post of executive command and ethical service and zero crime duty. A prime minister and president should be prime knowledgeable person of the country of the time should be prime ethical person of the country of the time should be a politically addicted person of the country of the time to establish zero crime approach in the country in the

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.),
Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia),
Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*}
Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process,
color engg), applied law & criminology
Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)*
Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)*
Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg
& Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam);
Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and
Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

global platform. So, a life time safety allowance/safety care should be the vital support to the prime minister and president. No leader or CEO should die by the force of criminal by the target of enemy by the illegal technique of prison by the force of weapon. Globally, every prime minister and president should have a common dress code with a common symbol of peace and ethical beauty in terms of zero crime approach. Dress code is also necessary from the office assistant to the minister and ministerial cabinet. UN may implement and gazette a common dress code for the people of prime minister and president. UN may have a special safety support for the people of prime minister and president. Every safety service is not a detention service. There is far difference between the service of safety and service of detention or custody. A detention service should be the post condition of a judicial assessment of any country. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain asked safety service to the Australian government for the protection against international criminal against Australian criminal.

7.10 Every public servant should say/tune to the citizen, “your honour, your honour.”

The salary of a research category professor should be few grades higher than the president and prime minister of the country/countries. Such way, people will dream to be a professor of technology, professor of knowledge industry. People will not dream to be a president. Professor means the contribution of knowledge. President means the contribution in power implementation, but the moral power has remarkable contribution of knowledge. How many crisis meeting of prime minister/president is run by the professor (Dr.). How can a political leader get the highest post/designation of the country? Practically and theoretically, it seems that the study outcome/practice of political science has more priority rather than the practice of technology rather than the practice of knowledge industry. Although, the political service of a politician is not a core profession, this is also the subsidiary service of a profession. This should be the subsidiary profession at the age of retirement and early retirement of the mother profession. Professional service should be the actual profession. People have also a tendency to involve politics rather than the contribution in knowledge. A professor can not invest for journalists, but a political leader can huge invest for the journalists. What is the source of income of the political leaders? Nobody knows the genuine income source. The consequences are tending to crimes and criminal. If there is transparency in everywhere, the currency inflation will be/should be zero/minus. Moreover, the general lifestyle of the people will be/should be improved and improved automatically for peace surviving for heaven surviving. The rank of chief professor/senior professor/ethical professor should be two rank higher than the president/prime minister of the country. Possibly, a wrong policy of politicians was established and practiced under the support of human power, human politics, bloody power, weapon power, and wrong management of wealth distribution. Maximum politician follows the unethical techniques of crimes and climbing rather than scholarly contribution. Indirectly ethical professor should control the political community and/or ministerial cabinet without which global threat may increase. Indirectly knowledge should control the political

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia
Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

community. Indirectly professor will solve the problem to run the country. In general, professors should be more knowledgeable than the politicians of the country if the professors are professors of the countries. It should be established globally. Practically and possibly, professors have more food crisis than the politicians, when professors are practicing ethics and ethics rather than power and power rather than weapon and weapon rather than crime and criminal. Every ethical post/person of the country should have a higher salary of the country should have a higher safety of the country. Every ethical person/ethical category profession of the country should have a higher salary, quality lifestyle, and quality safety to minimize the currency inflation. If the administration of a country denies the ethical support to professor, there is possibility of disorder of the country/countries/UN against the right surviving on the planet. As a result, these are the symptom of uncontrolled bombing and weapon display in the planet. So, the highest post of a country should not only control by the politician. Possibly, it was leaded/continued/started by the wrong practice by the force practice by the practice of weapon by the practice of criminal and crimes. These are also symptom of bombing and bombing. Every public servant should say/tune to the citizen, “your honour, your honour.” This is the symptom of democracy, advocacy, and peace surviving theory in the planet(Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024u, 2024w).

7.11 Country policy is failing, United Nations policy is failing, University policy is also failing against the peace surviving

Every country is an association of citizens (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024w). A country/UN is a paid organization/paid-association. Every country/UN is a citizen of paid association/organization. So, every citizen has a beneficiary right for claiming for surviving in the planet. Some organization tries/tried to reply the message of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain without ensuring the service, but the office has intention to keep the evidence of their response. In this case, evidence gets more priority than the public service than the solution of the problem. Bangladeshi organization kept fake e-mail address and/or invalid e-mail address in the website, but Bangladesh is a country of UN. These are the cheating symptom with the public service under the intentional practice of negligence and denying the self-accountability of self-office. Possibly, protection of job has more priority than the public service than the ministerial service than the secretarial service. Possibly, additional benefit has more priority than the personal salary/fixed salary of office and public service. No public service office/officer/CEO/prime minister/president should take/negotiate/expect/dream/intent single dollar without the fixed salary and self-salary. Expensive car, expensive housing, expensive tour, expensive party of a public service officer/CEO/prime minister/president increases the currency inflation of a country. But nobody should say anything because of administrative weapon of the ministerial cabinet who authenticate supreme power of weapon, administrative force, and judicial force. So, there is scope to moderate the policy of citizen-friendly public service in Australia, Bangladesh, and UN.

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology</p> <p>Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia</p> <p>International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anwar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva</p> <p>Research address of Dr. Anwar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anwar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	--	--

7.12 Family wealth should be the wealth of government wealth after death of the person

Every wealth and power should be achieved by the appropriate way of service. Every achievement of wealth should be peer reviewed and peer reviewed. If a king/queen gets wealth by birth, he/she should not be a king/queen automatically. Every citizen is the total owner of the wealth of the country of the king palace. Unfortunately, still now wealth is getting more priority than education and knowledge. Paternal/maternal/family wealth should not be the fact to achieve any honour in any platform. Knowledge, education, and personal achievement should be the fact and act to achieve any honour in any platform. Let's establish education and knowledge, let's accumulate knowledge rather than accumulation of wealth, let's practice knowledge rather than wealth for peace surviving in planet. Therefore, people will invest and invest for knowledge, knowledge industry, and learning which will tend to peace establishing, peace surviving, and peace tuning in the planet (M. A. Hossain, 2023aq, 2023au).

7.13 Iftar party should not be funded by government of Bangladesh

Bangladesh government should not organize/approve any iftar party funded by government. There was iftar party at the office of chief advisor on March 2025. A government should not approve the iftar party when Bangladesh is facing a crisis situation. Therefore, everywhere has scope to minimize the currency inflation of a country. Every government/ministry should have a transparent cost summery and balance sheet at the end of year. Every government should have a profit margin. Every government should pay the salary of the employee should increase the salary of the employee from the income of a government. Every government should proportionally increase the salary of the employee from the income of a government. An increment of the salary of the government employee should not be a performance of a political leader. An increment of the income of the government should be a performance of a political leader which is the principle of zero currency inflation which is the principle of public friendly ministerial cabinet which is the principle of public peace cabinet. A government should not forget that every public/citizen is not a political leader and/or a government employee. The percentage of public/citizen is higher than the political leaders and government employee.

7.14 Zero income support = zero income tax of a profession (M. A. Hossain, 2023aq, 2023bw; Md. Anwar Hossain, 2024k, 2024x)

Why is professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain not getting legal support/food allowance/income support. Every professor category person should have legal right to ask legal support/food allowance/income support/safety to the office of president/prime minister. If a government is not paying income support, the government should not take the income tax. This is the symptom of crime/limitation in policy making of a government. The solution can be equationally stated that zero income support = zero income tax of a profession. If a professor has no income support, if a

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia
Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anwar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

professor has no crisis support, government should not take the income tax of single taka/dollar from the pocket of any professor.

7.15 Md. Anowar Hossain is not a Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) by beneficiary/by heritage/by successor/by birth(M. A. Hossain, 2023aq, 2023az, 2023ba, 2023bb) (M. A. Hossain, 2023au, 2023bx; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x)

A person may be king/queen by beneficiary/by heritage/by successor/by birth/by nation/by history/by father/by mother/by husband/by wife but a person can not be a professor by heritage/successor/beneficiary. No body should get power/wealth/designation by birth by beneficiary. This is not a matter of private organization and/or public organization and/or government organization and/or the organization of king/queen. By mistake, by chance, by confuse with the heritage; people respect king/queen for their wealth of beneficiary but comparatively people don't respect the appeal of professor but comparatively government don't respect the professor. So, still the power of wealth is winning, still the power of weapon is winning, still the power of force is winning, still the power of illegal source of alarming and tuning are winning. But the ethical practice or service of professor is comparatively failing and failing in the planet. So, the crime is winning. So, the criminal is winning. So, the weapon is winning. So, the money/currency is winning. Where is the democracy and advocacy? Democracy and advocacy are the words only. Democracy and advocacy are the fashion in globalization are the fashion of the political leaders. Democracy and advocacy are the words of broadcasting of politicians are the words of newspapers and newspapers. So, the actual peace is declining and declining in the planet. So, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) is begging and begging for legal support for the protection against Australian criminal but he is not getting since 2021-2022. If a king/queen of a country is getting quality food and quality living cost; every professor, scientist, researcher should also get quality food and quality living cost all over the world. Nobody should cease the food of a professor, no country should cease the food of a professor, no criminal should cease the food of a professor, no businessman should cease the food of a professor, no minister should cease the food of a professor, no professor should cease the food of a professor, nobody should kill the professor, nobody should plan to kill the professor, nobody should think to kill the professor when professor has no control of weapon and weapon when professor can not control the government. Historically and possibly, criminals are enjoying the quality food and quality life style than the people of the ethical class in the planet. Possibly, this is comparatively true scenery. If the people/society believe and continue accordingly, it will be the disastrous situation for the human society against the human surviving in the planet. There is huge scope of research and development. There is scope of peer review and continuous research about the king/queen family about the wealth of king/queen family about the power of king/queen

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	---	---

family about the education and profession of king/queen family. In this research of democracy and advocacy and pure globalization and tradition of king family, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) is asking and requesting research fund from the office of king, Charles Philip Arthur George, King Charles III, King of United Kingdom. Charles Philip Arthur George may write a book about the 'history of wealth and chain achievement of king family'. There is scope of school study at RMIT, school research at RMIT, peer review at Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, RMIT for the reference of historical drama of democracy and advocacy. Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) is also asking and requesting research fund from different king/queen. Let's globally establish and tune for the food safety and living cost safety to every professor to the royal class person rather than royal class family. Therefore, let's establish and tune that a royal class person is thousand and thousand times better than the royal class family. An ethical professor graded person can make a legal claim to be a royal class person. An ethical politician graded person can make a legal claim to be a royal class person. An ethical king/queen graded person can make a legal claim to be a royal class person. In globalization of democracy and advocacy, a royal class person may claim may nominate to be a political leader or CEO or president/prime minister or king/queen of any country, it should not be a matter of citizen of any country. Scientifically, the term of royal class family is a wrong word, royal class person should be the right word. In a royal class family, one person may be ethical professor and another person may be unethical professor; one person may be ethical king and another person may be unethical queen. To be a royal class person, it is not necessity to be a son/daughter of a royal class couple. Scientifically, every human brain is a natural is a unique psychophysics. Natural psychophysics is a generic matter of becoming criminal or ethical. Natural situation of life journey and/or self-surviving in the family/community of crimes and criminal may vibrate/influence the generic matter of becoming criminal or ethical. Although royal class child may get good nursing of brain development in a royal family, this is by chance. Democracy should also serve and ensure the brain development of every child for the surviving in the planet. Therefore, let's prohibit the word of king/queen/royal class family from the planet and replace by the words of democracy and advocacy when a professor graded person is not getting food and living costs when a professor graded person is not getting the legal support, legal costs, and safety under the present support/globalized practice of democracy and advocacy under the present situation of globalization under the administration of UN. The whole world should shout and shout to establish the ethical platform of the royal class persona who contribute for the people for the nation.

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

7.16 Let's establish democracy and advocacy, let's build a weapon free world and criminal free world for zero-crime approach for the peace of human being for increasing the life-time of the people

Nobody should cease the ethical weapon of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. An ethical person is more valuable than a country or organization. Every citizen should have rights to serve as ethical citizen of the country. People show weapon/threat to establish the unethical approach which is a symptom of crime and crime. The power of writing is failing and failing, the power of ethics is failing and failing; the power of weapon is winning, the power of threat is winning. The power of designation is winning; the power of wealth is winning; but the power of service and ethics are failing and failing. Possibly, criminals are doing crimes, criminals are motivating and influencing the fighting between countries between brothers and brothers. Criminals are forcing to produce weapon to purchase weapon. But weapon should not be the basic needs of any country. Possibly, every country is investing higher and higher for the defence rather than food, textile, housing, education, medical, recreation, legal rights, human rights, and protection against natural calamity. Every political leader/CEO should not allow the crimes and criminals for the quality surviving in the planet for the peace of human being for increasing the lifetime of the people. Possibly, people will have zero crisis, people will have peace and peace, people will have heaven and heaven if people have the situation of zero cost of defence if people follow the technique of zero-crime. Possibly, criminals are very professional, expert, and highly camouflage. Possibly criminals have connection with the political leaders and/or CEO and/or gang of different countries. Possibly criminals/CEO are practicing self-benefit rather than the public service. Sometimes, it is also tough to identify to understand the symptom to understand the target of the criminals. For example: a singer sings a song but a group of people harmony for the song but a group of instruments/tunes harmony for the song, if there is mistake the whole harmony may displace. So, everyone is important for the song of the singer. So, every tune is also important for the song of the singer.

Let's destroy and dispose the source of global violence, global fighting, global aggression, global forcing, global slavery, global cheating, and global bombing.

Let's destroy the ego of negativity.

Let's forget the ego of negativity.

Let's improve the ego of positivity.

Let's improve the service of positivity.

Let's protect the planet for peace surviving.

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/</p>	
---	--	--

Let's try to establish zero crime in the planet.

Let's build a peace world and heaven for peace surviving.

Let's extend the peace and lifetime of the people.

8 Conclusion

Every ministerial income and costs are directly relevant to the currency inflation. Every prestigious post of a country or UN is created to serve the public to serve the society to serve the country. A post of public service is a post of public nursing is a post of public servant is a post of power of service is post of power of nursing. These are not the post of power of forcing rather than power of nursing. So, everyone can not perform the job of public service. If a person can not serve to the public, if a person can not understand the public service, he/she should not come to the job of the public service, he/she should resign from the post of public service. This is very simple theory of the public service. Everyone should capable to understand the simple theory. Everyone should be educated to understand the simple theory. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is a person is a citizen; he can not make force to government but the government can make force but the government can implement power but the government should be more ethical more transparent than the citizen. Citizens are paying penalty to the government. Similarly, government should pay the penalty to the citizen. The penalty percentage of a government should be higher than the citizen. This is very simple theory and simple understanding to satisfy the practice of democracy and advocacy. Without which the policy of government penalty should be banned. Practically, citizen has no power. But the government holds the power holds the weapon. There is huge lacking to establish the rights of citizen, democracy, and advocacy for the public for the citizen (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024w). Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is a long-term sufferer and lifelong sufferer (M. A. Hossain, 2023f). Australia/Bangladesh/UN should be legally and officially responsible to establish the legal rights of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in Australian court and/or international court.

9 Evidence of seeking and begging the service in Australia, Bangladesh, and UN, cited in figure 1; although every reference in reference list has the separate evidence

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

9.1 Evidence of relevant communications with prime minister of Australia to access the public service of Australian government to secure the Australian human rights of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) to ensure safety, salary (chief professor/senior professor category stipend), and ‘compensation award’ of 8390000 Australian penalty units (230,72,50,000AUD) (M. A. Hossain, 2023f, 2023g; M. A. Hossain, 2023c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x; Hossain, 2025f)

Australian Government
Department of the Prime Minister and Cabinet

ANDREW FISHER BUILDING
ONE NATIONAL CIRCUIT
BARTON

Reference: MC23-103435

Dear Professor Dr. Engr. Hossain

Thank you for getting in touch with the Prime Minister.

Looking at the issues you have raised, I would recommend the Department of Education would be best placed to respond to you.

To assist with that, we have referred your correspondence to the Department of Education for their consideration.

Please keep in mind that your correspondence might need input from multiple government departments or agencies and this could take time to compile for you.

You can contact the Department of Education regarding the progress of your correspondence by visiting their contact us web page.

On behalf of the Prime Minister, thank you again for getting in touch.

Yours sincerely

Megan
Senior Adviser
Ministerial Correspondence Unit
Department of the Prime Minister and Cabinet

Note: Please do not reply to this email as this address is not monitored. If you have follow-up questions for the Department of the Prime Minister and Cabinet, please visit our contact us form: www.pmc.gov.au/contact-us#contact-form

Postal Address: PO Box 6500, CANBERRA ACT 2600
Telephone: +61 2 6271 5111 www.pmc.gov.au ABN: 18 108 001 191

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*}
Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process,
color engg), applied law & criminology
Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)³
Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁴
Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCRC College of Engg
& Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam);
Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Trained from India, Australia, Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and
Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

9.2 Evidence of relevant communications with prime minister of Australia to access the public service of Australian government to secure the Australian human rights of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) to ensure safety, salary (chief professor/senior professor category stipend), and 'compensation award' of 8390000 Australian penalty units (230,72,50,000AUD) (M. A. Hossain, 2023f, 2023g; M. A. Hossain, 2023c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x; Hossain, 2025f)

MC24-163852

Referred to the Department of Home Affairs

Thank you for your message to the Prime Minister.

All items of correspondence are read and carefully considered, however not all items will receive a response.

Looking at the issues you have raised, I would recommend the Department of Home Affairs would be best placed to respond to you. To assist with that, we have referred your correspondence to the Department of Home Affairs for their consideration.

Please keep in mind that your correspondence might need input from multiple government departments or agencies and this could take time to compile for you.

You can contact the Department of Home Affairs regarding the progress of your correspondence by visiting their contact us web page.

Thank you for your correspondence to the Hon Anthony Albanese MP, Prime Minister. The Prime Minister appreciates you taking the time to write to him.

Ministerial Correspondence Unit Notification Service

This is an automatically generated email. Please do not reply to this email as this address is not monitored.

9.3 Evidence of communications with local community of social service in Melbourne, Australia (M. A. Hossain, 2023f)

RE: Contact us | MCM

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

- Melbourne City Mission

info@mcm.org.au

To: me · Thu, Aug 14 at 10:13 AM

<engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

Message Body

Hi Md. Anowar,

Thanks for getting in touch with Melbourne City Mission. We hope that we can be of assistance.

If you are experiencing or at risk of homelessness, you will need to present to your local access point where they will assess your situation and connect you to the relevant support services, this may be services through MCM or other organisations.

Under 25:

MCM's Frontyard Youth Services the statewide housing access point for under 25 year olds. They provide crisis accommodation combined with support services that address physical, emotional, and social needs. No referrals are necessary.

Phone: 03 9977 0077

Email: frontyard@mcm.org.au

Website: www.mcm.org.au/services/homelessness/frontyard

Over 25:

To get more information on access points and services that is closest to you, you can contact Housing Victoria on 1800 825 955. Or you can visit their website where there is a list of access points under the 'Local homelessness support' section: <https://services.dffh.vic.gov.au/getting-help>

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology</p> <p>Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁹ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia</p> <p>International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva</p> <p>Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	--	--

If you need assistance locating your local access point, please let me know which area you are currently located in and I can look it up for you.

Launch Housing provides a [Rough Sleeper Initiative](#) in the Cities of Melbourne, Yarra, Port Phillip, Stonnington, Frankston or Dandenong. Contact your local council or call (03) 8598 1170 for more information.

City of Melbourne have resources for support services on their [website](#) and [The Helping Out Guide](#) provides a comprehensive list of free and low-cost services for people experiencing hardship and homelessness.

I hope this helps but please let me know if you need more information.

Best regards,
 Melbourne City Mission

Melbourne City Mission 164-180 Kings Way, South Melbourne VIC 3205

P: 03 9977 0000 | mcm.org.au

TOGETHER: COURAGEOUS & CURIOUS: OPEN & ACCOUNTABLE

From: webmaster@mcm.org.au <webmaster@mcm.org.au>
Sent: Tuesday, 12 August 2025 8:43 PM
To: Melbourne City Mission <info@mcm.org.au>
Subject: Contact us | MCM

Hi MCM Admin Team,
 The following enquiry has been submitted via the enquiry form on the MCM website.

First Name: Md. Anowar
Last Name: Hossain

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia
Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Phone Number: +8801788396264

Preferred Method: Email

Enquiry: Our services

Page | 62

Message: Dear Officer, May I seek an assistance of living, food, and legal support from your office. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19140.19849> <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21520.17927> <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14584.05126> <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18413.19685> <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33291.67366> <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1> Kind regards Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist, Barrister (Dr.)

Thanks

9.4 Evidence of communications with local community of social service in Melbourne, Australia (M. A. Hossain, 2023f)

May I seek an assistance of living, food, and legal support from your office

- Anowar Hossain

To: operations@smhow.org.au · Tue, Aug 12 at 4:53 PM

From: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Message Body

Dear Officer,

May I seek an assistance of living, food, and legal support from your office?

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is seeking legal support to The Hon Anthony Albanese MP, Prime Minister, Australia for the conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in PhD school, RMIT University. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19140.19849>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10990583>

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁹ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	---	--

Reporting to Honorable Minister, Department of Home Affairs, Australia and delegates for activation and extension of VISA of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Delegate of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University until the final order of Australian Supreme Court, Australian human rights commission and chief authorities of Australian Government relates to PhD harassment and conspiracy of life-threatening of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21520.17927>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11195451>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is asking to Ms. Nardia Simpson, Australian High Commissioner for approving the extension of Australian Student VISA for legal and ethical claiming to Australian court under the ethical support of Minister of home affairs, foreign affairs and education. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14584.05126>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1469107>

A follow-up letter to The Hon Jason Clare MP, Education Minister, Australia for the conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in Australian PhD school. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18413.19685>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10964382>

Anowar Hossain's invention for peace in PhD schooling, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33291.67366>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12742364>

Permanent Address

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist; Vill: Purbo Nuthurchar, Post Office: K. Mohonpur (1990), Police Station: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh (by birth)

Professional Address

School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Your Honour; Please Pardon Me

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Best Regards for your excellency

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist

PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh)

Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing

Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066

School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry

Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)

Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology

University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India

BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia

Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College, Chittagong

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	--	---

Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh

Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.

Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)

International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg

Research Address since 2020

512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, engranowar06@gmail.com, +8801788396264

Please Visit the Profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

9.5 Evidence of communications with local community of social service in Melbourne, Australia (M. A. Hossain, 2023f)

Page | 66

The Social Blueprint - We received your enquiry

- The Social Blueprint

noreply@thesocialblueprint.org.au

To: me · Tue, Aug 12 at 5:09 PM

Engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Message Body

Hi Md. Anowar Hossain,

The team at The Social Blueprint has received your request and will get in contact with you soon.

Have a nice day,

The Social Blueprint Team

9.6 Evidence of follow-up notice to the attorney general of Australia

Ms. Michelle Rowland

Attorney General, Australia

Dear Sir,

I would like to attach a cc letter to the attorney general's department of Australia.

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is seeking legal support to The Hon Anthony Albanese MP, Prime Minister, Australia for the conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in PhD school, RMIT University. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19140.19849>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10990583>

Do not reply: Your contact us form has been submitted

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anwar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anwar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	--	---

- ag.noreply@govcms.gov.au

To: me · Tue, Sep 2 at 4:14 PM

Engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Message Body

Thank you for contacting the Attorney-General Department.

This is an automated response to confirm that we have received your email and forwarded it to the appropriate area of the department for consideration. We may provide a response if you have included your name and email address.

9.7 Evidence of failure notice of sent e-mail to President, chief advisor, and attorney general of Bangladesh

cc letters to the attorney general's department of Bangladesh

- Anowar Hossain

To: attorneygeneral@attorneygeneral.gov.bd, and 7 others, Cc: secretary@bangabhaban.gov.bd, and 3 others · Tue, Sep 2 at 4:00 PM

To:

- [<attorneygeneral@attorneygeneral.gov.bd>](mailto:attorneygeneral@attorneygeneral.gov.bd),
- [<ps_ag@attorneygeneral.gov.bd>](mailto:ps_ag@attorneygeneral.gov.bd),
- [<adv.ajb1@gmail.com>](mailto:Adv.ajb1@gmail.com),
- [<ps_addl_ag1@attorneygeneral.gov.bd>](mailto:ps_addl_ag1@attorneygeneral.gov.bd),
- [<addl_ag2@attorneygeneral.gov.bd>](mailto:addl_ag2@attorneygeneral.gov.bd),
- [<ps_addl_ag2@attorneygeneral.gov.bd>](mailto:ps_addl_ag2@attorneygeneral.gov.bd),
- [<addl_ag3@attorneygeneral.gov.bd>](mailto:addl_ag3@attorneygeneral.gov.bd),
- [<ps_addl_ag3@attorneygeneral.gov.bd>](mailto:ps_addl_ag3@attorneygeneral.gov.bd)

Cc:

- [<secretary@bangabhaban.gov.bd>](mailto:secretary@bangabhaban.gov.bd),

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (enr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

- <ps_president@bangabhaban.gov.bd>,
- <psecy@cao.gov.bd>,
- <secretary@cao.gov.bd>

Message Body

Mr. Md. Asaduzzaman (translated)

Attorney General, Bangladesh

attorneygeneral@attorneygeneral.gov.bd

ps_ag@attorneygeneral.gov.bd

Mr. Muhammad Abdul Jabbar Bhuiyan (translated)

Additional Attorney General, Bangladesh

Adv.ajb1@gmail.com

ps_addl_ag1@attorneygeneral.gov.bd

Mr. Md. Arshadur Rouf (translated)

Additional attorney general

addl_ag2@attorneygeneral.gov.bd

ps_addl_ag2@attorneygeneral.gov.bd

Mr. Mohammad Anik Rushad Haque (translated)

Additional attorney general

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁹ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	---	--

addl_ag3@attorneygeneral.gov.bd

ps_addl_ag3@attorneygeneral.gov.bd

Dear Sir,

I would like to attach cc letters to the attorney general's department of Bangladesh.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14837268>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is self-approaching to enhance higher education and research support in Bangladesh and Australia School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32735.16801>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15718630>

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is seeking legal support to The Hon Anthony Albanese MP, Prime Minister, Australia for the conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in PhD school, RMIT University. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19140.19849>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10990583>

Your Honour; Please Pardon Me

Best Regards for your excellency

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh)
Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing
Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)

Page | 70

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066

School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry

Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)

Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology

University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India

BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia

Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College, Chittagong

Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh

Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia, Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	---	---

Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.

Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)

International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg

Research Address since 2020

512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, engranowar06@gmail.com, +8801788396264

Please Visit the Profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

9.7.1 Failure Notice

- To: me · Tue, Sep 2 at 4:14 PM

Engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Message Body

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<ps_ag@attorneygeneral.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (ps_ag@attorneygeneral.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

9.7.2 Failure Notice

- MAILER-DAEMON@yahoo.com

To: me · Tue, Sep 2 at 4:14 PM

Engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Message Body

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<secretary@cao.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (secretary@cao.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

9.7.3 Failure Notice

- MAILER-DAEMON@yahoo.com

To: me · Tue, Sep 2 at 4:04 PM

Engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India, Australia, Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	---	---

Message Body

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<secretary@bangabhaban.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (secretary@bangabhaban.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

9.7.4 Failure Notice

- MAILER-DAEMON@yahoo.com

To: me · Tue, Sep 2 at 4:04 PM

Engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Message Body

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<ps_president@bangabhaban.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (ps_president@bangabhaban.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

9.7.5 Failure Notice

Your message could not be delivered to the Attorney General's address, and the sender has provided details about a Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's legal and educational requests.

- To: me · Tue, Sep 2 at 4:04 PM

Engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Message Body

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<attorneygeneral@attorneygeneral.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (attorneygeneral@attorneygeneral.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

9.7.6 Failure Notice

- MAILER-DAEMON@yahoo.com

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

To: me · Tue, Sep 2 at 4:04 PM

Engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Message Body

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<ps_addl_ag3@attorneygeneral.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (ps_addl_ag3@attorneygeneral.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

9.7.7 Failure Notice

- MAILER-DAEMON@yahoo.com

To: me · Tue, Sep 2 at 4:04 PM

Engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Message Body

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<ps_addl_ag1@attorneygeneral.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (ps_addl_ag1@attorneygeneral.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

9.7.8 Failure Notice

Your message could not be delivered to psecy@cao.gov.bd due to a permanent failure for one or more recipients.

- To: me · Tue, Sep 2 at 4:04 PM
- Engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Message Body

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<psecy@cao.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (psecy@cao.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)³ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁴ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	---	---

9.7.9 Failure Notice

- To: me · Tue, Sep 2 at 4:03 PM
- Engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Message Body

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<ps_addl_ag2@attorneygeneral.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (ps_addl_ag2@attorneygeneral.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

9.7.10 Failure Notice

- To: me · Tue, Sep 2 at 4:03 PM
- Engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Message Body

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<addl_ag2@attorneygeneral.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (addl_ag2@attorneygeneral.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

9.8 Evidence of recent communication with foreign ministry of Bangladesh

May I seek official counselling of foreign ministry regarding international category legal aid support in Australian court and/or international court

Anowar Hossain

Engr.anowar@yahoo.com

To: fs@mofa.gov.bd, Cc: dirfso@mofa.gov.bd, and 22 others · Thu, Jul 31 at 5:52 AM

To:

- <fs@mofa.gov.bd>

Cc:

- <dirfso@mofa.gov.bd>,

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

- <ssa@mofa.gov.bd>,
- Robert Shanks,<robert.shanks@rmit.edu.au>,
- Lijing Wang,<lijing.wang@rmit.edu.au>,
- Vice Chancellor,<vc@rmit.edu.au>,
- <aswelfare@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <dgcnw@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <asconsular2@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <dgla@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <asrnd@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <labour.canberra@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <mission.canberra@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <ahc.dhaka@dfat.gov.au>,
- Andrea Eckersley,<andrea.eckersley@rmit.edu.au>,
- <alice.payne@rmit.edu.au>,
- Sean Ryan,<sean.ryan@rmit.edu.au>,
- Robert Shanks,<robert.shanks.scientific@gmail.com>,
- <brooke.griffin@rmit.edu.au>,
- <ea.vc@rmit.edu.au>,
- <jason.ngam@rmit.edu.au>,
- <nicole.hendrie@rmit.edu.au>,
- <fa@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <apsfao@mofa.gov.bd>

Message Body

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.). Postdoc² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	---	--

Mr. Asad Alam Siam

Foreign Secretary

Government of Bangladesh

fs@mofa.gov.bd

May I seek official counselling of foreign ministry regarding international category legal aid support in Australian court and/or international court

Dear Sir,

I would like to seek official counselling of foreign ministry regarding international category legal aid support in Australian court and/or international court and/or government investigation of life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school. I asked an appointment with foreign secretary on 4 February 2025. I have attached the evidence. I also sent following reports and links of pdf files for the action and support of foreign ministry.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14837268>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is requesting to Mr. António Guterres, Secretary-General of United Nations for a legal stipend or legal award to proceed with legal proceeding of life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35976.12805>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14934539>

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is seeking legal support to The Hon Anthony Albanese MP, Prime Minister, Australia for the conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in PhD school, RMIT University. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19140.19849>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10990583>

Page | 78

My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-01). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16530.84162>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7890974>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is asking to Ms. Nardia Simpson, Australian High Commissioner for approving the extension of Australian Student VISA for legal and ethical claiming to Australian court under the ethical support of Minister of home affairs, foreign affairs and education. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14584.05126>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14699107>

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Bangladeshi Passport No: EE0444946; Bangladeshi Address: Vill: Purbo Nuthurchar, P.O: K. Mohonpur (Postal Code: 1990) P.S: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh is reporting life-threatening conspiracy to Mr. Jeremy Bruer, Australian High Commissioner to Bangladesh located at 184 Gulshan Avenue, Gulshan, Dhaka, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28153.24164>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10025287>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is self-approaching to enhance higher education and research support in Bangladesh and Australia School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32735.16801>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15718630>

Your Honour; Please Pardon Me

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology</p> <p>Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia</p> <p>International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg., City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg., BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg.; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva</p> <p>Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	---	--

Best Regards for your excellency

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist

PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh)

Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing

Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066

School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry

Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)

Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology

University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India

BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia

Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College, Chittagong

Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh

Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.

Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)

International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg

Research Address since 2020

512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, engranowar06@gmail.com, +8801788396264

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh); MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁹ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assisit. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCME College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assisit. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assisit. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	--	--

Please Visit the Profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Higher education and research

- Anowar Hossain

Engr.anowar@yahoo.com

To: ssa@mofa.gov.bd, and 10 others · Tue, Jun 24 at 5:42 PM

To:

- <ssa@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <aswelfare@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <dgcnw@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <asconsular2@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <asconsular1@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <asmrp@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <dircnmrp@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <dirwelfare@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <rector.fsa@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <fsa@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <dirfsa@mofa.gov.bd>

Message Body

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Dear Sir/Madam,

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is self-approaching to enhance higher education and research support in Bangladesh and Australia School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).

Page | 82

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32735.16801>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15718630>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14837268>

Your Honour; Please Pardon Me

Best Regards for your excellency

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist

PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh)

Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing

Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066

School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCME College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	--	---

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry

Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)

Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology

University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India

BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia

Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College, Chittagong

Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh

Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)

International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg

Page | 84

Research Address since 2020

512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, engranowar06@gmail.com, +8801788396264

Please Visit the Profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

9.9 Evidence of recent communication with foreign ministry of Australia

Anowar Hossain

Engr.anowar@yahoo.com

To: paula.ganly@dfat.gov.au · Fri, Dec 27, 2024 at 6:26 AM

Message Body

Ms. Paula Ganly

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology</p> <p>Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)³ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁴ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia</p> <p>International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva</p> <p>Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	--	--

First Assistant Secretary

Consular and Crisis Management Division

Department of Foreign Affairs and Trade

RG Casey Building

John McEwen Crescent

BARTON ACT 0221

ula.ganly@dfat.gov.au

Dear Secretary,

I would like to attach an acknowledgment letter of Australian Prime Minister.

Accordingly, could you please assess below letters and e-mails? I also applied to your office in previous time. I applied for student VISA and detention visit VISA. Both VISA application was rejected. I should have an option to claim through Australian court if your office is not responsible to solve the issue of a foreign applicant. Somehow, at least, I should get a support to claim when I am a long-term victim, and I am begging and begging since 2021-2022 under the administrative platform of Australian platform. It seems that nobody is responsible to solve the issue to support the applicant.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is asking to Ms. Nardia Simpson, Australian High Commissioner for approving the extension of Australian Student VISA for legal and ethical claiming to Australian court under the ethical support of Minister of home affairs, foreign affairs and education. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14584.05126>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14498859>

Seeking VISA extension, legal support, legal costs, legal insurance support, accommodation costs, fooding costs, personal safety, PhD compensation award of Australian Government, PhD compensation award of RMIT University, PhD certificate, PhD mark sheets or academic transcript and job offer letter to Australian Home affairs. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34569.04960>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13822693>

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Reporting to Honorable Minister, Department of Home Affairs, Australia and delegates for activation and extension of VISA of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Delegate of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University until the final order of Australian Supreme Court, Australian human rights commission and chief authorities of Australian Government relates to PhD harassment and conspiracy of life-threatening of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21520.17927>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11195451>

Page | 86

50% income support and 100% life-safety compensation were requested and proposed to Professor Dr. Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University for 63 years duration under calculation of 100 years life-time of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29528.47360>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10159331>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14048863>

Your Honour; Please Pardon Me

Best Regards for your excellency

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist

PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh)

Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing

Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology</p> <p>Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia</p> <p>International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	---	--

School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry

Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)

Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology

University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India

BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia

Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College, Chittagong

Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh

Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.

Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)

Page | 88

International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg

Research Address since 2020

512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, engranowar06@gmail.com, +8801788396264

Please Visit the Profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology</p> <p>Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁴ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁵ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia</p> <p>International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India, Australia, Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva</p> <p>Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	--	--

9.10 Evidence of communication with human rights commission of Australia

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking free of cost legal support and victim support for a full funding financial assistance to ACT Human Rights Commission of Australia

- Anowar Hossain

Engr.anowar@yahoo.com

To: human.rights@act.gov.au, and 1 other · Tue, Oct 29, 2024 at 5:02 PM

To:

- <human.rights@act.gov.au>
- <humanrightsmedia@act.gov.au>

Message Body

ACT Human Rights Commission of Australia
 56 Allara St Canberra ACT 2601

Dear Chief Executive Officer,

Could you please help for the free of cost legal support of below incidence. I am a victim since 2021-2022? I faced life-threatening conspiracy to pursue Australian PhD. I am facing financial crisis since 2022 for going to Australian Court for my legal support.

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is seeking legal support to The Hon Anthony Albanese MP, Prime Minister, Australia for the conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in PhD school, RMIT University. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19140.19849>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10990583>

Seeking VISA extension, legal support, legal costs, legal insurance support, accommodation costs, fooding costs, personal safety, PhD compensation award of Australian Government, PhD compensation award of RMIT University, PhD certificate, PhD mark sheets or academic transcript and job offer letter to Australian Home affairs. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34569.04960>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13822693>

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia
Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection [Biodata]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13884624>

Page | 90

Your Honour; Please Pardon Me

Best Regards for your excellency

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist

PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh)

Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing

Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066

School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry

Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)

Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology

University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India

BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia

Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anwar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCME College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anwar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	--	---

Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College, Chittagong

Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh

Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.

Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)

International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg

Research Address since 2020

512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, engranowar06@gmail.com, +8801788396264

Please Visit the Profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Legal support to PhD researcher, PhD ID: 3820066, RMIT University

- Anowar Hossain

Engr.anowar@yahoo.com

To: infoservice@humanrights.gov.au · Wed, Nov 27, 2024 at 7:04 AM

Message Body

Dear Chief Executive Officer,

A cc e-mail is being forwarded for your action and support.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is asking to Ms. Nardia Simpson, Australian High Commissioner for approving the extension of Australian Student VISA for legal and ethical claiming to Australian court under the ethical support of Minister of home affairs, foreign affairs and education.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14584.05126>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14208048>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14048863>

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg., City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg., BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	--	--

Your Honour; Please Pardon Me

Best Regards for your excellency

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist

PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh)

Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing

Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066

School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry

Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)

Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology

University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India

BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia

Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College, Chittagong

Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh

Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.

Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)

International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg

Research Address since 2020

512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, engranowar06@gmail.com, +8801788396264

Please Visit the Profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology</p> <p>Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia</p> <p>International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva</p> <p>Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	--	--

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is self-approaching to enhance higher education and research support in Bangladesh and Australia

- Anowar Hossain

To: reception@humanrights.gov.au · Mon, Jun 23 at 4:27 PM

Message Body

Dear Sir/Madam,

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is self-approaching to enhance higher education and research support in Bangladesh and Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32735.16801>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15718630>

Your Honour; Please Pardon Me

Best Regards for your excellency

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist

PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh)

Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing

Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066

School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry

Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)

Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology

University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India

BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia

Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College, Chittagong

Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh

Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	--	--

Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)

International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg

Research Address since 2020

512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, engranowar06@gmail.com, +8801788396264

Please Visit the Profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

- Anowar Hossain
- Engr.anowar@yahoo.com

To: education@humanrights.gov.au · Mon, Jun 23 at 4:56 PM

Message Body

----- Forwarded Message -----

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

From: Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To: reception@humanrights.gov.au <reception@humanrights.gov.au>

Sent: Monday, June 23, 2025 at 04:27:20 PM GMT+6

Subject: Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is self-approaching to enhance higher education and research support in Bangladesh and Australia

Page | 98

Dear Sir/Madam,

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is self-approaching to enhance higher education and research support in Bangladesh and Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32735.16801>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15718630>

Dear Sir/Madam,

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is self-approaching to enhance higher education and research support in Bangladesh and Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32735.16801>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15718630>

Your Honour; Please Pardon Me

Best Regards for your excellency

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist

PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh)

Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.). Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	--	--

Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066

School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry

Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)

Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology

University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India

BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia

Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College, Chittagong

Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh

Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.

Page | 100

Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)

International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg

Research Address since 2020

512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, engranowar06@gmail.com, +8801788396264

Please Visit the Profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

9.11 Evidence of communication with high commissioner of Australia in Bangladesh

Automatic reply: [EXTERNAL] Re: Letter of Australian VISA Proposal from an Australian Citizen

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	---	---

- Nardia Simpson

nardia.simpson@dfat.gov.au

To: me · Wed, Feb 12 at 9:24 PM

Engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Message Body

Thank you for your email. I have concluded my posting to Dhaka and will not be checking this email regularly.

If you would like to contact the Australian High Commission in Dhaka, please email AHC.dhaka@dfat.gov.au

Kind regards

Nardia Simpson

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is asking to Ms. Nardia Simpson, Australian High Commissioner for approving the extension of Australian Student VISA for legal and ethical claiming to Australian court under the ethical support of Minister of home affairs, foreign affairs and education.

- Anowar Hossain

To: nardia.simpson@dfat.gov.au, and 6 others, Cc: Robert, and 19 others · Wed, Nov 27, 2024 at 6:08 AM

- <nardia.simpson@dfat.gov.au>,
- <ahc.dhaka@dfat.gov.au>,
- <consular.dhaka@dfat.gov.au>,
- <esos@rmit.edu.au>,

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

- SGR Scholarships,<sgr.scholarships@rmit.edu.au>,
- <ahc.newdelhi@dfat.gov.au>,
- <contact.centre@education.gov.au>

Cc:

- Robert Shanks,<robert.shanks@rmit.edu.au>,
- Lijing Wang,<lijing.wang@rmit.edu.au>,
- Robert Shanks,<robert.shanks.scientific@gmail.com>,
- Vice Chancellor,<vc@rmit.edu.au>,
- Andrea Eckersley,<andrea.eckersley@rmit.edu.au>,
- Scott Mayson,<scott.mayson@rmit.edu.au>,
- Md Hossain,<s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au>,
- <brooke.griffin@rmit.edu.au>,
- <ea.vc@rmit.edu.au>,
- <jason.ngam@rmit.edu.au>,
- <nicole.hendrie@rmit.edu.au>,
- <vso@dfat.gov.au>,
- <dunning@callinanchambers.com.au>,
- <contact@austbar.asn.au>,
- <media@austbar.asn.au>,
- <academic.registrar@rmit.edu.au>,
- Grants@vla.vic.gov.au,<grants@vla.vic.gov.au>,
- <alice.payne@rmit.edu.au>,
- <calum.drummond@rmit.edu.au>,
- <ahc.dhaka@dfat.gov.au>

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg., City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg., BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	--	--

Message Body

Dear executive concern,

I would like to notify below letter for your official action and support.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is asking to Ms. Nardia Simpson, Australian High Commissioner for approving the extension of Australian Student VISA for legal and ethical claiming to Australian court under the ethical support of Minister of home affairs, foreign affairs and education. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14584.05126>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14208048>

I have also attached my CoE and offer letter. Officially, I can not proceed for Australian student VISA without active CoE although I applied for student VISA (evidence attached) through immi account of Australian home affairs.

Your Honour; Please Pardon Me

Best Regards for your excellency

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist

PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh)

Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing

Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066

School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry

Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology

University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India

BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Page | 104

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia

Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College, Chittagong

Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh

Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.

Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)

International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy,

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology</p> <p>Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)³ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁴ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia</p> <p>International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva</p> <p>Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	--	--

Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg

Research Address since 2020

512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, engranowar06@gmail.com, +8801788396264

Please Visit the Profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

9.12 Evidence of communication with UGC, Bangladesh

Anowar Hossain

To: fakhrul@ugc.gov.bd, and 10 others · Mon, Jun 23 at 2:33 PM

To:

- <fakhrul@ugc.gov.bd>,
- <secretary@ugc.gov.bd>,
- <syrawarn@gmail.com>,
- <nazmul@ugc.gov.bd>,
- <director_research@ugc.gov.bd>,

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

- <ferdousugc@gmail.com>,
- <mustafiz@ugc.gov.bd>,
- <mustafizugc@gmail.com>,
- <mrkhan@ugc.gov.bd>,
- <parvezugc@gmail.com>,
- <info@ugc.gov.bd>

Message Body

Dear Sir/Madam,

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is self-approaching to enhance higher education and research support in Bangladesh and Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32735.16801>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15718630>

Your Honour; Please Pardon Me

Best Regards for your excellency

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist

PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh)

Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing

Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCME College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	--	--

PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066

School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry

Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)

Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology

University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India

BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia

Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College, Chittagong

Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh

Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.

Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)

International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg

Research Address since 2020

512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, engranowar06@gmail.com, +8801788396264

Please Visit the Profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)³ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁴ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	---	--

9.13 Evidence of recent communication with the office of prime minister of Bangladesh

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. ANowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) seeking action and support from the office of chief advisor of Bangladesh government

- Anowar Hossain

To: dggiu@pmo.gov.bd · Tue, Jul 8 at 11:17 AM

Message Body

Governance Innovation Unit
 Prime Minister's Office
 Tejgaon, Dhaka-1215.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. ANowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) seeking action and support from the office of chief advisor of Bangladesh government

Dear Sir,

Local government in Bangladesh to minimize official crimes in public administration in a democratic country School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28463.85929>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15826808>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is self-approaching to enhance higher education and research support in Bangladesh and Australia School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32735.16801>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15718630>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14837268>

Your Honour; Please Pardon Me

Best Regards for your excellency

Page | 110

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist

PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh)

Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing

Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066

School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry

Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)

Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology

University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India

BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia

Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCME College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	--	--

Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College, Chittagong

Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh

Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.

Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)

International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg

Research Address since 2020

512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, engranowar06@gmail.com, +8801788396264

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Please Visit the Profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Page | 112

9.14 Evidence of communication with the office of chief advisor and president of Bangladesh

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

- Anowar Hossain

To: secretary@bangabhaban.gov.bd, and 12 others, Cc: lijing.wang@rmit.edu.au, and 122 others · Thu, Nov 7, 2024 at 10:33 AM

To:

- <secretary@bangabhaban.gov.bd>,
- <press.secy@bangabhaban.gov.bd>,
- <ps_president@bangabhaban.gov.bd>,
- <akmmonirul31@gmail.com>,
- <majumderali1950@gmail.com>,
- <musfiquldu33@gmail.com>,
- <psecy@cao.gov.bd>,
- <secretary@cao.gov.bd>,
- <seafath.mahmud@cao.gov.bd>,

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)³ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁴ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCME College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	---	--

- <lutfey.siddiqi@cao.gov.bd>,
- <sultanpmo1974@gmail.com>,
- <ddresearch@cao.gov.bd>,
- <jamery.hasan@cao.gov.bd>

Cc:

- <lijing.wang@rmit.edu.au>,
- <robert.shanks@rmit.edu.au>,
- <robert.shanks.scientific@gmail.com>,
- <fakhrul@ugc.gov.bd>,
- <secretary@ugc.gov.bd>,
- <syrawarn@gmail.com>,
- <nazmul@ugc.gov.bd>,
- <director_research@ugc.gov.bd>,
- <ferdousugc@gmail.com>,
- <vc@rmit.edu.au>,
- <brooke.griffin@rmit.edu.au>,
- <ea.vc@rmit.edu.au>,
- <jason.ngam@rmit.edu.au>,
- <nicole.hendrie@rmit.edu.au>,
- <contact@dhakatribune.com>,
- <vc@cityuniversity.ac.bd>,
- <registrar@cityuniversity.ac.bd>,
- <registrar@smuct.ac.bd>,
- <registrar@du.ac.bd>,

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

- <contact.centre@education.gov.au>,
- <consular.canberra@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <labour.canberra@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <commerce.canberra@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <mission.canberra@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <ahc.dhaka@dfat.gov.au>,
- <consular.dhaka@dfat.gov.au>,
- <fs@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <dirfso@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <ssa@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <aswelfare@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <dgcnw@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <dirwelfare@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <asconsular2@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <vso@dfat.gov.au>,
- <ijtaksamanta@gmail.com>,
- <ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com>,
- <abserju@yahoo.com>,
- <d.sun@hw.ac.uk>,
- <drsaifur@diu.edu.bd>,
- <fukudaiko@yahoo.com>,
- <provc@buft.edu.bd>,
- <s.islam05@gmail.com>,
- <saiful.bste@cityuniversity.ac.bd>,

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
 Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*}
 Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
 MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process,
 color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
 PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg
& Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam);
 Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
 Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
 Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
 University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and
 Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

- <ftm@nhrc.org.bd>,
- <chairman@nhrc.org.bd>,
- <secretary@nhrc.org.bd>,
- <liptonbjs@gmail.com>,
- <letters@theaustralian.com.au>,
- <victoria@theaustralian.com.au>,
- <wa@theaustralian.com.au>,
- <act@theaustralian.com.au>,
- <scba.bd@gmail.com>,
- <dunning@callinanchambers.com.au>,
- <contact@austbar.asn.au>,
- <media@austbar.asn.au>,
- <info@barindia.in>,
- <barindia1959@gmail.com>,
- <service@americanbar.org>,
- ContactUs@BarCouncil.org.uk,<contactus@barcouncil.org.uk>,
- <press@barcouncil.org.uk>,
- <info.eseaprobangkok@amnesty.org>,
- <contactus@amnesty.org>,
- <head_te@duet.ac.bd>,
- <reg_duet@duet.ac.bd>,
- <registrar@mbstu.ac.bd>,
- <drjalil@te.kuet.ac.bd>,
- <registrar@kuet.ac.bd>,

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

- <vc@kuet.ac.bd>,
- <ps2vc@kuet.ac.bd>,
- <bcmccrm@hotmail.com>,
- <chairman@tex.green.edu.bd>,
- <vc@green.edu.bd>,
- <headte@daffodilvarsity.edu.bd>,
- <vc@daffodilvarsity.edu.bd>,
- <drhaque@diu.edu.bd>,
- <drhaque@alumni.manchester.ac.uk>,
- <info@bubt.edu.bd>,
- <vc@bubt.edu.bd>,
- <vc@butex.edu.bd>,
- <registrar@butex.edu.bd>,
- <textile@primeasia.edu.bd>,
- <vc@primeasia.edu.bd>,
- <registrar@primeasia.edu.bd>,
- <faysal.tex@gmail.com>,
- <info@nub.ac.bd>,
- <ymislam@seu.edu.bd>,
- <vc@seu.edu.bd>,
- <mashud.ahmed@seu.edu.bd>,
- <registrar@seu.edu.bd>,
- <arun.guha@seu.edu.bd>,
- <head@dce.butex.edu.bd>,

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)³
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁴
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia

International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

- <butexdce@gmail.com>,
- <kamrul_regbuet@yahoo.com>,
- <rakib_ao@regtr.buet.ac.bd>,
- <saikatbarua@dce.buet.ac.bd>,
- <registrar@admin.iitd.ac.in>,
- <brmehta@physics.iitd.ernet.in>,
- <brmehta_p@hotmail.com>,
- <sukumarray@gmail.com>,
- <ijtskg40@gmail.com>,
- <sadhan53@yahoo.co.in>,
- <andrea.eckersley@rmit.edu.au>,
- <scott.mayson@rmit.edu.au>,
- <sean.ryan@rmit.edu.au>,
- <xin.wang@rmit.edu.au>,
- <academic.registrar@rmit.edu.au>,
- Grants@vla.vic.gov.au,<grants@vla.vic.gov.au>,
- <alice.payne@rmit.edu.au>,
- <ray.kirby@rmit.edu.au>,
- <igmartin@deakin.edu.au>,
- <calum.drummond@rmit.edu.au>,
- <arahman@duet.ac.bd>,
- <customer@bl.uk>,
- <rajiv.padhya@rmit.edu.au>,
- <khossain@citechco.net>,

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

- <bma.org.bd@gmail.com>,
- <ama@ama.com.au>,
- <iebhq@gmail.com>,
- <info@iebbd.org>,
- <ittfaqdigital@gmail.com>,
- <ittfaq.adsection@gmail.com>,
- <registrarju@gmail.com>,
- <registrar@juniv.edu>

Message Body

Date 7 November 2024

Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin

President

Office of President

The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

Office of President, Bangabhaban, Dhaka, Bangladesh

secretary@bangabhaban.gov.bd

press.secy@bangabhaban.gov.bd

ps_president@bangabhaban.gov.bd

akmmonirul31@gmail.com

Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Economist

Chief Advisor

Office of Chief Advisor

The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	---	--

State Guest House Jamuna, Dhaka, Bangladesh

majumderali1950@gmail.com

musfiguldu33@gmail.com

psecy@cao.gov.bd

secretary@cao.gov.bd

seafath.mahmud@cao.gov.bd

lutfey.siddiqi@cao.gov.bd

sultanpmo1974@gmail.com

ddresearch@cao.gov.bd

jamery.hasan@cao.gov.bd

May I seek income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>

Dear President and Chief Advisor,

Your Excellency for the peace of mankind

Your honour to ensure legal rights of Bangladeshi Citizen

Your honour to ensure legal safety of Bangladeshi Citizen

Your honour for the excellency of global leadership

Your honour for keeping a quality relation with the government of Australia

I would like to attach a letter (pdf file) for your kind assessment and consideration to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.

Your Honour; Please Pardon Me

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Best Regards for your excellency

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist

PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh)

Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing

Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066

School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry

Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)

Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology

University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India

BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia

Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College, Chittagong

Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh); MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	--	--

Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh Page | 121

Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.

Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)

International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg

Research Address since 2020

512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, engranowar06@gmail.com, +8801788396264

Please Visit the Profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Higher education and research support

- Anowar Hossain

To: cab_secy@cabinet.gov.bd, and 9 others · Tue, Jun 24 at 6:58 PM

Page | 122

To:

- <cab_secy@cabinet.gov.bd>,
- <secy_cnr@cabinet.gov.bd>,
- <addl_coord@cabinet.gov.bd>,
- <addl_dfa@cabinet.gov.bd>,
- <secretary@bangabhaban.gov.bd>,
- <ps_president@bangabhaban.gov.bd>,
- <j.secretary@bangabhaban.gov.bd>,
- <ds_service@bangabhaban.gov.bd>,
- <akmmonirul31@gmail.com>,
- <aps2@bangabhaban.gov.bd>

Message Body

Dear Sir/Madam,

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is self-approaching to enhance higher education and research support in Bangladesh and Australia School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32735.16801>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15718630>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus,

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg., City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg., BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	--	--

Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14837268>

Your Honour; Please Pardon Me

Best Regards for your excellency

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist

PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh)

Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing

Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066

School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry

Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)

Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology

University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India

BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia

Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College, Chittagong

Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh

Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.

Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)

International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg

Research Address since 2020

512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.). Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), M.Tech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁹ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	--	---

Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, engranowar06@gmail.com, +8801788396264

Please Visit the Profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

9.15 Evidence of communication with international crime tribunal of Bangladesh

Could you please assess the international case if the case can be proceeded to international court?

- Anowar Hossain

To: ictbdinvestigation@gmail.com · Sat, Feb 22 at 8:47 PM

Message Body

Lt. Gen.l (Retd.) Jahangir Alam Chowdhury

Special Assistant to Hon'ble Chief Adviser

Mr. Md. Khuda Baksh Chowdhury

Special Assistant to Hon'ble Chief Adviser

Mr. Namimul Ghani

Senior Secretary

Public Security Division

Ministry of Home Affairs

Mr. Md. Mazharul Hoque, PPM

Coordinator

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

International Crimes Tribunal

Mr. Muhammed Shahidullah Chowdhury, PPM

Co-Coordinator

International Crimes Tribunal

Investigation Agency, International Crimes Tribunal

Address: House no.87 & 93, Road no-11/A, Dhanmomdi R/A, Dhaka-1209

Dear Secretary and coordinators,

Could you please assess the international case if the case can be proceeded to international court through the international crime tribunal? I also need the support of international legal aids.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14048863>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is requesting to Mr. António Guterres, Secretary-General of United Nations for a legal stipend or legal award to proceed with legal proceeding of life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35976.12805>

Your Honour; Please Pardon Me

Best Regards for your excellency

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	--	--

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist

PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh)

Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing

Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066

School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry

Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)

Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology

University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India

BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia

Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College, Chittagong

Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh Page | 128

Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.

Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)

International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg

Research Address since 2020

512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, engranowar06@gmail.com, +8801788396264

Please Visit the Profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<http://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	--	--

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

9.16 Evidence of communications with ministry of home affairs, Australia

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

- Anowar Hossain

To: SFC@finance.gov.au, and 1 other · Thu, Nov 7, 2024 at 11:47 AM

- SFC@finance.gov.au,<sfc@finance.gov.au>,
- <feedback@finance.gov.au>

Message Body

Dear Officer,

I would like to forward a cc letter to the honour of Minister of Home affairs. Accordingly, I have attached a pdf file to the office of home affairs.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 November 2024; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>

Your Honour; Please Pardon Me

Best Regards for your excellency

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist

PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh)

Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia
Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066

School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry

Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)

Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology

University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India

BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia

Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College, Chittagong

Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh

Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology</p> <p>Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia</p> <p>International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva</p> <p>Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	--	--

Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.

Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)

International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg

Research Address since 2020

512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, engranowar06@gmail.com, +8801788396264

Please Visit the Profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

RE: Application 1-45173493323 [SEC=OFFICIAL]

- SFC

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

- sfc@finance.gov.au

To: me · Mon, Jan 6 at 9:09 AM

Engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Message Body

Page | 132

OFFICIAL

Dear Professor Hossain,

Thank you for contacting the Department of Finance. As previously communicated, please contact Home Affairs in relation to Immigration matter. The appropriate avenue to raise your concerns about the exercise of judicial functions, or the actions of Court Officials, is through the Court and appeal process. You may also wish to seek legal advice about your options.

I encourage you to seek independent advice. Finance is unable to assist you further.

Kind regards

Discretionary Payments Team

Discretionary Payments|Comcover and Discretionary Payment Claims Branch

Department of Finance

T: 1800 227 572

E: sfc@finance.gov.au

A: One Canberra Avenue, Forrest ACT 2603

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is requesting to Mr. António Guterres, Secretary-General of United Nations for a legal stipend or legal award to proceed with legal proceeding of life-threatening ...

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	---	--

- Grants
- grants@vla.vic.gov.au

To: me · Sun, Jan 19 at 3:39 PM

Engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Message Body

Thank you for contacting Victoria Legal Aid Grants and Quality Assurance. From Monday 23 December until Friday 3 January, we will be operating with a skeleton staff and you may experience some delays in responses to your enquiry.

Your enquiry is important to us and we appreciate your patience during this time. Thank you

Appreciate your assistance with this request

Thank you

Victoria Legal Aid's website makes it easier for all Victorians to find services and information to help with their legal problem. Visit www.legalaid.vic.gov.au.

9.17 Evidence of recent communication with high commission of Bangladesh, Australia

Anowar Hossain

To: cab_secy@cabinet.gov.bd, and 3 others · Thu, Nov 7, 2024 at 4:48 PM

Message Body

----- Forwarded Message -----

From: Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To: secretary@bangabhaban.gov.bd <secretary@bangabhaban.gov.bd>;
press.secyc@bangabhaban.gov.bd <press.secyc@bangabhaban.gov.bd>;
ps_president@bangabhaban.gov.bd <ps_president@bangabhaban.gov.bd>;
akmmonirul31@gmail.com <akmmonirul31@gmail.com>; majumderali1950@gmail.com
 <majumderali1950@gmail.com>; musfiquldu33@gmail.com <musfiquldu33@gmail.com>;
psecyc@cao.gov.bd <psecyc@cao.gov.bd>; secretary@cao.gov.bd <secretary@cao.gov.bd>;
seafath.mahmud@cao.gov.bd <seafath.mahmud@cao.gov.bd>; lutfey.siddiqi@cao.gov.bd
 <lutfey.siddiqi@cao.gov.bd>; sultanpmo1974@gmail.com <sultanpmo1974@gmail.com>;
ddresearch@cao.gov.bd <ddresearch@cao.gov.bd>; jamery.hasan@cao.gov.bd
 <jamery.hasan@cao.gov.bd>

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Cc: lijing.wang@rmit.edu.au <lijing.wang@rmit.edu.au>; robert.shanks@rmit.edu.au <robert.shanks@rmit.edu.au>; robert.shanks.scientific@gmail.com <robert.shanks.scientific@gmail.com>; fakhrul@ugc.gov.bd <fakhrul@ugc.gov.bd>; secretary@ugc.gov.bd <secretary@ugc.gov.bd>; syrawarn@gmail.com <syrawarn@gmail.com>; nazmul@ugc.gov.bd <nazmul@ugc.gov.bd>; director_research@ugc.gov.bd <director_research@ugc.gov.bd>; ferdousugc@gmail.com <ferdousugc@gmail.com>; vc@rmit.edu.au <vc@rmit.edu.au>; brooke.griffin@rmit.edu.au <brooke.griffin@rmit.edu.au>; ea.vc@rmit.edu.au <ea.vc@rmit.edu.au>; jason.ngam@rmit.edu.au <jason.ngam@rmit.edu.au>; nicole.hendrie@rmit.edu.au <nicole.hendrie@rmit.edu.au>; contact@dhakatribune.com <contact@dhakatribune.com>; vc@cityuniversity.ac.bd <vc@cityuniversity.ac.bd>; registrar@cityuniversity.ac.bd <registrar@cityuniversity.ac.bd>; registrar@smuct.ac.bd <registrar@smuct.ac.bd>; registrar@du.ac.bd <registrar@du.ac.bd>; contact.centre@education.gov.au <contact.centre@education.gov.au>; consular.canberra@mofa.gov.bd <consular.canberra@mofa.gov.bd>; labour.canberra@mofa.gov.bd <labour.canberra@mofa.gov.bd>; commerce.canberra@mofa.gov.bd <commerce.canberra@mofa.gov.bd>; mission.canberra@mofa.gov.bd <mission.canberra@mofa.gov.bd>; ahc.dhaka@dfat.gov.au <ahc.dhaka@dfat.gov.au>; consular.dhaka@dfat.gov.au <consular.dhaka@dfat.gov.au>; fs@mofa.gov.bd <fs@mofa.gov.bd>; dirfso@mofa.gov.bd <dirfso@mofa.gov.bd>; ssa@mofa.gov.bd <ssa@mofa.gov.bd>; aswelfare@mofa.gov.bd <aswelfare@mofa.gov.bd>; dgcnw@mofa.gov.bd <dgcnw@mofa.gov.bd>; dirwelfare@mofa.gov.bd <dirwelfare@mofa.gov.bd>; asconsular2@mofa.gov.bd <asconsular2@mofa.gov.bd>; vso@dfat.gov.au <vso@dfat.gov.au>; ijtaksamanta@gmail.com <ijtaksamanta@gmail.com>; ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com <ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com>; abserju@yahoo.com <abserju@yahoo.com>; d.sun@hw.ac.uk <d.sun@hw.ac.uk>; drsaifur@diu.edu.bd <drsaifur@diu.edu.bd>; fukudaiko@yahoo.com <fukudaiko@yahoo.com>; provc@buft.edu.bd <provc@buft.edu.bd>; s.islam05@gmail.com <s.islam05@gmail.com>; saiful.bste@cityuniversity.ac.bd <saiful.bste@cityuniversity.ac.bd>; ftm@nhrc.org.bd <ftm@nhrc.org.bd>; chairman@nhrc.org.bd <chairman@nhrc.org.bd>; secretary@nhrc.org.bd <secretary@nhrc.org.bd>; liptonbjs@gmail.com <liptonbjs@gmail.com>; letters@theaustralian.com.au <letters@theaustralian.com.au>; victoria@theaustralian.com.au <victoria@theaustralian.com.au>; wa@theaustralian.com.au <wa@theaustralian.com.au>; act@theaustralian.com.au <act@theaustralian.com.au>; scba.bd@gmail.com <scba.bd@gmail.com>; dunning@callinanchambers.com.au <dunning@callinanchambers.com.au>; contact@austbar.asn.au <contact@austbar.asn.au>; media@austbar.asn.au <media@austbar.asn.au>; info@barindia.in <info@barindia.in>;

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCRC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	---	--

barindia1959@gmail.com <barindia1959@gmail.com>; service@americanbar.org
 <service@americanbar.org>; ContactUs@BarCouncil.org.uk <contactus@barcouncil.org.uk>;
 press@barcouncil.org.uk <press@barcouncil.org.uk>; info.eseaprobangkok@amnesty.org
 <info.eseaprobangkok@amnesty.org>; contactus@amnesty.org <contactus@amnesty.org>;
 head_te@duet.ac.bd <head_te@duet.ac.bd>; reg_duet@duet.ac.bd <reg_duet@duet.ac.bd>;
 registrar@mbstu.ac.bd <registrar@mbstu.ac.bd>; drjalil@te.kuet.ac.bd <drjalil@te.kuet.ac.bd>;
 registrar@kuet.ac.bd <registrar@kuet.ac.bd>; vc@kuet.ac.bd <vc@kuet.ac.bd>;
 ps2vc@kuet.ac.bd <ps2vc@kuet.ac.bd>; bcmccrm@hotmail.com <bcmccrm@hotmail.com>;
 chairman@tex.green.edu.bd <chairman@tex.green.edu.bd>; vc@green.edu.bd
 <vc@green.edu.bd>; headte@daffodilvarsity.edu.bd <headte@daffodilvarsity.edu.bd>;
 vc@daffodilvarsity.edu.bd <vc@daffodilvarsity.edu.bd>; drhaque@diu.edu.bd
 <drhaque@diu.edu.bd>; drhaque@alumni.manchester.ac.uk
 <drhaque@alumni.manchester.ac.uk>; info@bubt.edu.bd <info@bubt.edu.bd>; vc@bubt.edu.bd
 <vc@bubt.edu.bd>; vc@butex.edu.bd <vc@butex.edu.bd>; registrar@butex.edu.bd
 <registrar@butex.edu.bd>; textile@primeasia.edu.bd <textile@primeasia.edu.bd>;
 vc@primeasia.edu.bd <vc@primeasia.edu.bd>; registrar@primeasia.edu.bd
 <registrar@primeasia.edu.bd>; faysal.tex@gmail.com <faysal.tex@gmail.com>;
 info@nub.ac.bd <info@nub.ac.bd>; ymislam@seu.edu.bd <ymislam@seu.edu.bd>;
 vc@seu.edu.bd <vc@seu.edu.bd>; mashud.ahmed@seu.edu.bd <mashud.ahmed@seu.edu.bd>;
 registrar@seu.edu.bd <registrar@seu.edu.bd>; arun.guha@seu.edu.bd <arun.guha@seu.edu.bd>;
 head@dce.butex.edu.bd <head@dce.butex.edu.bd>; butexdce@gmail.com
 <butexdce@gmail.com>; kamrul_regbuet@yahoo.com <kamrul_regbuet@yahoo.com>;
 rakib_ao@regtr.buet.ac.bd <rakib_ao@regtr.buet.ac.bd>; saikatbarua@dce.buet.ac.bd
 <saikatbarua@dce.buet.ac.bd>; registrar@admin.iitd.ac.in <registrar@admin.iitd.ac.in>;
 brmehta@physics.iitd.ernet.in <brmehta@physics.iitd.ernet.in>; brmehta_p@hotmail.com
 <brmehta_p@hotmail.com>; sukumarroy@gmail.com <sukumarroy@gmail.com>;
 ijtskg40@gmail.com <ijtskg40@gmail.com>; sadhan53@yahoo.co.in
 <sadhan53@yahoo.co.in>; andrea.eckersley@rmit.edu.au <andrea.eckersley@rmit.edu.au>;
 scott.mayson@rmit.edu.au <scott.mayson@rmit.edu.au>; sean.ryan@rmit.edu.au
 <sean.ryan@rmit.edu.au>; xin.wang@rmit.edu.au <xin.wang@rmit.edu.au>;
 academic.registrar@rmit.edu.au <academic.registrar@rmit.edu.au>; Grants@vla.vic.gov.au
 <grants@vla.vic.gov.au>; alice.payne@rmit.edu.au <alice.payne@rmit.edu.au>;
 ray.kirby@rmit.edu.au <ray.kirby@rmit.edu.au>; igmartin@deakin.edu.au
 <igmartin@deakin.edu.au>; calum.drummond@rmit.edu.au <calum.drummond@rmit.edu.au>;
 arahman@duet.ac.bd <arahman@duet.ac.bd>; customer@bl.uk <customer@bl.uk>;
 rajiv.padhya@rmit.edu.au <rajiv.padhya@rmit.edu.au>; khossain@citechco.net
 <khossain@citechco.net>; bma.org.bd@gmail.com <bma.org.bd@gmail.com>;

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

ama@ama.com.au <ama@ama.com.au>; iebhq@gmail.com <iebhq@gmail.com>;
info@iebbd.org <info@iebbd.org>; ittefaqdigital@gmail.com <ittefaqdigital@gmail.com>;
ittefaq.adsection@gmail.com <ittefaq.adsection@gmail.com>; registrarju@gmail.com
<registrarju@gmail.com>; registrar@juniv.edu <registrar@juniv.edu>

Page | 136

Sent: Thursday, November 7, 2024 at 10:33:17 AM GMT+6

Subject: Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

Date 7 November 2024

Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin

President

Office of President

The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

Office of President, Bangabhaban, Dhaka, Bangladesh

secretary@bangabhaban.gov.bd

press.secy@bangabhaban.gov.bd

ps_president@bangabhaban.gov.bd

akmmonirul31@gmail.com

Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Economist

Chief Advisor

Office of Chief Advisor

The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

State Guest House Jamuna, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	---	---

majumderali1950@gmail.com

musfiguldu33@gmail.com

psecy@cao.gov.bd

secretary@cao.gov.bd

seafath.mahmud@cao.gov.bd

lutfey.siddiqi@cao.gov.bd

sultanpmo1974@gmail.com

ddresearch@cao.gov.bd

jamery.hasan@cao.gov.bd

May I seek income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>

Dear President and Chief Advisor,

Your Excellency for the peace of mankind

Your honour to ensure legal rights of Bangladeshi Citizen

Your honour to ensure legal safety of Bangladeshi Citizen

Your honour for the excellency of global leadership

Your honour for keeping a quality relation with the government of Australia

I would like to attach a letter (pdf file) for your kind assessment and consideration to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.

Your Honour; Please Pardon Me

Best Regards for your excellency

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh)

Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing

Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066

School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry

Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)

Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology

University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India

BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia

Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College, Chittagong

Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh

Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.). Postdoc² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	--	--

Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.

Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)

International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg

Research Address since 2020

512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, engranowar06@gmail.com, +8801788396264

Please Visit the Profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

9.18 Evidence of recent communication with United Nations

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is requesting to Mr. António Guterres, Secretary-General of United Nations for a legal stipend or legal award to proceed with legal proceeding of life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school

Page | 140

- Anowar Hossain

To: lijing.wang@rmit.edu.au, and 121 others, Cc: customer@bl.uk · Sun, Jan 19 at 3:35 PM <lijing.wang@rmit.edu.au>,

- <robert.shanks@rmit.edu.au>,
- <robert.shanks.scientific@gmail.com>,
- <contact.centre@education.gov.au>,
- <vc@rmit.edu.au>,
- <brooke.griffin@rmit.edu.au>,
- <ea.vc@rmit.edu.au>,
- <jason.ngam@rmit.edu.au>,
- <nicole.hendrie@rmit.edu.au>,
- <vso@dfat.gov.au>,
- <secretary@bangabhaban.gov.bd>,
- <press.secy@bangabhaban.gov.bd>,
- <ps_president@bangabhaban.gov.bd>,
- <akmmonirul31@gmail.com>,
- <majumderali1950@gmail.com>,
- <musfiquldu33@gmail.com>,
- <psecy@cao.gov.bd>,
- <secretary@cao.gov.bd>,
- <seafath.mahmud@cao.gov.bd>,

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
 Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD²
 Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
 MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process,
 color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
 PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anwar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg
& Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam);
 Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
 Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
 Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
 University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anwar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and
 Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

- <lutfey.siddiqi@cao.gov.bd>,
- <sultanpmo1974@gmail.com>,
- <ddresearch@cao.gov.bd>,
- <jamery.hasan@cao.gov.bd>,
- <infoservice@humanrights.gov.au>,
- <consular.canberra@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <labour.canberra@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <commerce.canberra@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <mission.canberra@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <registrar@du.ac.bd>,
- <publicaffairs.unit@icc-cpi.int>,
- <otpnnewsdesk@icc-cpi.int>,
- <liaisonofficeny@icc-cpi.int>,
- Security@icc-cpi.int,<security@icc-cpi.int>,
- Procurement@icc-cpi.int,<procurement@icc-cpi.int>,
- <asp@icc-cpi.int>,
- <tgchague@tgchambers.com>,
- ICCVisits@icc-cpi.int,<iccvisits@icc-cpi.int>,
- <information@icj-cij.org>,
- <cdlbd21@gmail.com>,
- <customer@bl.uk>,
- <library@icj-cij.org>,
- <repository@rmit.edu.au>,
- Registry@hcourt.gov.au,<registry@hcourt.gov.au>,

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

- <fakhrul@ugc.gov.bd>,
- <secretary@ugc.gov.bd>,
- <syrawarn@gmail.com>,
- <nazmul@ugc.gov.bd>,
- <director_research@ugc.gov.bd>,
- <ferdousugc@gmail.com>,
- <chairman@ugc.gov.bd>,
- <mustafiz@ugc.gov.bd>,
- <mustafizugc@gmail.com>,
- <pschairman@ugc.gov.bd>,
- <vc@cityuniversity.ac.bd>,
- <registrar@cityuniversity.ac.bd>,
- <s.islam05@gmail.com>,
- <saiful.bste@cityuniversity.ac.bd>,
- <ijtskg40@gmail.com>,
- <sadhan53@yahoo.co.in>,
- <ahc.dhaka@dfat.gov.au>,
- <consular.dhaka@dfat.gov.au>,
- <fs@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <dirfso@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <ssa@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <aswelfare@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <dgcnw@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <dirwelfare@mofa.gov.bd>,

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
 Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*}
 Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
 MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process,
 color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
 PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anwar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCME College of Engg
& Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam);
 Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
 Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
 Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
 University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anwar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and
 Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

- <asconsular2@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <ftm@nhrc.org.bd>,
- <chairman@nhrc.org.bd>,
- <secretary@nhrc.org.bd>,
- <liptonbjs@gmail.com>,
- <letters@theaustralian.com.au>,
- <victoria@theaustralian.com.au>,
- <wa@theaustralian.com.au>,
- <act@theaustralian.com.au>,
- <dunning@callinanchambers.com.au>,
- <contact@austbar.asn.au>,
- <media@austbar.asn.au>,
- <scba.bd@gmail.com>,
- <info@barindia.in>,
- <barindia1959@gmail.com>,
- <service@americanbar.org>,
- ContactUs@BarCouncil.org.uk,<contactus@barcouncil.org.uk>,
- <press@barcouncil.org.uk>,
- <info.eseaprobangkok@amnesty.org>,
- <contactus@amnesty.org>,
- <vc@butex.edu.bd>,
- <registrar@butex.edu.bd>,
- <head@dce.butex.edu.bd>,
- <butexdce@gmail.com>,

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

- <andrea.eckersley@rmit.edu.au>,
- <scott.mayson@rmit.edu.au>,
- <sean.ryan@rmit.edu.au>,
- <xin.wang@rmit.edu.au>,
- <academic.registrar@rmit.edu.au>,
- Grants@vla.vic.gov.au,<grants@vla.vic.gov.au>,
- <alice.payne@rmit.edu.au>,
- <ray.kirby@rmit.edu.au>,
- <calum.drummond@rmit.edu.au>,
- <arahman@duet.ac.bd>,
- <yunus@yunuscentre.org>,
- <khossain@citechco.net>,
- <ittfaqdigital@gmail.com>,
- <ittfaq.adsection@gmail.com>,
- <ijtaksamanta@gmail.com>,
- <ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com>,
- <abserju@yahoo.com>,
- <ehossainsau@gmail.com>,
- <provc@buft.edu.bd>,
- <mihmondal@gmail.com>,
- <mihmondal@yahoo.com>,
- <mihmondal@ru.ac.bd>,
- <drjalil@te.kuet.ac.bd>,
- <mhuddincu@yahoo.com>,

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	--	--

- <mhuddin.acce@cu.ac.bd>,
- <bshamimsc@gmail.com>,
- <aseyam@ncsu.edu>,
- <malgorzata.zimniewska@iwnirz.pl>,
- <xungai.wang@polyu.edu.hk>,
- <mlg54@hotmail.com>,
- <mg@sdc.org.uk>

Cc:

- <customer@bl.uk>

Message Body

Dear Nobel Winner/Chairman/Sir/Madam/Professor/Dr./Scientist/President/Chief advisor/lawyer/Minister/Vice Chancellor/High Commissioner/Secretary/Director/Editor,

Your excellency for the peace of mankind.

May I attach a link and pdf file of a cc letter.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is requesting to Mr. António Guterres, Secretary-General of United Nations for a legal stipend or legal award to proceed with legal proceeding of life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35976.12805>

Your Honour; Please Pardon Me

Best Regards for your excellency

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist

PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh)

Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066

School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry

Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)

Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology

University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India

BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia

Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College, Chittagong

Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh

Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology</p> <p>Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)³ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁴ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia</p> <p>International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva</p> <p>Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	--	--

Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.

Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)

International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg

Research Address since 2020

512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, engranowar06@gmail.com, +8801788396264

Please Visit the Profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Higher education and research

- Anowar Hossain

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

To: rcs-unbd@un.org · Tue, Jun 24 at 5:46 PM

Message Body

Dear Sir/Madam,

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is self-approaching to enhance higher education and research support in Bangladesh and Australia School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).

Page | 148

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32735.16801>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15718630>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14837268>

Your Honour; Please Pardon Me

Best Regards for your excellency

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist

PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh)

Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing

Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCME College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	--	---

PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066

School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry

Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)

Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology

University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India

BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia

Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College, Chittagong

Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh

Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.

Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)

International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg

Research Address since 2020

512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, engranowar06@gmail.com, +8801788396264

Please Visit the Profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Letter of request for legal action and support to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

- Anowar Hossain

To: lewisg@un.org, Cc: s.vize@unesco.org, and 6 others · Thu, Mar 13 at 3:57 PM

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)³ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁴ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India, Australia, Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	---	--

To:

- <lewisg@un.org>

Cc:

- <s.vize@unesco.org>,
- <fs@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <dirfso@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <ssa@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <vc@rmit.edu.au>,
- <brooke.griffin@rmit.edu.au>,
- <vso@dfat.gov.au>

Message Body

Dear Ms. Gwyn Lewis,

Your honour for your leading to United Nations in Bangladesh.

I would like to inform and submit following letters to your office of United Nations, Bangladesh office. May I seek your action and support to proceed my letter and appeal. I would like to meet your office if you have any function about my letters and appeal to United Nations. Mr. António Guterres, Secretary-General of United Nations is coming to your office on 15 March 2025. May I seek your permission to meet with the secretary general of the United Nations on 15 March 2025 if my approach is relevant with the following letters.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is requesting to Mr. António Guterres, Secretary-General of United Nations for a legal stipend or legal award to proceed with legal proceeding of life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35976.12805>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14934539>

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is seeking legal support to The Hon Anthony Albanese MP, Prime Minister, Australia for the conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in PhD school, RMIT

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

University. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19140.19849>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10990583>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14837268>

Page | 152

This e-mail has attachment of two pdf files.

Your Honour; Please Pardon Me

Best Regards for your excellency

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist

PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh)

Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing

Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066

School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry

Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)

Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	--	--

University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India

BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia

Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College, Chittagong

Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh

Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.

Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)

International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court,

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg

Page | 154

Research Address since 2020

512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, engranowar06@gmail.com, +8801788396264

Please Visit the Profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

9.19 Evidence of communication with international human rights commission/human rights commission of United Nations

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD researcher, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship from 2020 to still now.

Anowar Hossain

engr.anowar@yahoo.com

To: ferdous@bjri.gov.bd, and 198 others · Tue, May 9, 2023 at 9:40 AM

To:

- <ferdous@bjri.gov.bd>,
- <abm.abdullah@primeasia.edu.bd>,

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
 Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD²
 Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
 MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process,
 color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
 PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg
& Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam);
 Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
 Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
 Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
 University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and
 Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

- <provc@buft.edu.bd>,
- <chairman@tex.green.edu.bd>,
- <izerin@niter.edu.bd>,
- <mredhaahad@gmail.com>,
- <nucbd.edu@gmail.com>,
- <bcmccrm@yahoo.com>,
- <iamzakdude@gmail.com>,
- <skr@ketex.com>,
- <shossain@gmail.com>,
- <mobarak.hossain61@gmail.com>,
- <abdur.razzak@viyellatexgroup.com>,
- <sghosh@emich.edu>,
- <roysn19@yahoo.com>,
- <ketex.sckhatua@gmail.com>,
- <nnm@colorantindia.com>,
- <learningclub@rediffmail.com>,
- <majkajol@gmail.com>,
- <timollah@gmail.com>,
- <cedricc@fastmail.com>,
- <shahid@duet.ac.bd>,
- <abm.abdullah45@yahoo.com>,
- <ummeyrayhan@duet.ac.bd>,
- <zahangir@du.ac.bd>,
- <ganesh@duet.ac.bd>,

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

- <reazmbstu@gmail.com>,
- <kafitex@duet.ac.bd>,
- <drjalilATte@kuet.ac.bd.com>,
- <jalilteAT@gmail.com>,
- <alexander.buesgen@hs-niederrhein.de>,
- <d.sun@hw.ac.uk>,
- <rnd@ketex.com>,
- <ranojit_phybuet@yahoo.com>,
- <abserju@yahoo.com>,
- <mahbub.mbstu@yahoo.com>,
- <fukudaiko@yahoo.com>,
- <chairman@bcsir.gov.bd>,
- <forhadbd77@gmail.com>,
- <sazaman_2006@yahoo.com>,
- <baizidrahman97@gmail.com>,
- <arifuzzaman.cu@gmail.com>,
- <muna.dinar@gmail.com>,
- <arnobbasak@ymail.com>,
- <jarin123_vns@hotmail.com>,
- <sumanchandrapaulbste.aust035@gmail.com>,
- <kanon201213076@gmail.com>,
- <rupokkhan83@gmail.com>,
- <murshida076@gmail.com>,
- <mihmondal@yahoo.com>,

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia

International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCRC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

- <sdhar@cuet.ac.bd>,
- <huddin72@gmail.com>,
- <ijtskg40@gmail.com>,
- <mukhrtjee.asis27@gmail.com>,
- <atin1957@yahoo.co.in>,
- <drdebashishdas@yahoo.co.in>,
- <dalapati_k@rediffmail.com>,
- <drsksett@yahoo.co.in>,
- <sadhan53@yahoo.co.in>,
- <jonathanorasugh@yahoo.com>,
- <kashmita.bh@gmail.com>,
- <arindambagchi58@gmail.com>,
- <engranowar06@gmail.com>,
- <djft.cu.pgdtm@gmail.com>,
- <s.islam05@gmail.com>,
- <arifsidikizaman@yahoo.com>,
- <sumon.duet.textile@gmail.com>,
- <humaunka@gmail.com>,
- <sharifultextiles@gmail.com>,
- <arunguha70@yahoo.com>,
- <ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com>,
- <kjkim@khu.ac.kr>,
- <adwaita19@rediffmail.com>,
- <ranjansatyabairagi@gmail.com>,

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

- <nilendu82.bhaumik@gmail.com>,
- <nafistextile@gmail.com>,
- <mdfaridulislam63@gmail.com>,
- <pubalina@gmail.com>,
- <rabeya.islam@live.com>,
- <saniyat.islam@rmit.edu.au>,
- <rajibjuly1974@gmail.com>,
- <shossain_cp@du.ac.bd>,
- <repository@rmit.edu.au>,
- <mahmudrahman@yahoo.com>,
- <shawkut19@gmail.com>,
- <tanvirahman@bau.edu.bd>,
- <rmitstudent.connect@edu.au>,
- <sarah.palmer@rmit.edu.au>,
- <rmit.connect@edu.au>,
- <enganowar06@gmail.com>,
- <wazed@textile.iitd.ac.in>,
- <toj331@hotmail.com>,
- <Satyaranjan.Bairagi@glasgow.ac.uk>,
- <lijing.wang@rmit.edu.au>,
- <robert.shanks@rmit.edu.au>,
- <safercommunity@rmit.edu.au>,
- <s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au>,
- <scott.mayson@rmit.edu.au>,

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)³
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁴
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia

International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCME College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

- <sean.ryan@rmit.edu.au>,
- <shadi.houshyar@rmit.edu.au>,
- <steve.michielsen@rmit.edu.au>,
- <xin.wang@rmit.edu.au>,
- <rts-dscresearchservicecentre@rmit.edu.au>,
- <andrea.eckersley@rmit.edu.au>,
- <mac.fergusson@rmit.edu.au>,
- <shelley.macrae@rmit.edu.au>,
- <academic.registrar@rmit.edu.au>,
- <vc@rmit.edu.au>,
- <dvcr@rmit.com.au>,
- <denise.cuthbert@rmit.edu.au>,
- <robyn.healy@rmit.edu.au>,
- <rusu@rmit.edu.au>,
- <alice.payne@rmit.edu.au>,
- <amber.douglas@rmit.edu.au>,
- <sgr.scholarships@rmit.edu.au>,
- <alec.cameron@rmit.edu.au>,
- <alec.cameron@aarnet.edu.au>,
- <david.castle@rmit.edu.au>,
- <calum.drummond@rmit.edu.au>,
- <contact.centre@education.gov.au>,
- <yourcustomer.service@defence.gov.au>,
- <smrkabir@gmail.com>,

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

- <prof.shossain3@gmail.com>,
- <drdulalbarua@gmail.com>,
- <syed_hasan04@yahoo.com>,
- <hasanfbru51@gmail.com>,
- <safayeth@gmail.com>,
- <samrat.cse@cityuniversity.edu.bd>,
- <humayun.eee@cityuniversity.edu.bd>,
- <monimuluque4@gmail.com>,
- <houdanzmul@gmail.com>,
- <zeba.khanam18@gmail.com>,
- <sharmin.nusrath@yahoo.com>,
- <mahmud004825@gmail.com>,
- <muhibiftakhar@gmail.com>,
- <tareque.ms@gmail.com>,
- <shahinkabir77@gmail.com>,
- <dani.andree@rmit.edu.au>,
- <nahid.islam@idp.com>,
- <ashwini@smita-iitd.com>,
- <bhupendra.singh.butola@textile.iitd.ac.in>,
- <sabbih.hossain@gmail.com>,
- <foreign.minister@dfat.gov.au>,
- <jason.clare.mp@aph.gov.au>,
- <fm@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <minister@moedu.gov.bd>,

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology</p> <p>Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia</p> <p>International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva</p> <p>Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	--	--

- <info@nhrc.org.bd>,
- <headquarters@ihrchq.org>,
- <office@ihrchq.org>,
- <geneva@ihrchq.org>,
- <yunus@yunuscentre.org>,
- <vc@butex.edu.bd>,
- <vc@duet.ac.bd>,
- <provacademic@caluniv.ac.in>,
- <akcstat@caluniv.ac.in>,
- <oic_opscr@police.gov.bd>,
- <addligcid@police.gov.bd>,
- <chairman@ugc.gov.bd>,
- <contact.ugc@nic.in>,
- <fsa@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <NOSSC-Canberra@afp.gov.au>,
- <NOSSC@afp.gov.au>,
- <vpwebsite-mgr@police.vic.gov.au>,
- <missing@afp.gov.au>,
- <conduct@dfat.gov.au>,
- <hc@bhcanberra.com>,
- <bshamimsc@gmail.com>,
- <heath.mcdonald@rmit.edu.au>,
- <mark.sanderson@rmit.edu.au>,
- <namita.choudhury@rmit.edu.au>,

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

- <asen@fas.harvard.edu>,
- <phoebesuh@fas.harvard.edu>,
- <alain.aspect@institutoptique.fr>,
- <Advocate.islam14@gmail.com>,
- <Shaikat_hemonto@yahoo.com>,
- <Shrwardi.1984@gmail.com>,
- <cims16@yahoo.com>,
- <mhuddincu@yahoo.com>,
- <jahirugc@gmail.com>,
- <igor.abrikosov@liu.se>,
- <fredrik.all@kva.se>,
- <maria.asp@kva.se>,
- <kristina.wolff@nobel.kva.se>,
- <library@nobel.no>,
- <postmaster@nobel.no>,
- <berit.reissandersen@dlapiper.com>,
- <berit.reiss-andersen@dlapiper.com>,
- <bib@nupi.no>,
- <post@nupi.no>,
- <ulf.danielsson@physics.uu.se>,
- <Aisha.rehman@rmit.edu.au>,
- <zeyad.nesa@rmit.edu.au>,
- <nauman.choudhury@rmit.edu.au>,
- <Sutapa.choudhury@rmit.edu.au>,

<p>Nobel Nominee Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	--	--

- <Karien.dekker@rmit.edu.au>,
- <naveta.kumari@rmit.edu.au>,
- <Vipul.bansal@rmit.edu.au>,
- <dinesh.kumar@rmit.edu.au>,
- <shahruzzaman@du.ac.bd>
- **Message Body**

Dear Respected Nobel Laureates, Ministers, Professors, Scientists, Researchers, Executive professionals, Human Rights professionals, Lawyers, education professionals, Executive concern of education compliance, supervisors at PhD school, Criminal investigation departments, Police Departments in home and abroad, copy right concerns of Nobel office, Office of Nobel organization, The Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences, Nobel committee member for Nobel prize in peace and physics,

I am happy to write this letter as 'living person' of RMIT student/researcher community at RMIT University, Australia.

As I faced life-threatening in my PhD school at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University; I would like to contribute my understanding for future protection of student community and professor community all over the world as part of my PhD contribution and critical life threatening in my PhD journey. I have also attached my ongoing invention at PhD school.

Planned for submission and nomination for the nobel prize in peace.

Education is the basic needs of human being. The life-threatening, harassment and corruption are the obstacle of quality education. This case letters may influence for highest climbing and highest platform of global education.

Hossain, M. A. (2023g). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-01)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7890974>

[\(PDF\) Md. Anowar Hossain, My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School \(Part-01\) \(researchgate.net\)](#)

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Hossain, M. A. (2023h). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-02)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7892431>

(PDF) Md. Anowar Hossain, My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-02) (researchgate.net) Page | 164

Hossain, M. A. (2023h). Cut the cost of defence and invest more for education” when self-studying of student/researcher is an automatic contribution for national and worldwide development without getting money. *PREPRINT (Version 1) available at Research Square*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2831203/v1>

Planned for submission and nomination for the nobel prize in peace and/or camouflage physics.

Md. Anowar Hossain, Invention of PhD Thesis, RMIT University, Australia

The invention of PhD thesis has camouflage theory, color engineering, camouflage engineering, photon theory of camouflage, camouflage materials and camouflage physics for camouflage assessment against multidimensional combat backgrounds in UV-Vis-IR spectrums for defence protection. The concept of UV camouflage and simultaneous camouflage in UV-Vis-IR spectrums is an invention of PhD Thesis in camouflage engineering for defence protection.

Hossain, M. A. (2023i). *My declaration, acknowledgement and dedication to achieve PhD degree (Fashion & Textiles) on “camouflage textiles with technical coloration and incorporating illumination under multidimensional combat backgrounds”* [Textile Engineering, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2021]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18532.65925>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7898850>

Hossain, M. A. (2023e). *Camouflage textiles with technical coloration incorporating illumination, PhD student: 3820066, First milestone for the degree of doctor of philosophy* [Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2021]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15701.50403>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7898541>

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology</p> <p>Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia</p> <p>International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	--	--

Hossain, M. A. (2023d). *Camouflage textiles with technical coloration incorporating illumination under multidimensional combat backgrounds*, PhD student: 3820066, *Second milestone for the degree of doctor of philosophy* [Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2022]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15701.50403>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7898707>

Hossain, A. (2020). A Practical Guideline of Few Standardized Ready Made Shades of Natural Dyed Textiles. In A. K. Samanta & N. S. Awwad (Eds.), *Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments* (pp. 151-170). IntechOpen. <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.92360>

Hossain, A. (2021a). Concealment, Detection, Recognition, and Identification of Target Signature on Water Background under Natural Illumination. *International Journal of Science and Engineering Investigations*, 10(117), 1-11, Article 1011721-01. <http://www.ijsei.com/papers/ijsei-1011721-01.pdf>

Hossain, A. (2021b). Spectral simulation and method design of camouflage textiles for concealment of hyperspectral imaging in UV-Vis-IR against multidimensional combat background. *The Journal of the Textile Institute*, 1-12. [Spectral simulation and method design of camouflage textiles for concealment of hyperspectral imaging in UV-Vis-IR against multidimensional combat background](#)

Hossain, M. A. (2021a). Adaptive Camouflage Textiles with Thermochromic Colorant and Liquid Crystal for Multidimensional Combat Background, a Technical Approach for Advancement in Defence Protection. *American Journal of Materials Engineering and Technology*, 9(1), 31-47. <https://doi.org/10.12691/materials-9-1-3>

Hossain, M. A. (2021b). Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration and Incorporating Illumination. Presented in academic conference, First milestone of PhD candidature, RMIT

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

University, 12 February 2021, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson street, Brunswick, Vic-3056, Melbourne, Australia; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844692>.

Hossain, M. A. (2021c). Evaluation of Camouflage Coloration of Polyamide-6,6 Fabric by Comparing Simultaneous Spectrum in Visible and Near-Infrared Region for Defense Applications. In A. K. Samanta (Ed.), *Colorimetry* (pp. 1-22). IntechOpen. [Colorimetry | IntechOpen](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844692) Page | 166

Hossain, M. A. (2022a). Camouflage Assessment Of Aluminium Coated Textiles for Woodland and Desertland Combat Background in Visible and Infrared Spectrum under UV-Vis-IR Background Illumination. *Defence Science Journal*, 72(3), 359-370. <https://doi.org/10.14429/dsj.72.17731>

Hossain, M. A. (2022b, 15 February 2022). Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration and Incorporating Illumination under Multidimensional Combat Background. Presented in humanities and social context conference, second milestone of PhD candidature, RMIT University; 15 February 2022, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson street, Brunswick, Vic-3056, Melbourne, Australia; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844729>.

Hossain, M. A. (2022c). Ecofriendly Camouflage Textiles with Natural Sand-based Silicon Dioxide against Simultaneous Combat Background of Woodland, Desertland, Rockland, Concreteland and Water/Marine. *Preprint (Version 1) available at Research Square* [Ecofriendly Camouflage Textiles with Natural Sand-based Silicon Dioxide against Simultaneous Combat Background of Woodland, Desertland, Rockland, Concreteland and Water/Marine](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844692)

Hossain, M. A. (2022). Simulation of chromatic and achromatic assessments for camouflage textiles and combat background. *Journal of Defense Modeling and Simulation: Applications, Methodology, Technology*, 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.1177/15485129211067759>

Hossain, M. A. (2023a). Advancement in UV-Vis-IR camouflage Textiles for concealment of defense surveillance against multidimensional combat background. *PREPRINT (Version 1)*

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	--	--

available at Research Square. [Advancement in UV-Visible-IR Camouflage Textiles for Concealment of Defense Surveillance against Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds](#)

Hossain, M. A. (2023b). Camouflage textiles against advanced surveillance of defence in UV-Visible-IR spectrums for multidimensional combat backgrounds. 5th Edition of International Conference on Materials Science and Engineering, Accepted on 28 March 2023, Valencia, Spain; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844652>.

Hossain, M. A. (2023c). Camouflage Textiles against advanced surveillance of defence in UV-Visible-IR spectrums for Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds. Global Summit on Chemical Engineering and Catalysis (ISTRCEC 2023), accepted on 20 March 2023, Rome, Italy; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7847802>.

Hossain, M. A. (2023d). Camouflage textiles with technical coloration incorporating illumination under multidimensional combat backgrounds, PhD student: 3820066, Second milestone for the degree of doctor of philosophy [Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2022]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15701.50403>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7898707>

Hossain, M. A. (2023e). *Camouflage textiles with technical coloration incorporating illumination, PhD student: 3820066, First milestone for the degree of doctor of philosophy* [Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2021]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15701.50403>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7898541>

Hossain, M. A. (2023f). Coloration of polyamide-6,6 fabric with carbon black nano particle for camouflage textiles of simultaneous spectrum probe in visible and near infrared. *Preprint (Version 1) available at Research Square* <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2686707/v1>

Hossain, M. A. (2023g). Cr oxide coated woodland camouflage textiles for protection of defense target signature in UV-Visible-IR spectrum opposing of hyperspectral and digital imaging. *Preprint (Version 1) available at Research Square* 1-18. [Cr oxide coated woodland](#)

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

[camouflage textiles for protection of defense target signature in UV-Visible-IR spectrum opposing of hyperspectral and digital imaging](#)

Hossain, M. A. (2023i). My declaration, acknowledgement and dedication to achieve PhD degree (Fashion & Textiles) on “camouflage textiles with technical coloration and incorporating illumination under multidimensional combat backgrounds” [Textile Engineering, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2021]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18532.65925>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7898850>

Page | 168

Hossain, M. A. (2023j). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-01)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7890974>

Hossain, M. A. (2023k). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-02)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7892431>

Hossain, M. A. (2023l). Neuro-camouflaging is an Indicator of Human Camouflage, an Assumption of Brain Engineering for Self-protection against Criminal Attacking. *PREPRINT (Version 1) available at Research Square*. [Neuro-camouflaging is an Indicator of Human Camouflage, an Assumption of Brain Engineering for Self-protection against Criminal Attacking](#)

Hossain, M. A. (2023m, 10-11 July 2023). An optical platform of material engineering for design of camouflage product against multidimensional combat backgrounds from 400 nm to 2500 nm. Scholars World Congress on Material Science and Nanotechnology” (MatScience 2023), Accepted on 18 April 2023, Paris, France; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844597>.

Hossain, M. A. (2023n). Spectral simulation and materials design for camouflage textiles coloration against materials of multidimensional combat backgrounds in visible and near infrared spectrums. *MRS Communications* <https://doi.org/10.1557/s43579-023-00344-3>

Hossain, M. A. (2023o). UV-Visible-NIR camouflage textiles with natural plant based natural dyes on natural fibre against woodland combat background for defence protection. *Scientific Reports*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-31725-2>

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	--	---

A copyright application has been submitted to the office of Nobel Organization, The Nobel Foundation, P.O. Box 5232, SE-102 45 Stockholm, Sweden, Street address: Sturegatan 14, Stockholm.

Best Regards

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD Researcher (Technical Textiles), Thesis-final part, PhD Student ID: 3820066, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship).

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles), Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India.

BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Lecturer (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering, BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore, Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.

Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering, Newcastle University College, Chittagong, Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh.

Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile and Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Former Product Developer and Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd, Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying and Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.

Consultant (Textile coloration, Defence textiles, Technical textiles) since 2010

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Research Office: 512.01.12, 25, Dawson Street, Brunswick, Vic-3056, Melbourne, Australia,

E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, Mobile: +8801788396264

For details biography and profile,

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>, <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>, www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT, <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7848583>

Page | 170

[Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship, but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world]

9.20 Evidence of communication with international court

Seeking a case filing support under the category of international student at RMIT University, Australia

- Anowar Hossain

To: information@icj-cij.org · Mon, Feb 10 at 6:38 PM

Message Body

Dear Registrar,

Can I proceed a case filing under the category of international student at RMIT University, Australia? I notified a copy of the letter for your assessment and consideration.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is requesting to Mr. António Guterres, Secretary-General of United Nations for a legal stipend or legal award to proceed with legal proceeding of life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35976.12805>

Could you please let me know online or offline case filing process at international court?

Your Honour; Please Pardon Me

Best Regards for your excellency

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	---	--

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist

PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh)

Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing

Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066

School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry

Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)

Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology

University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India

BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia

Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College, Chittagong

Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh

Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Page | 172

Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.

Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)

International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg

Research Address since 2020

512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, engranowar06@gmail.com, +8801788396264

Please Visit the Profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder, Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India, Australia, Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	--	---

9.21 Evidence of communication with IDP, Australia

If IDP, Australia has any function to solve the raising issue of legal support or legal funding to carry out PhD research at RMIT University, Australia?

- Anowar Hossain

To: Nahid, Cc: tennealle.oshannessy@idp.com, and 1 other · Tue, Dec 10, 2024 at 5:37 AM

To:

- Nahid Islam, <nahid.islam@idp.com>

Cc:

- <tennealle.oshannessy@idp.com> ,
- <tennealle@hotmail.com>

Message Body

Dear Ms. Nahid Islam,

I hope that you are fine. I had communication with you in 2019-2020.

Could you please assess the attached letter if IDP, Australia has any function to solve the raising issue of legal support or legal funding to carry out PhD research at RMIT University, Australia? I would like to seek your official comments if IDP has any advice under the situation of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist. In previous time, I also kept cc e-mail to you.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is asking to Ms. Nardia Simpson, Australian High Commissioner for approving the extension of Australian Student VISA for legal and ethical claiming to Australian court under the ethical support of Minister of home affairs, foreign affairs and education. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14584.05126>

Your Honour; Please Pardon Me

Best Regards for your excellency

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist

PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh)

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia
Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing

Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066

School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry

Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)

Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology

University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India

BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia

Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College, Chittagong

Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh

Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology</p> <p>Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia</p> <p>International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCME College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva</p> <p>Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	--	--

Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.

Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)

International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg

Research Address since 2020

512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, engranowar06@gmail.com, +8801788396264

Please Visit the Profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

9.22 Evidence of communication with human rights commission of Bangladesh

To: me · Mon, Jul 7 at 2:34 PM

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Message Body

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<secretary@nhrc.org.bd>:

554: rejecting banned content

To: me · Mon, Jun 23 at 12:48 PM

Visit Message Body

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<secretary@nhrc.org.bd>:

554: rejecting banned content

Understanding of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist about different research area and research proposal for the peace of mankind

- Anowar Hossain

To: ferdous@bjri.gov.bd, and 151 others · Tue, May 14, 2024 at 11:24 AM
<ferdous@bjri.gov.bd>,

- <abm.abdullah@primeasia.edu.bd>,
- <provc@buft.edu.bd>,
- <chairman@tex.green.edu.bd>,
- <izerin@niter.edu.bd>,
- <mredhaahad@gmail.com>,
- <nucbd.edu@gmail.com>,
- <bcmccrm@yahoo.com>,
- <iamzakdude@gmail.com>,
- <skr@ketex.com>,
- <shossain@gmail.com>,
- <mobarak.hossain61@gmail.com>,

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)³
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁴
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

- <abdur.razzak@viyellatexgroup.com>,
- <sghosh@emich.edu>,
- <roysn19@yahoo.com>,
- <ketex.sckhatua@gmail.com>,
- <nmm@colorantindia.com>,
- <learningclub@rediffmail.com>,
- <majkajol@gmail.com>,
- <timollah@gmail.com>,
- <cedricc@fastmail.com>,
- <shahid@duet.ac.bd>,
- <abm.abdullah45@yahoo.com>,
- <ummeyrayhan@duet.ac.bd>,
- <zahangir@du.ac.bd>,
- <ganesh@duet.ac.bd>,
- <reazmbstu@gmail.com>,
- <kafitex@duet.ac.bd>,
- <drjalilATte@kuet.ac.bd.com>,
- <jalilteAT@gmail.com>,
- <alexander.buesgen@hs-niederrhein.de>,
- <d.sun@hw.ac.uk>,
- <rnd@ketex.com>,
- <ranojit_phybuet@yahoo.com>,
- <abserju@yahoo.com>,
- <mahbub.mbstu@yahoo.com>,

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

- <fukudaiko@yahoo.com>,
- <chairman@bcsir.gov.bd>,
- <forhadbd77@gmail.com>,
- <sazaman_2006@yahoo.com>,
- <baizidrahman97@gmail.com>,
- <arifuzzaman.cu@gmail.com>,
- <muna.dinar@gmail.com>,
- <arnobbasak@ymail.com>,
- <jarin123_vns@hotmail.com>,
- <sumanchandrapaulbste.aust035@gmail.com>,
- <kanon201213076@gmail.com>,
- <rupokkhan83@gmail.com>,
- <murshida076@gmail.com>,
- <mihmondal@yahoo.com>,
- <sdhar@cuet.ac.bd>,
- <huddin72@gmail.com>,
- <ijtskg40@gmail.com>,
- <mukhrtjee.asis27@gmail.com>,
- <atin1957@yahoo.co.in>,
- <drdebasishdas@yahoo.co.in>,
- <dalapati_k@rediffmail.com>,
- <drsksett@yahoo.co.in>,
- <sadhan53@yahoo.co.in>,
- <jonathanorasugh@yahoo.com>,

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁸
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia

International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

- <kashmita.bh@gmail.com>,
- <arindambagchi58@gmail.com>,
- <engranowar06@gmail.com>,
- <djft.cu.pgajtm@gmail.com>,
- <s.islam05@gmail.com>,
- <arifsidikizaman@yahoo.com>,
- <sumon.duet.textile@gmail.com>,
- <humaunka@gmail.com>,
- <sharifultextiles@gmail.com>,
- <arunguha70@yahoo.com>,
- <ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com>,
- <kjkim@khu.ac.kr>,
- <adwaita19@rediffmail.com>,
- <ranjansatyabairagi@gmail.com>,
- <nilendu82.bhaumik@gmail.com>,
- <nafistextile@gmail.com>,
- <mdfaridulislam63@gmail.com>,
- <pubalina@gmail.com>,
- <rabeya.islam@live.com>,
- <saniyat.islam@rmit.edu.au>,
- <rajibjuly1974@gmail.com>,
- <shossain_cp@du.ac.bd>,
- <repository@rmit.edu.au>,
- <mahmudrahman@yahoo.com>,

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

- <shawkut19@gmail.com>,
- <tanvirahman@bau.edu.bd>,
- <rmitstudent.connect@edu.au>,
- <sarah.palmer@rmit.edu.au>,
- <rmit.connect@edu.au>,
- <enganowar06@gmail.com>,
- <wazed@textile.iitd.ac.in>,
- <toj331@hotmail.com>,
- <Satyaranjan.Bairagi@glasgow.ac.uk>,
- <lijing.wang@rmit.edu.au>,
- <robert.shanks@rmit.edu.au>,
- <safercommunity@rmit.edu.au>,
- <s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au>,
- <scott.mayson@rmit.edu.au>,
- <sean.ryan@rmit.edu.au>,
- <shadi.houshyar@rmit.edu.au>,
- <steve.michielsen@rmit.edu.au>,
- <xin.wang@rmit.edu.au>,
- <rts-dscresearchservicecentre@rmit.edu.au>,
- <andrea.eckersley@rmit.edu.au>,
- <mac.fergusson@rmit.edu.au>,
- <shelley.macrae@rmit.edu.au>,
- <academic.registrar@rmit.edu.au>,
- <vc@rmit.edu.au>,

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)³
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁴
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia

International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

- <dvcr@rmit.com.au>,
- <denise.cuthbert@rmit.edu.au>,
- <robyn.healy@rmit.edu.au>,
- <rusu@rmit.edu.au>,
- <alice.payne@rmit.edu.au>,
- <amber.douglas@rmit.edu.au>,
- <sgr.scholarships@rmit.edu.au>,
- <alec.cameron@rmit.edu.au>,
- <alec.cameron@aarnet.edu.au>,
- <david.castle@rmit.edu.au>,
- <calum.drummond@rmit.edu.au>,
- <contact.centre@education.gov.au>,
- <yourcustomer.service@defence.gov.au>,
- <smrkabir@gmail.com>,
- <prof.shossain3@gmail.com>,
- <drdulalbarua@gmail.com>,
- <syed_hasan04@yahoo.com>,
- <hasanfbru51@gmail.com>,
- <safayeth@gmail.com>,
- <samrat.cse@cityuniversity.edu.bd>,
- <humayun.eee@cityuniversity.edu.bd>,
- <monimuluque4@gmail.com>,
- <houdanazmul@gmail.com>,
- <zeba.khanam18@gmail.com>,

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

- <sharmin.nusrath@yahoo.com>,
- <mahmud004825@gmail.com>,
- <muhibiftakhar@gmail.com>,
- <tareque.ms@gmail.com>,
- <shahinkabir77@gmail.com>,
- <dani.andree@rmit.edu.au>,
- <nahid.islam@idp.com>,
- <ashwini@smita-iitd.com>,
- <bhupendra.singh.butola@textile.iitd.ac.in>,
- <sabbih.hossain@gmail.com>,
- <foreign.minister@dfat.gov.au>,
- <jason.clare.mp@aph.gov.au>,
- <fm@mofa.gov.bd>,
- <minister@moedu.gov.bd>,
- <info@nhrc.org.bd>,
- <headquarters@ihrchq.org>,
- <office@ihrchq.org>,
- <geneva@ihrchq.org>,
- <yunus@yunuscentre.org>,
- <vc@butex.edu.bd>

Message Body

Dear Respected Nobel Laureate, Ministers, Professors, Scientists, Researchers, Executive professionals, Human Rights professionals, Lawyers, education professionals, Executive concern of education compliance, supervisors at PhD school, Criminal investigation departments, Police Departments in home and abroad, copy right concerns of Nobel office, Office of Nobel

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology</p> <p>Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁴ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁴ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia</p> <p>International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva</p> <p>Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	--	--

organization, *The Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences, Nobel committee member for Nobel prize in peace and physics,*

I am happy to write this letter as ‘living person’ of RMIT PhD researcher community at RMIT University, Australia.

As I faced life-threatening in my PhD school at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University; I would like to contribute my understanding for future protection of student community and professor community all over the world as part of my PhD contribution and critical life threatening in my PhD journey. All respected professionals are being requested to understand the whole philosophy of PhD ‘case letter’ (including whole attachment), self-understanding, self-struggling under additional output of PhD Degree at PhD school funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship from 2020 to still now.

My understanding about different research area and research proposal for the peace of mankind.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1250–2500-point policy for the impact factor to certify university designation and university promotion from lecturer to professor. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13177.68968>; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1250–2500-point policy for the impact factor to certify university designation and university promotion from lecturer to professor

A follow-up letter to The Hon Jason Clare MP, Education Minister, Australia for the conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in Australian PhD school. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18413.19685>; A follow-up letter to The Hon Jason Clare MP, Education Minister, Australia for the conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in Australian PhD school

Hossain, M. A. (2024b). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is searching a good-looking lady for his marriage, a requirement of RMIT PhD school. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13112.97282>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1082449>

Hossain, M. A. (2024c). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 7050–14100-point policy for the impact factor or ranking of an international standard

University. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25604.13447>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10814275>

Hossain, M. A. (2024d). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the inventor of 10-point policy to elect the democratic leaders all over the world*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19343.76968>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10662617> Page | 184

Hossain, M. A. (2024a). *Australian Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist asked 100000 Australian penalty unit to Hon Mark Dreyfus KC MP, Australian Attorney General/law minister of Australian Government*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14776.72967>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10556279>

A self-understanding of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist about Bangladeshi Nobel laureate Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus and law implementation of Bangladesh Government. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26912.35846>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10461097>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bv). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is expected for full-time/part-time/contractual/casual positions of professional services all over the world*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13240.32001>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10360586>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bu). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is begging to Mr. António Guterres, the Secretary General of United Nations to stop the conflict between Gaza & Israel*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25967.41129>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10318727>

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	--	--

Hossain, M. A. (2023bw). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is seeking legal support to The Hon Anthony Albanese MP, Prime Minister, Australia for the conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in PhD school, RMIT University.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19140.19849>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10355816>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bk). *Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection (CV of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist).* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10824532>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bx). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's invention for the peace in PhD schooling for the peace of mankind for the excellency in higher education, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33291.67366>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10224211>

Hossain, M. A. (2023g). *Anowar Hossain's invention of camouflage physics at PhD School, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29936.23048>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10224214>

Your Honour; Please Pardon Me

Best Regards for your excellency

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist

PhD (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066

School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry

Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)

Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology

University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India

BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022; Australia

Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College, Chittagong

Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh

Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology</p> <p>Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia</p> <p>International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva</p> <p>Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	--	--

Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.

Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)

International Consultant (Textile Production, Fashion & Garments, Technical Textiles, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News), Motivational speaker, literary writer, Trainer of Certificate courses (Textile & Research)

Research Address since 2020

512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

9.23 Evidence of communication with the security department of Australia under the direction of immi account

Application for ‘detention visit VISA’ (researcher category) including legal support and safety, cost of living and fooding, cost of researcher practice or study support or income support, cost of air ticket from Dhaka to Melbourne and Melbourne to Dhaka

- Anowar Hossain

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

To: ahc.newdelhi@dfat.gov.au, and 6 others, Cc: lijing.wang@rmit.edu.au, and 14 others · Sun, Dec 8, 2024 at 5:49 PM

- [<ahc.newdelhi@dfat.gov.au>](mailto:ahc.newdelhi@dfat.gov.au),
- [<ardia.simpson@dfat.gov.au>](mailto:ardia.simpson@dfat.gov.au),
- [<ahc.dhaka@dfat.gov.au>](mailto:ahc.dhaka@dfat.gov.au),
- [<consular.dhaka@dfat.gov.au>](mailto:consular.dhaka@dfat.gov.au),
- [<detention.visits@abf.gov.au>](mailto:detention.visits@abf.gov.au),
- [<dl_mitavisitapplications@serco-ap.com>](mailto:dl_mitavisitapplications@serco-ap.com),
- [<clientservice.newdelhiahc@dfat.gov.au>](mailto:clientservice.newdelhiahc@dfat.gov.au)

Cc:

- [<lijing.wang@rmit.edu.au>](mailto:lijing.wang@rmit.edu.au),
- [<robert.shanks@rmit.edu.au>](mailto:robert.shanks@rmit.edu.au),
- [<robert.shanks.scientific@gmail.com>](mailto:robert.shanks.scientific@gmail.com),
- [<contact.centre@education.gov.au>](mailto:contact.centre@education.gov.au),
- [<vc@rmit.edu.au>](mailto:vc@rmit.edu.au),
- [<brooke.griffin@rmit.edu.au>](mailto:brooke.griffin@rmit.edu.au),
- [<ea.vc@rmit.edu.au>](mailto:ea.vc@rmit.edu.au),
- [<jason.ngam@rmit.edu.au>](mailto:jason.ngam@rmit.edu.au),
- [<nicole.hendrie@rmit.edu.au>](mailto:nicole.hendrie@rmit.edu.au),
- [<consular.canberra@mofa.gov.bd>](mailto:consular.canberra@mofa.gov.bd),
- [<labour.canberra@mofa.gov.bd>](mailto:labour.canberra@mofa.gov.bd),
- [<commerce.canberra@mofa.gov.bd>](mailto:commerce.canberra@mofa.gov.bd),
- [<mission.canberra@mofa.gov.bd>](mailto:mission.canberra@mofa.gov.bd),
- [<vso@dfat.gov.au>](mailto:vso@dfat.gov.au),

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	--	--

- <infoservice@humanrights.gov.au>

Message Body

Dear high commissioner and VISA officer,

I would like to attach a letter for your assessment, consideration, and advice.

Application for ‘detention visit VISA’ (researcher category) including legal support and safety, cost of living and fooding, cost of researcher practice or study support or income support, cost of air ticket from Dhaka to Melbourne and Melbourne to Dhaka; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 8 December 2024

Your Honour; Please Pardon Me

Best Regards for your excellency

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist

PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh)

Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing

Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066

School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry

Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)

Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology

University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India

BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia

Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College, Chittagong

Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh

Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.

Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)

International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary &

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh); MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	---	---

Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg

Research Address since 2020

512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, engranowar06@gmail.com, +8801788396264

Please Visit the Profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Anowar Hossain

To: philip.green@dfat.gov.au · Mon, Dec 9, 2024 at 7:35 AM

Message Body

Dear high commissioner and VISA officer,

I would like to attach a letter for your assessment, consideration, and advice.

Application for ‘detention visit VISA’ (researcher category) including legal support and safety, cost of living and fooding, cost of researcher practice or study support or income support, cost of air ticket from Dhaka to Melbourne and Melbourne to Dhaka; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 8 December 2024

9.24 Evidence of communication with the education department of Australia

RE: Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nob ETKN:033000003682

- Education - Contact Centre
- contact.centre@education.gov.au

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia
Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

To: me · Thu, Nov 7, 2024 at 10:43 AM

Engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Message Body

Good afternoon,

Page | 192

Thank you for contacting the Department of Education.

This enquiry falls outside the scope of the Department, as such we are unable to assist.

Please let us know if you require any further assistance or you may contact us on 1300 363 079 to discuss further

Regards,

Josh

Departmental Contact Centre

Australian Government Department of Education

Phone: 1300 363 079 | Email: contact.centre@education.gov.au

[Department of Education](http://www.education.gov.au)

Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is requesting to Mr. António Guterres, Secretary-General of United Nations for a legal stipend or legal award to proceed with le ETKN:025000036800

- Education - Contact Centre

contact.centre@education.gov.au

To: me · Sun, Jan 19 at 3:41 PM

Engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Message Body

Hi,

Thank you for contacting the Departmental Contact Centre team.

We endeavour to respond to your email as soon as possible.

Please note, information can also be obtained on the Department's website.

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology</p> <p>Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia</p> <p>International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva</p> <p>Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	--	--

For any future correspondence about this enquiry, please quote case reference number [CC1641189].

Departmental Contact Centre

Australian Government Department of Education

Phone: 1300 363 079 | Email: contact.centre@education.gov.au

www.education.gov.au

9.25 A follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia

- Anowar Hossain

To: Lijing, and 154 others · Sun, Sep 28 at 11:14 AM

To:

- Lijing Wang, <lijing.wang@rmit.edu.au>
- Robert Shanks, <robert.shanks.scientific@gmail.com>
- Robert Shanks, <robert.shanks@rmit.edu.au>
- <vso@dfat.gov.au>
- <fa@mofa.gov.bd>
- <apsfao@mofa.gov.bd>
- <dirfao@mofa.gov.bd>
- <pro@mofa.gov.bd>
- <fs@mofa.gov.bd>
- <dirfso@mofa.gov.bd>
- <ssa@mofa.gov.bd>
- <info@barcouncil.gov.bd>
- <attorneygeneral@attorneygeneral.gov.bd>
- <ps_ag@attorneygeneral.gov.bd>
- Adv.ajb1@gmail.com, <adv.ajb1@gmail.com>
- <ps_addl_ag1@attorneygeneral.gov.bd>
- addl_ag2@attorneygeneral.gov.bd, <addl_ag2@attorneygeneral.gov.bd>
- <ps_addl_ag2@attorneygeneral.gov.bd>
- addl_ag3@attorneygeneral.gov.bd, <addl_ag3@attorneygeneral.gov.bd>
- <ps_addl_ag3@attorneygeneral.gov.bd>
- <cdlbd21@gmail.com>
- <customer@bl.uk>
- <repository@rmit.edu.au>
- Registry@hcourt.gov.au, <registry@hcourt.gov.au>
- <fakhrul@ugc.gov.bd>

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

- <secretary@ugc.gov.bd> ,
- <syrawarn@gmail.com> ,
- <nazmul@ugc.gov.bd> ,
- <director_research@ugc.gov.bd> ,
- <ferdousugc@gmail.com> ,
- <chairman@ugc.gov.bd> ,
- <mustafiz@ugc.gov.bd> ,
- <mustafizugc@gmail.com> ,
- <pschairman@ugc.gov.bd> ,
- <rajiv.padhye@rmit.edu.au> ,
- <khossain@citechco.net> ,
- <vc@cityuniversity.ac.bd> ,
- <registrar@cityuniversity.ac.bd> ,
- <secretary@bangabhaban.gov.bd> ,
- <press.secy@bangabhaban.gov.bd> ,
- <ps_president@bangabhaban.gov.bd> ,
- <akmmonirul31@gmail.com> ,
- <majumderali1950@gmail.com> ,
- <musfiquldu33@gmail.com> ,
- <psecy@cao.gov.bd> ,
- <secretary@cao.gov.bd> ,
- <seafath.mahmud@cao.gov.bd> ,
- <lutfey.siddiqi@cao.gov.bd> ,
- <vc@rmit.edu.au> ,
- <brooke.griffin@rmit.edu.au> ,
- <ea.vc@rmit.edu.au> ,
- <jason.ngam@rmit.edu.au> ,
- <nicole.hendrie@rmit.edu.au> ,
- <alec.cameron@rmit.edu.au> ,
- <alec.cameron@aarnet.edu.au> ,
- <s.islam05@gmail.com> ,
- <saiful.bste@cityuniversity.ac.bd> ,
- <ijtaksamanta@gmail.com> ,
- <ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com> ,
- <ijtskg40@gmail.com> ,
- <sadhan53@yahoo.co.in> ,
- <d.sun@hw.ac.uk> ,
- <lola.akinojelabi@rmit.edu.au> ,
- <andrea.eckersley@rmit.edu.au> ,
- <scott.mayson@rmit.edu.au> ,
- <xin.wang@rmit.edu.au> ,
- <academic.registrar@rmit.edu.au> ,
- Grants@vla.vic.gov.au, <grants@vla.vic.gov.au> ,
- <alice.payne@rmit.edu.au> ,

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)³
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁴
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia

International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder, Defence & Law Researchist (Dr.), RMIT, Australia
Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.348831>

- <robyn.healy@rmit.edu.au> ,
- <calum.drummond@rmit.edu.au> ,
- <karien.dekker@rmit.edu.au> ,
- <ray.kirby@rmit.edu.au> ,
- <sean.ryan@rmit.edu.au> ,
- <shelley.marshall@rmit.edu.au> ,
- Fs256@cam.ac.uk, <fs256@cam.ac.uk> ,
- <ahc.dhaka@dfat.gov.au> ,
- <consular.dhaka@dfat.gov.au> ,
- <consular.canberra@mofa.gov.bd> ,
- <labour.canberra@mofa.gov.bd> ,
- <commerce.canberra@mofa.gov.bd> ,
- <mission.canberra@mofa.gov.bd> ,
- <aswelfare@mofa.gov.bd> ,
- <dgcnw@mofa.gov.bd> ,
- <dirwelfare@mofa.gov.bd> ,
- <asconsular2@mofa.gov.bd> ,
- <scba.bd@gmail.com> ,
- <registrar@smuct.ac.bd> ,
- <registrar@du.ac.bd> ,
- <head@dce.butex.edu.bd> ,
- <butexdce@gmail.com> ,
- <abserju@yahoo.com> ,
- <ehossainsau@gmail.com> ,
- <kamrul_regbuet@yahoo.com> ,
- <rakib_ao@regtr.buet.ac.bd> ,
- <saikatbarua@dce.buet.ac.bd> ,
- <registrar@admin.iitd.ac.in> ,
- <brmehta@physics.iitd.ernet.in> ,
- <brmehta_p@hotmail.com> ,
- <registrarju@gmail.com> ,
- <drsairfur@diu.edu.bd> ,
- <fukudaiko@yahoo.com> ,
- <ftm@nhrc.org.bd> ,
- <chairman@nhrc.org.bd> ,
- <secretary@nhrc.org.bd> ,
- <liptonbjs@gmail.com> ,
- <provc@buft.edu.bd> ,
- <bshamimsc@gmail.com> ,
- <ittefaqdigital@gmail.com> ,
- <ittefaq.adsection@gmail.com> ,
- <letters@theaustralian.com.au> ,
- <victoria@theaustralian.com.au> ,
- <wa@theaustralian.com.au> ,
- <act@theaustralian.com.au> ,

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

- <contact@austbar.asn.au>
- <media@austbar.asn.au>
- Singh.vikas@gmail.com,<singh.vikas@gmail.com>
- <info@barindia.in>
- <barindia1959@gmail.com>
- <service@americanbar.org>
- ContactUs@BarCouncil.org.uk,<contactus@barcouncil.org.uk>
- <press@barcouncil.org.uk>
- <info.esiaprobangkok@amnesty.org>
- <contactus@amnesty.org>
- <secretary@lawjusticediv.gov.bd>
- <adviser@minlaw.gov.bd>
- <zillurlaw@gmail.com>
- <shamimsrm@yahoo.com>
- <sydul1980@gmail.com>
- <additional_secretary@lawjusticediv.gov.bd>
- <head_te@duet.ac.bd>
- <reg_duet@duet.ac.bd>
- <registrar@mbstu.ac.bd>
- <drjalil@te.kuet.ac.bd>
- <registrar@kuet.ac.bd>
- <vc@kuet.ac.bd>
- <ps2vc@kuet.ac.bd>
- <bcmccrm@hotmail.com>
- <arun.guha@seu.edu.bd>
- <chairman@tex.green.edu.bd>
- Freya.Baetens@law.ox.ac.uk,<freya.baetens@law.ox.ac.uk>
- <lawfac@law.ox.ac.uk>
- <contact.centre@education.gov.au>
- <international@judiciary.uk>
- Civil.Feedback@usdoj.gov,<civil.feedback@usdoj.gov>
- OIJA@usdoj.gov,<oija@usdoj.gov>
- <rg@supremecourt.gov.bd>
- <contact@dhakatribune.com>
- <igmartin@deakin.edu.au>
- <arahman@duet.ac.bd>
- <vc@pilani.bits-pilani.ac.in>
- <headquarters@ihrchq.org>
- <office@ihrchq.org>
- <geneva@ihrchq.org>
- ohchr-infoDesk@un.org,<ohchr-infodesk@un.org>

Message Body

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*}
Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process,
color engg), applied law & criminology
Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)³
Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁴
Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg
& Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam);
Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Trained from India, Australia, Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and
Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Dear Sir/Madam,

A follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Page | 197

<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18369.83044>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17216692>

This e-mail has also attachment of pdf file of the letter of communication.

Your Honour; Please Pardon Me

Best Regards for your excellency

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh)

Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing

Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066

School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry

Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)

Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology

University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia

Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College, Chittagong

Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh

Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.

Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)

International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg

Research Address since 2020

512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Contact: enqr.anowar@yahoo.com, engranowar06@gmail.com, +8801788396264

Please Visit the Profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology</p> <p>Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia</p> <p>International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva</p> <p>Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	--	--

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

9.25.1 A follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT

- Anowar Hossain

To: reception@humanrights.gov.au, and 2 others · Sun, Sep 28 at 11:48 AM

To:

<reception@humanrights.gov.au>, <communications@humanrights.gov.au>, <infoservice@humanrights.gov.au>

Message Body

Mr. Hugh de Kretser, President

Human Rights Commission, The Commonwealth of Australia

reception@humanrights.gov.au

communications@humanrights.gov.au

infoservice@humanrights.gov.au

Dear Sir,

A follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18369.83044>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17216692>

Symptom of zero responsibility of Mr. Hugh de Kretser, President, Human Rights Commission, Australia; legal notice to the president of human rights commission from the office of Nobel Nominee Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.); RMIT University, Australia (M. A. Hossain, 2023f; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024b)

Page | 200

A full information and evidence of life-threatening conspiracy and history of long-term harassment in Australian PhD school was sent to the office of human rights commission of Australia, prime minister of Australia, governor general of Australia, law minister of Australia, attorney general of Australia, high commissioner of Bangladesh in Australia, high commissioner of Australia in Bangladesh, RMIT university of Australia, local police station of Australia, local ministerial cabinet of Melbourne/Victoria, St. Vincent hospital in Melbourne, relevant offices and professional communities. Mr. Hugh de Kretser, President, Human Rights Commission, Australia should pay the penalty of 1,00,000 Australian penalty units if he is neglecting the international service, if he is neglecting and delaying the public service, if the office of human rights commission is neglecting and delaying the public service (M. A. Hossain, 2023bw) (M. A. Hossain, 2023f; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024b, 2024k). What is the purpose of human rights commission? What should be the purpose of human rights commission? Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should have a legal right and legal authorization to access the ready platform of public service. Nobody should have right to cease the rights of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Nobody should cease the money/salary of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, he also needs living and food allowance. RMIT should not cease single dollar from the pocket of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Nobody should plan to kill the researcher. Nobody should harass the merit growth of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Every Australian PhD scholar should have right to access the office of president of human rights commission. Every Australian PhD scholar should have right to access the legal aid fund/welfare fund/research fund of president. This is not begging to the president, this is the legal rights of the PhD scholar, this is also the beneficiary rights of the PhD scholar (Hossain, 2025d). How many complaint letters did president get/receive in his public service like the request letter from Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain; president of human rights commission should prove to the relevant court to

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.).
Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*}
Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process,
color engg), applied law & criminology
Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸
Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁸
Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg
& Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam);
Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
Vyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and
Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

signify his busy schedule/manpower shortage/secretary shortage in his office of public service? If he is doing service offence, he should pay the 'compensation award' to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) (M. A. Hossain, 2023f). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) should have legal rights to use the administrative desk of president of human rights commission if president can claim his self-designation of president of human rights commission of Australia if president can claim his self-salary of human rights commission of Australia. This is the administrative supremacy of democracy and advocacy of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.).

This email has a pdf file of full letter.

Your Honour; Please Pardon Me

Best Regards for your excellency

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh)

Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing

Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066

School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry

Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)

Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology

University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia

Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College, Chittagong

Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh

Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.

Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)

International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg

Research Address since 2020

512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Contact: enqr.anowar@yahoo.com, engranowar06@gmail.com, +8801788396264

Please Visit the Profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology</p> <p>Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia</p> <p>International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India, Australia, Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva</p> <p>Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	--	--

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

9.25.2 Contact The PM, UK

To: me · Sun, Sep 28 at 12:24 PM
 Message Body

Thank you for your message.

Please note that the Prime Minister's Office is a part of the Cabinet Office, a Government Department.

Please confirm the message by clicking on the following link: <https://contact.no10.gov.uk/VerifyMessage.aspx?id=42c10ddb-6ca6-45bd-8bf3-a9c94852ed9c>

By confirming this email, you give permission for this office to forward your email to the appropriate Government Department.

Please note – this is an automated email. Please do not reply to this email address as your message will not be read.

Contact Number 10

Thank you. The Prime Minister's Office is currently receiving an exceptionally high volume of emails. If your message concerned an issue relating to the responsibilities of another Government Department or public authority then you should resend it to them. The Prime Minister's Office is, at this time, only able to consider matters directly relating to the Prime Minister and will not reply to emails that could have been dealt with elsewhere or which are of a general nature.

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

9.25.3 A follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT

- Anowar Hossain

Page | 204

To: secy.president@rb.nic.in, and 2 others · Sun, Sep 28 at 1:31 PM

To:

- <secy.president@rb.nic.in>,
- <jha.am@nic.in>,
- <usha.sudhindra@rb.nic.in>

Message Body

Ms. Droupadi Murmu, President of India; Office of President, India

secy.president@rb.nic.in; jha.am@nic.in;
usha.sudhindra@rb.nic.in

Dear Ms. Droupadi Murmu,

A follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18369.83044>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17216692>

This e-mail has also attachment of pdf file of the letter.

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.).
Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD²
Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process,
color engg), applied law & criminology
Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵
Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶
Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg
& Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam);
Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and
Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Your Honour; Please Pardon Me

Best Regards for your excellency

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist

PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh)

Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing

Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066

School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry

Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)

Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology

University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India

BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia

Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College, Chittagong

Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.

Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)

International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg

Research Address since 2020

512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, engranowar06@gmail.com, +8801788396264

Please Visit the Profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

9.25.4 Communication with governor general, Australia

Thank you for contacting the Office of the Official Secretary to the Governor-General. Form letters or emails generated as part of a broader campaign may not be responded to. Individual items of correspondence of this type will not be brought to the attention of the Governor-General and senders should not expect a reply. Please read our [Privacy Statement](#).

Media enquiries should be sent directly to media@gg.gov.au (your previous request has not been forwarded).

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	---	--

We will endeavour to respond to your enquiry as quickly as possible, however an immediate response may not be possible.

9.25.5 Grants; grants@vla.vic.gov.au

To: me · Sun, Sep 28 at 11:27 AM

Message Body

Thank you for contacting the Grants and Quality Assurance team at Victoria Legal Aid.

Due to the significant volume of applications for legal assistance that we receive, we have established priorities for assessing these applications.

Our current priorities include the following matters:

- court ordered funding
- criminal trials
- civil law applications with hearing dates within the next 5 days
- family law matters with either FDRS conference or hearing dates within the next 10 days (excludes mentions, directions hearings and other procedural hearings)
- High Court matters
- matters in the Court of Appeal
- matters for filing materials for Commonwealth family law final hearings
- matters where the court date has passed
- public interest and strategic litigation (PISL) matters
- requests for Senior Counsel
- requests for two Counsel
- requests for large amounts of additional preparation
- requests for expert reports in Major Criminal Cases matters with imminent court and/or expert assessment dates

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

If your enquiry relates to a family law matter, the estimated timeframe for assessment is approximately **9 business days**.

If your enquiry relates to a criminal law matter, the estimated timeframe for assessment is approximately **14 business days**.

Page | 208

If your enquiry relates to a civil matter, the estimated timeframe for assessment is approximately **25 business days**.

If your matter meets one of our priorities, it will be allocated to a grants officer for assessment as soon as possible and may be assessed within a shorter timeframe.

An outcome will be provided in your ATLAS inbox once the assessment occurs.

Help us to respond to your enquiries more quickly

We also ask that you please use the following format when sending emails so we can respond as quickly as possible:

Subject Field: [next court date] [type of hearing e.g. mention/hearing/trial/appeal] [file reference] [client's full name] [type of matter e.g. summary/indictable/family/FDRS/ICL/child protection/civil] Body of text (brief dot points):
What is your enquiry? Is it urgent – if so, why?

Legal Help

If you do not have a grant of legal aid and want information on a legal problem, please contact Victoria Legal Aid's (VLA) Legal Help phoneline for free information about the law and how VLA can help you. Legal Help can be contacted on 1300 792 387, Monday to Friday, 8am to 6pm (excluding public holidays). Legal Help also offers a free online chat service for general information and referrals, which operates Monday to Friday, 9am to 5pm, subject to availability. You can access Legal Help Chat from the VLA website: www.legalaid.vic.gov.au

If you are a panel practitioner

If you are a practitioner with a query about how to use ATLAS, or how our Guidelines or Fees apply to your client's legal matter, our team of Practitioner Support Officers can provide a range of training and support for all non-assessment grants queries. To discuss your ATLAS, Guidelines or Fees queries, please contact grantstraining@vla.vic.gov.au.

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	---	---

9.25.6 JO International, international@judiciary.uk

To: me · Sun, Sep 28 at 11:27 AM

Message Body

Thank you for your email.

Please be advised that we aim to respond within 3-5 working days (and this mailbox is not monitored during the weekend or Bank Holidays).

9.25.7 Minister Correspondence Reference: MC25-039379

To: me · Sun, Sep 28 at 12:05 PM

Message Body

Thank you for contacting the Minister.

The Minister appreciates hearing your views. Your correspondence will be noted by the Department of Home Affairs and, in some cases, the Department may be asked to respond on the Minister's behalf.

Your request was successfully submitted on 28/09/2025 at 04:04:58 and your reference number is MC25-039379.

If you have concerns about criminal activity in your local community, contact your local police on 131 444 or Crime Stoppers on 1800 333 000.

If you wish to report suspicious activity, you can contact the National Security Hotline in the following ways:

Call: 1800 1234 00

From outside Australia: (+61) 1300 1234 01

Email: hotline@nationalecurity.gov.au

SMS: 0429 771 822

9.25.8 Opened - [CC1687864] - [A follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMI ETKN:025000059628

Education - Contact Centre

To: me · Sun, Sep 28 at 11:20 AM

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Message Body

Hi,

Thank you for contacting the Departmental Contact Centre team.

We endeavour to respond to your email as soon as possible.

Please note, information can also be obtained on the Department's website.

For any future correspondence about this enquiry, please quote case reference number [CC1687864].

Departmental Contact Centre

Australian Government Department of Education

Phone: 1300 363 079 | Email: contact.centre@education.gov.au

www.education.gov.au

9.25.9 Your contact us form has been submitted

ag.noreply@govcms.gov.au

To: me · Sun, Sep 28 at 11:32 AM

Message Body

Thank you for contacting the Attorney-General Department.

9.25.10 Failure Notice

MAILER-DAEMON@yahoo.com

To: me · Sun, Sep 28 at 11:27 AM

Message Body

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<ps_addl_ag2@attorneygeneral.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (ps_addl_ag2@attorneygeneral.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

9.25.11 Failure Notice

To: me · Sun, Sep 28 at 11:27 AM

Message Body

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	--	---

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<ps_addl_ag3@attorneygeneral.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients
 (ps_addl_ag3@attorneygeneral.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

9.25.12 Failure Notice

To: me · Sun, Sep 28 at 11:27 AM

Message Body

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<seafath.mahmud@cao.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (seafath.mahmud@cao.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

9.25.13 Failure Notice

To: me · Sun, Sep 28 at 11:27 AM

Message Body

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<ps_addl_ag1@attorneygeneral.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (ps_addl_ag1@attorneygeneral.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

9.25.14 Failure Notice

To: me · Sun, Sep 28 at 11:27 AM

Message Body

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<ftm@nhrc.org.bd>:

554: rejecting banned content

9.25.15 Failure Notice

To: me · Sun, Sep 28 at 11:27 AM

Message Body

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<secretary@cao.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (secretary@cao.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

----- Forwarded message -----

Page | 212

9.25.16 Failure Notice

To: me · Sun, Sep 28 at 11:27 AM

Message Body

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<press.secy@bangabhaban.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (press.secy@bangabhaban.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

9.25.17 Failure Notice

To: me · Sun, Sep 28 at 11:27 AM

Message Body

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<ps_president@bangabhaban.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (ps_president@bangabhaban.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

9.25.18 Failure Notice

To: me · Sun, Sep 28 at 11:17 AM

Message Body

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<adviser@minlaw.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (adviser@minlaw.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

9.25.19 Failure Notice

To: me · Sun, Sep 28 at 11:17 AM

Message Body

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	---	---

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<secretary@bangabhaban.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (secretary@bangabhaban.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

9.25.20 Failure Notice

To: me · Sun, Sep 28 at 11:17 AM

Message Body

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<pschairman@ugc.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (pschairman@ugc.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

9.25.21 Failure Notice

To: me · Sun, Sep 28 at 11:17 AM

Message Body

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<lutfey.siddiqi@cao.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (lutfey.siddiqi@cao.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

9.25.22 Failure Notice

To: me · Sun, Sep 28 at 11:17 AM

Message Body

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<psecy@cao.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (psecy@cao.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

9.25.23 Failure Notice

To: me · Sun, Sep 28 at 11:17 AM

Message Body

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

<attorneygeneral@attorneygeneral.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (attorneygeneral@attorneygeneral.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

9.25.24 Failure Notice

To: me · Sun, Sep 28 at 11:17 AM

Message Body

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<addl_ag3@attorneygeneral.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (addl_ag3@attorneygeneral.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

9.25.25 Failure Notice

To: me · Sun, Sep 28 at 11:17 AM

Message Body

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<secretary@ugc.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (secretary@ugc.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

9.25.26 Failure Notice

To: me · Sun, Sep 28 at 11:17 AM

Message Body

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<fakhrul@ugc.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (fakhrul@ugc.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

9.25.27 Failure Notice

To: me · Sun, Sep 28 at 11:17 AM

Message Body

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India, Australia, Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	--	---

<addl_ag2@attorneygeneral.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (addl_ag2@attorneygeneral.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

9.25.28 Failure Notice

To: me · Sun, Sep 28 at 11:17 AM

Message Body

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<chairman@ugc.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (chairman@ugc.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

9.25.29 Failure Notice

To: me · Sun, Sep 28 at 11:17 AM

Message Body

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<nazmul@ugc.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (nazmul@ugc.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

9.25.30 A follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Au...

Consular Dhaka

To: me · Sun, Sep 28 at 11:17 AM

Message Body

Thank you for contacting the Australian High Commission in Dhaka, Bangladesh. **We have received your email.**

Australian Passport, Consular and Notarial Services appointments

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

If you are an Australian citizen and wish to make an appointment for an Australian passport, Consular or Notarial matter, please do so by going to our website: <https://bangladesh.embassy.gov.au/daca/consular.html>

you may wish to email to the Consular Dhaka mailbox consular.dhaka@dfat.gov.au

Visa Services

If you are a Bangladeshi citizen and your query relates to Australian visas or citizenship, you may wish to email to the Immigration Dhaka mailbox immigration.dhaka@dfat.gov.au

If you are not a citizen of Bangladesh and have a query regarding your visa application, please contact the relevant processing office outside Australia responsible for your country of citizenship: [Offices outside Australia](#)

For child and orphan relative visa enquiries: [Child and Orphan Relative Visa Processing Centre Form](#)

Further visa information can be found at www.homeaffairs.gov.au

Helplines:

For Visa-related queries, you can also contact the Global Service Centre [Telephone](#) from Monday to Friday 9 am to 5 pm your local time. GSC is closed on Australian National Public Holidays.

In Australia

Phone: 131 881

Outside Australia

Phone: +61 2 6196 0196

9.25.31 Failure Notice

To: me · Sun, Sep 28 at 11:17 AM

Message Body

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<director_research@ugc.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (director_research@ugc.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCRC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	---	---

9.25.32 Failure Notice

To: me · Sun, Sep 28 at 11:17 AM

Message Body

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address

<ps_ag@attorneygeneral.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (ps_ag@attorneygeneral.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

9.25.33 Failure Notice

To: me · Sun, Sep 28 at 11:17 AM

Message Body

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<mustafiz@ugc.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (mustafiz@ugc.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

9.25.34 Failure Notice

To: me · Sun, Sep 28 at 11:17 AM

Message Body

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<secretary@lawjusticediv.gov.bd>:

554: rejecting banned content

9.25.35 Failure Notice

To: me · Sun, Sep 28 at 11:17 AM

Message Body

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<secretary@nhrc.org.bd>:

554: rejecting banned content

9.25.36 Failure Notice

To: me · Sun, Sep 28 at 11:17 AM

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Message Body

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<rg@supremecourt.gov.bd>:

554: rejecting banned content

9.25.37 Failure Notice

To: me · Sun, Sep 28 at 11:16 AM

Message Body

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<chairman@nhrc.org.bd>:

554: rejecting banned content

9.25.38 Failure Notice

To: me · Sun, Sep 28 at 11:16 AM

Message Body

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<additional_secretary@lawjusticediv.gov.bd>:

554: rejecting banned content

9.25.39 Failure Notice

To: me · Sun, Sep 28 at 11:16 AM

Message Body

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<syrawarn@gmail.com>:

550: 5.1.1 The email account that you tried to reach does not exist. Please try

5.1.1 double-checking the recipient's email address for typos or

5.1.1 unnecessary spaces. For more information, go to

5.1.1 <https://support.google.com/mail/?p=NoSuchUser> d75a77b69052e-4db121b76cesi43333791cf.1002 - gsmtip

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.). Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁹ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	--	--

10 Quoted Australian criminal act for judicial recommendation (M. A. Hossain, 2023f)

10.1 Australian criminal code 2002; A2002-51

21 22 Negligence: A person is negligent in relation to a physical element of an offence if the person's conduct merits criminal punishment for the offence because it involves— (a) such a great falling short of the standard of care that a reasonable person would exercise in the circumstances; and (b) such a high risk that the physical element exists or will exist.

10.2 Australian trade practices act 1974 (Cth)

75AZI Certain misleading conduct in relation to services

(1) A corporation must not, in trade or commerce, engage in conduct that is liable to mislead the public about the nature, the characteristics, the suitability for their purpose, or the quantity, of any services.

Penalty: 10,000 penalty units.

10.3 Australian Human Rights Commission Act 1986

11. Functions of Commission

(h) to undertake research and educational programs and other programs, on behalf of the Commonwealth, for the purpose of promoting human rights, and to co-ordinate any such programs undertaken by any other persons or authorities on behalf of the Commonwealth; and

(j) on its own initiative or when requested by the Minister, to report to the Minister as to the laws that should be made by the Parliament, or action that should be taken by the Commonwealth, on matters relating to human rights

10.4 Panel law of Criminal code act of Australia, 1995

11.5 Conspiracy

(1) A person who conspires with another person to commit an offence punishable by imprisonment for more than 12 months, or by a fine of 200 penalty units or more, commits the offence of conspiracy to commit that offence and is punishable as if the offence to which the conspiracy relates had been committed.

Note: Penalty units are defined in section 4AA of the Crimes Act 1914.

Fraudulent conduct

if the threatened offence is the offence under section 71.6 or 71.11 (causing harm to, or damaging the property etc. of, a UN or associated person)—imprisonment for 5 years; or

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

92.2 Offence of intentional foreign interference

Interference generally

(1) A person commits an offence if:

- (a) the person engages in conduct; and
- (b) any of the following circumstances exists:

(i) the person engages in the conduct on behalf of, or in collaboration with, a foreign principal or a person acting on behalf of a foreign principal;

(ii) the conduct is directed, funded or supervised by a foreign principal or a person acting on behalf of a foreign principal; and

Interference involving targeted person

Penalty: Imprisonment for 20 years.

Part 5.3—Terrorism

creates a serious risk to the health or safety of the public or a section of the public;

101.5 Collecting or making documents likely to facilitate terrorist acts

1) A person commits an offence if:

(a) the person collects or makes a document; and

(b) the document is connected with preparation for, the engagement of a person in, or assistance in a terrorist act; and

(c) the person mentioned in paragraph (a) knows of the connection described in paragraph (b).

Penalty: Imprisonment for 15 years.

115.3 Intentionally causing serious harm to an Australian citizen or a resident of Australia

(1) A person commits an offence if:

- (a) the person engages in conduct outside Australia; and

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCRC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	--	--

- (b) the conduct causes serious harm to another person; and
- (c) the other person is an Australian citizen or a resident of Australia; and
- (d) the first-mentioned person intends to cause serious harm to the Australian citizen or resident of Australia or any other person by the conduct.

Penalty: Imprisonment for 20 years.

115.4 Recklessly causing serious harm to an Australian citizen or a resident of Australia

- (1) A person commits an offence if:
 - (a) the person engages in conduct outside Australia; and
 - (b) the conduct causes serious harm to another person; and
 - (c) the other person is an Australian citizen or a resident of Australia; and
 - (d) the first-mentioned person is reckless as to causing serious harm to the Australian citizen or resident of Australia or any other person by the conduct.

Penalty: Imprisonment for 15 years.

119.4 Preparations for incursions into foreign countries for purpose of engaging in hostile activities

Preparatory acts

- (1) A person commits an offence if:
 - (a) the person engages in conduct (whether within or outside Australia); and
 - (b) the conduct is preparatory to the commission of an offence against section 119.1 (whether by that or any other person); and
 - (c) when the person engages in the conduct, the person:
 - (i) is an Australian citizen; or
 - (ii) is a resident of Australia; or
 - (iii) is a holder under the *Migration Act 1958* of a visa; or
 - (iv) has voluntarily put himself or herself under the protection of Australia; or

(v) is a body corporate incorporated by or under a law of the Commonwealth or of a State or Territory.

Penalty: Imprisonment for life.

(5) A person commits an offence if:

Page | 222

(a) the person engages in any of the following conduct (whether within or outside Australia):

(i) giving money or goods to, or performing services for, any other person, body or association;

(ii) receiving or soliciting money or goods, or the performance of services; and

(b) the person engages in the conduct with the intention of supporting or promoting the commission of an offence against section 119.1; and

(c) when the person engages in the conduct, the person:

(i) is an Australian citizen; or

(ii) is a resident of Australia; or

(iii) is a holder under the *Migration Act 1958* of a visa; or

(iv) has voluntarily put himself or herself under the protection of Australia; or

(v) is a body corporate incorporated by or under a law of the Commonwealth or of a State or Territory.

Penalty: Imprisonment for life.

132.2 Robbery

(1) A person commits an offence if the person commits theft and:

(a) immediately before committing theft, the person:

(i) uses force on another person; or

(ii) threatens to use force then and there on another person;

with intent to commit theft or to escape from the scene; or

(b) at the time of committing theft, or immediately after committing theft, the person:

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁸ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	---	---

- (i) uses force on another person; or
 - (ii) threatens to use force then and there on another person;
- with intent to commit theft or to escape from the scene.

Penalty: Imprisonment for 15 years.

- (3) A Commonwealth public official commits an offence if:
 - (a) the official dishonestly:
 - (i) asks for a benefit for himself, herself or another person;

Penalty for individual

(5) An offence against subsection (1) or (3) committed by an individual is punishable on conviction by imprisonment for not more than 10 years, a fine not more than 10,000 penalty units, or both.

Penalty for body corporate

(6) An offence against subsection (1) or (3) committed by a body corporate is punishable on conviction by a fine not more than the greatest of the following:

- (a) 100,000 penalty units

10.5 Panel law of Australian trade practices act 1974 (Cth)

4KA Personal injury

In this Act (except in section 68B):

personal injury includes:

- (a) pre-natal injury; or
- (b) impairment of a person's physical or mental condition; or
- (c) disease;

but does not include an impairment of a person's mental condition unless the impairment consists of a recognised psychiatric illness.

Misleading or deceptive conduct

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

(1) A corporation shall not, in trade or commerce, engage in conduct that is misleading or deceptive or is likely to mislead or deceive.

(2) Nothing in the succeeding provisions of this Division shall be taken as limiting by implication the generality of subsection (1).

Note: For rules relating to representations as to the country of origin of goods, see Division 1AA (sections 65AA to 65AN).

Harassment and coercion

A corporation shall not use physical force or undue harassment or coercion in connection with the supply or possible supply of goods or services to a consumer or the payment for goods or services by a consumer.

Misleading conduct in relation to employment

(1) A corporation must not, in relation to employment that is to be, or may be, offered by the corporation or by another person, engage in conduct that is liable to mislead persons seeking the employment about the availability, nature, terms or conditions of, or any other matter relating to, the employment.

Penalty: 10,000 penalty units.

Note 1: The penalty specified above is the maximum penalty that may be imposed on a corporation: subsection 4B(3) of the *Crimes Act 1914* does not apply.

Note 2: For the application of this offence to a person other than a corporation (and the corresponding penalty), see section 6.

(2) Subsection (1) is an offence of strict liability.

Note 1: Chapter 2 of the *Criminal Code* sets out the general principles of criminal responsibility.

Note 2: For *strict liability*, see section 6.1 of the *Criminal Code*.

75AZI Certain misleading conduct in relation to services

(1) A corporation must not, in trade or commerce, engage in conduct that is liable to mislead the public about the nature, the characteristics, the suitability for their purpose, or the quantity, of any services.

Penalty: 10,000 penalty units.

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology</p> <p>Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁸ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia</p> <p>International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	--	--

Note 1: The penalty specified above is the maximum penalty that may be imposed on a corporation: subsection 4B(3) of the *Crimes Act 1914* does not apply.

Note 2: For the application of this offence to a person other than a corporation (and the corresponding penalty), see section 6.

(2) Subsection (1) is an offence of strict liability.

Note 1: Chapter 2 of the *Criminal Code* sets out the general principles of criminal responsibility.

Note 2: For **strict liability**, see section 6.1 of the *Criminal Code*.

75AZN Harassment and coercion

(1) If:

(a) a corporation uses physical force or undue harassment or coercion; and

(b) the corporation uses such force, harassment or coercion in connection with the supply or possible supply of goods or services to a consumer, or the payment for goods or services by a consumer;

the corporation is guilty of an offence punishable on conviction by a fine not exceeding 10,000 penalty units.

Note 1: The penalty specified in subsection (1) is the maximum penalty that may be imposed on a corporation: subsection 4B(3) of the *Crimes Act 1914* does not apply.

Note 2: For the application of the offence in subsection (1) to a person other than a corporation (and the corresponding penalty), see section 6.

(2) Strict liability applies to paragraph (1)(b).

Note 1: Chapter 2 of the *Criminal Code* sets out the general principles of criminal responsibility.

Note 2: For **strict liability**, see section 6.1 of the *Criminal Code*.

76F Pecuniary penalties under section 76E and offences

(1) The Court must not make an order under section 76E against a person in relation to either of the following matters (a **consumer protection breach**):

(a) a contravention of a provision referred to in paragraph 76E(1)(a);

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

(b) conduct referred to in paragraph 76E(1)(b), (c), (d), (e) or (f) that relates to a contravention of a provision referred to in paragraph 76E(1)(a);

if the person has been convicted of an offence constituted by conduct that is substantially the same as the conduct constituting the consumer protection breach.

(2) Proceedings for an order under section 76E against a person in relation to a consumer protection breach are stayed if:

(a) criminal proceedings are started or have already been started against the person for an offence; and

(b) the offence is constituted by conduct that is substantially the same as the conduct alleged to constitute the consumer protection breach.

The proceedings for the order may be resumed if the person is not convicted of the offence. Otherwise, the proceedings are dismissed.

(3) Criminal proceedings may be started against a person for conduct that is substantially the same as conduct constituting a consumer protection breach regardless of whether an order under section 76E has been made against the person in respect of the breach.

(4) Evidence of information given, or evidence of production of documents, by an individual is not admissible in criminal proceedings against the individual if:

(a) the individual previously gave the evidence or produced the documents in proceedings for an order under section 76E against the individual in relation to a consumer protection breach (whether or not the order was made); and

(b) the conduct alleged to constitute the offence is substantially the same as the conduct that was claimed to constitute the consumer protection breach.

However, this does not apply to a criminal proceeding in respect of the falsity of the evidence given by the individual in the proceedings for the order.

79B Preference must be given to compensation for victims

If the Court considers that:

(a) it is appropriate to order a person (the *defendant*):

(i) to pay a pecuniary penalty under section 76 or 76E; or

(ii) to impose a fine under section 44ZZRF or 44ZZRG or Part VC;

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁹ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCRC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	---	--

in respect of a contravention, or an involvement in a contravention, of this Act;
 and

(b) it is appropriate to order the defendant to pay compensation to a person who has
 suffered loss or damage in respect of the contravention or the involvement; and

(c) the defendant does not have sufficient financial resources to pay both the
 pecuniary penalty or fine and the compensation;

the Court must give preference to making an order for compensation.

82 Actions for damages

(1) Subject to subsection (1AAA), a person who suffers loss or damage by conduct of
 another person that was done in contravention of a provision of Part IV, IVA, IVB or V or
 section 51AC may recover the amount of the loss or damage by action against that other person or
 against any person involved in the contravention.

(1AAA) A person who suffers loss or damage by conduct of another person may not recover
 the amount of the loss or damage by an action under subsection (1) to the extent to which:

- (a) the action would be based on the conduct contravening a provision of Division 1
 of Part V; and
- (b) the loss or damage is, or results from, death or personal injury; and
- (c) the death or personal injury does not result from smoking or other use of tobacco
 products.

(1AAB) Divisions 2 and 7 of Part VIB apply to an action under subsection (1) for loss or
 damage a person suffers by conduct of another person to the extent to which:

- (a) the action is based on the conduct contravening a provision of Division 1 of
 Part V; and
- (b) the loss or damage is, or results from, death or personal injury; and
- (c) the death or personal injury results from smoking or other use of tobacco
 products;

as if the action were a proceeding to which Part VIB applies.

Note 1: Division 2 of Part VIB deals with the limitation periods that apply for claims for damages or compensation for death or personal injury and, to the extent to which that Division is applied to the action by this subsection, it overrides subsection (2) of this section.

Note 2: Division 7 of Part VIB deals with structured settlements for claims for damages or compensation for death or personal injury.

(1AA) Subsection (1) has effect subject to section 87AB.

Note: Section 87AB may limit the amount that the person may recover for a contravention of section 52 (Misleading or deceptive conduct) from the other person or from another person involved in the contravention.

(1B) Despite subsection (1), if:

(a) a person (the *claimant*) makes a claim under subsection (1) in relation to:

- (i) economic loss; or
- (ii) damage to property;

caused by conduct of another person (the *defendant*) that was done in contravention of section 52; and

(b) the claimant suffered the loss or damage:

- (i) as a result partly of the claimant's failure to take reasonable care; and
- (ii) as a result partly of the conduct referred to in paragraph (a); and

(c) the defendant:

- (i) did not intend to cause the loss or damage; and
- (ii) did not fraudulently cause the loss or damage;

the damages that the claimant may recover in relation to the loss or damage are to be reduced to the extent to which the court thinks just and equitable having regard to the claimant's share in the responsibility for the loss or damage.

Note: Part VIA also applies proportionate liability to a claim for damages under this section for a contravention of section 52.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	---	--

(2) An action under subsection (1) may be commenced at any time within 6 years after the day on which the cause of action that relates to the conduct accrued.

Note: Part VIB restricts awards of compensation for death or personal injury, and sets out time limits for commencing actions for damages for death or personal injury.

(3) In this section:
smoking has the same meaning as in the *Tobacco Advertising Prohibition Act 1992*.
tobacco product has the same meaning as in the *Tobacco Advertising Prohibition Act 1992*.

87U Personal injury damages for loss of earning capacity

In determining, in a proceeding to which this Part applies, personal injury damages for:

- (a) past economic loss due to loss of earnings or the deprivation or impairment of earning capacity; or
 - (b) future economic loss due to the deprivation or impairment of earning capacity;
- or
- (c) the loss of expectation of financial support;

a court must disregard the amount by which the plaintiff's gross weekly earnings during any quarter would (but for the personal injury or death in question) have exceeded:

- (d) if, at the time the award was made, the amount of average weekly earnings for the quarter was ascertainable—an amount that is twice the amount of average weekly earnings for the quarter; or
- (e) if:
 - (i) at the time the award was made, the amount of average weekly earnings for the quarter was not ascertainable; or
 - (ii) the award was made during, or before the start of, the quarter;
 - an amount that is twice the amount of average weekly earnings for the quarter that, at the time the award was made, was the most recent quarter for which the amount of average weekly earnings was ascertainable.

10.6 Panel law of Australian educational service for overseas student act 2000 (Cth)

15 Registered providers must not engage in misleading or deceptive conduct

A registered provider must not engage in misleading or deceptive conduct in connection with:

- (a) the recruitment of overseas students or intending overseas students; or
- (b) the provision of courses to overseas students.

Note: If a registered provider breaches this section, the ESOS agency for the provider may take action under Division 1 of Part 6 against the provider.

49 Student placement service

(1) This section applies if the TPS Director determines that:

(a) a registered provider (or former registered provider) has defaulted in relation to an overseas student or intending overseas student and a course at a location; and

(b) either:

(i) the provider has failed to discharge its obligations under section 46D to the student by the end of the provider obligation period; or

(ii) the provider is unlikely to be able to discharge its obligations under section 46D to the student by the end of the provider obligation period.

Suitable alternative courses

(2) If any suitable alternative courses are available, the TPS Director must provide, in writing, the student with one or more options for such alternative courses.

Accepting an alternative course

(3) If a registered provider of an alternative course referred to in subsection (2) offers the student a place in the course, the student may accept the offer.

Note: A call is made on the OSTF to pay the provider of the alternative course: see Division 4.

(4) An acceptance must:

- (a) be in writing; and

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	--	--

(b) be made within the period specified in subsection (5).

(5) For the purposes of subsection (4), the period is:

- (a) the period of 30 days after the end of the provider obligation period; or
- (b) if the TPS Director determines that exceptional circumstances apply:
 - (i) any shorter period determined in writing by the TPS Director; or
 - (ii) any longer period determined in writing by the TPS Director, and agreed to by

the student.

Legislative instrument

(6) The Minister may, by legislative instrument, specify criteria to be applied in considering whether a particular course is a suitable alternative course for the purposes of this Act.

10.7 High court of Australia act 1979 - SECT 17

Administration of the Court

- (1) The High Court shall administer its own affairs subject to, and in accordance with, this Act.
- (2) The Court has power for the purposes of the Court to do all things that are necessary or convenient to be done for or in connection with the administration of its affairs and, without limiting the generality of the foregoing, has power:
 - (a) to enter into contracts;
 - (b) to acquire, hold and dispose of real and personal property;
 - (c) to take on hire, to exchange, and to accept on deposit or loan, library material, and also furnishings, equipment and goods needed for the purposes of the Court;
 - (d) to control and manage any land or building occupied by the Court and any adjacent land or building that is declared by Proclamation to be part of the precincts of the Court;
 - (e) to accept gifts, devises and bequests made to the Court upon trust and act as trustee of moneys or other property vested in the Court upon trust; and
 - (f) to do such other things as it is authorized by this Act to do.

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

(3) Any real property, and any personal property (other than money), held by the Court shall be deemed to be the property of the

Commonwealth.

(4) For the purposes of the Lands Acquisition Act 1989, the Court shall be deemed to be an authority incorporated by a law of

the Commonwealth.

(5) The Court may appoint committees consisting of Justices, or of Justices and other persons, for the purpose of advising the Court

in relation to:

- (a) the exercise of the powers of the Court under this Act; or
- (b) the making of Rules of Court.

10.8 High court of Australia act 1979

- SECT 30

Registry

(1) There shall be a Registry of the High Court, which shall be at the seat of the Court.

(2) The Registry shall be under the control of the Chief Executive and Principal Registrar.

(3) There shall be an office of the Registry at the seat of the Court, at the capital city of each State, at Darwin in the Northern

Territory and at such other places as the Court deems necessary.

(4) The Minister may arrange with the appropriate Minister of a State or of the Northern Territory for an officer or officers of that

State or Territory to perform on behalf of the Court at any office in that State or Territory of the Registry of the Court all or any of the functions referred to in subsection (6).

(5) The Chief Justice may arrange with the Chief Justice of the Federal Court of Australia for an officer or officers of the Federal

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁹ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.348831</p>	
--	---	--

Court of Australia to perform on behalf of the High Court at an office or offices of the Registry of the High Court referred to in the arrangement all or any of the functions referred to in subsection (6).

(6) The functions to which an arrangement under subsection (4) or (5) may relate are:

- (a) the receipt of documents to be lodged with or filed in the High Court;
- (b) the signing and issuing of writs, commissions and process;
- (c) the administration of oaths and affirmations for the purposes of any proceedings in the High Court; and
- (d) such other functions as are permitted by Rules of Court to be performed in pursuance of such an arrangement.

(7) Documents received at any office of the Registry for lodgment with or filing in the Court shall be deemed to be received at the Registry.

(8) A copy of an arrangement made under subsection (4) or (5) shall be published in the Gazette.

(9) Where an office of the Registry is established at a place not specifically mentioned in subsection (3), a notice stating that an office of the Registry has been established at that place shall be published in the Gazette.

10.9 High court of Australia act 1979

- SECT 45

Proceedings in respect of administration of the Court

Any judicial or other proceedings relating to matters arising out of the administration of the affairs of the High Court under section 17, including any proceedings relating to matters arising out of the performance of the functions or the exercise of the powers of the Chief Executive and Principal Registrar under this Act, may be instituted

by or against the Commonwealth, as the case requires.

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

10.10 High court of Australia (fees) regulations 2022

Division 2.3—when fees are not payable

10 When fees are not payable

(1) A fee mentioned in Schedule 1 is not payable by the liable person for the fee if another person has paid the fee. Page | 234

(2) A fee mentioned in Schedule 1 is not payable in a proceeding for which an international convention that is in force for Australia provides that no fee is to be payable.

(3) A fee mentioned in any of items 108 to 110 of Schedule 1 is not payable in relation to an interlocutory proceeding.

(4) A hearing fee is not payable in relation to a hearing if the sole purpose of the hearing is the delivery of a reserved judgment.

Division 2.4—exemptions and financial hardship fees

11 Persons exempt from paying fees

(1) A person is exempt from paying a filing fee or a hearing fee if, at the time the fee is payable, one or more of the following apply:

(a) the person has been granted legal aid for the proceeding for which the fee would otherwise be payable under a legal aid scheme or service:

- (i) established under a law of the Commonwealth or of a State or Territory; or
- (ii) approved by the Attorney-General;

(b) the person is the holder of any of the following cards issued by the Commonwealth:

- (i) a health care card;
- (ii) a pensioner concession card;
- (iii) a Commonwealth seniors health card;
- (iv) any other card that certifies the holder's entitlement to Commonwealth health concessions;

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology</p> <p>Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia</p> <p>International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva</p> <p>Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	--	--

(c) the person is serving a sentence of imprisonment or is otherwise detained in a public institution, or is in immigration detention (within the meaning of the *Migration Act 1958*);

(d) the person is younger than 18;

(e) the person is receiving youth allowance or Austudy payments under the *Social Security Act 1991* or benefits under the ABSTUDY Scheme; Page | 235

(f) the person has received funding for the proceeding for which the fee would otherwise be payable under Part 11 of the *Native Title Act 1993* from:

(i) a representative body within the meaning of section 253 of that Act; or

(ii) a person or body to whom funding has been made available under section 203FE of that Act.

(2) For paragraph (1)(b), the **holder** of a card does not include a dependant of the person who is issued the card.

12 Financial hardship fees

(1) If:

(a) a full fee mentioned in an item in Schedule 1 is payable by an individual; and

(b) the item mentions a financial hardship fee; and

(c) in the opinion of a Registrar at the time the full fee is payable, the payment of the full fee would cause financial hardship to the individual;

the Registrar may determine that the individual may pay the financial hardship fee mentioned in the item instead of the full fee that would otherwise be payable.

(2) In considering whether payment of the full fee would cause financial hardship to an individual, the Registrar must consider the individual's income, day-to-day living expenses, liabilities and assets.

Note: A decision of the Registrar under this section is reviewable by the AAT: see section 17.

10.11 Federal register of legislation; higher education support act 2003; 19-38 higher education providers' expenditure of student services and amenities fees

(4) Subsection (3) does not prohibit expenditure for a purpose that relates to the provision of any of the following services:

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

- (e) providing legal services to students;
- (f) promoting the health or welfare of students;
- (g) helping students secure accommodation;
- (j) helping students obtain insurance against personal accidents;
- (k) supporting debating by students;
- (o) helping students develop skills for study, by means other than undertaking *courses of study or *accelerator program courses in which they are enrolled;
- (s) helping meet the specific needs of *overseas students relating to their welfare, accommodation and employment.

10.12 Federal Register of Legislation; Higher Education Support Act 2003

22-15: revocation of approval as a provider for a breach of conditions or the quality and accountability requirements

breached a *quality and accountability requirement, refer to high court rules, rule 24.01

10.13 Australian public service act 1999, no. 147, 1999, compilation no. 22

15 Breaches of the Code of Conduct

Sanctions that may be imposed

(1) An Agency Head may impose the following sanctions on an APS employee in the Agency who is found (under procedures established under subsection (3) of this section or subsection 41B (3) or 50A (2)) to have breached the Code of Conduct:

- (a) termination of employment;
- (b) reduction in classification;
- (c) re-assignment of duties;
- (d) reduction in salary;
- (e) deductions from salary, by way of fine;
- (f) a reprimand.

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg., City University, Bangladesh Former Assis. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg., BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assis. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assis. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	---	---

11 Acknowledgement

Sole author, chief director, PhD research; chief director & chief defence scientist, Textile, defence research centre; RMIT; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc; Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>) (**M. A. Hossain & A. Samanta, 2018**) (A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b; Hossain, Islam, et al., 2018; A. Hossain & A. Samanta, 2019; A. Hossain & A. K. Samanta, 2018; Hossain, Samanta, Bhaumik, et al., 2018; Hossain, Samanta, NS, et al., 2018; A. Hossain et al., 2019; Hossain, 2009, 2010b, 2010c, 2015a, 2019a, 2019c, 2019d; M. A. Hossain, 2021a, 2021c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a, 2022c; Md Anowar Hossain, 2022; M. A. Hossain, 2023ap; M. A. Hossain et al., 2019; M. A. Hossain & A. K. Samanta, 2019) (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024a) (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024a) (M. A. Hossain, 2023aj, 2023am, 2023bj, 2023cj, 2023ck) (Anowar Hossain, 2016; A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b, 2023; Hossain, 17 May 2023, 2010a, 2015b, 2015c, 2018, 2019b; M. A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b, 2021c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a, 2022b, 2022c; Md Anowar Hossain, 2022; M. A. Hossain, 2023a, 2023b, 2023c, 2023d, 2023e, 2023f, 2023h, 2023i, 2023j, 2023k, 2023l, 2023m, 2023n, 2023o, 2023p, 2023q, 2023r, 2023s, 2023t, 2023u, 2023v, 2023w, 2023x, 2023y, 2023z, 2023aa, 2023ab, 2023ac, 2023ad, 2023ae, 2023af, 2023ag, 2023ah, 2023ai, 2023aj, 2023ak, 2023al, 2023am, 2023an, 2023ao, 2023ap, 2023aq, 2023ar, 2023as, 2023at, 2023au, 2023av, 2023aw, 2023ax, 2023ay, 2023az, 2023ba, 2023bb, 2023bc, 2023bd, 2023be, 2023bf, 2023bg, 2023bh, 2023bi, 2023bj, 2023bk, 2023bl, 2023bm, 2023bn; M. A. Hossain, 2023a; M. A. Hossain, 2023bo, 2023bp, 2023bq, 2023br, 2023bs, 2023bt; M. A. Hossain, 2023b; M. A. Hossain, 2023bu, 2023bv, 2023bw; M. A. Hossain, 2023c, 2023d, 2023e; M. A. Hossain, 2023by, 2023bz, 2023ca, 2023cb, 2023cc, 2023cd, 2023ce; M. A. Hossain, 2023f, 2023g; M. A. Hossain, 2023cf, 2023cg, 2023ch, 2023cj, 2023ck, 2023cl, 2023cm; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024b, 2024c, 2024d, 2024e, 2024f, 2024g, 2024h, 2024i, 2024j, 2024k, 2024l, 2024m, 2024n, 2024o, 2024p, 2024q, 2024r, 2024s, 2024t, 2024u, 2024v, 2024w, 2024y, 2024z; Md.. Anowar Hossain, 2024; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024aa; Hossain, 2025a, 2025b, 2025c, 2025d, 2025e, 2025f, 2025g, 2025h; Nobel Nominee Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, 2025); name of father: late Dr. Md. Abdur Rashid, medical practitioner; permanent residence (PR): village: Purbo Nuthurchar, post office: K. Mohonpur (1990), police station: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh, South Asia (PR by birth); nationality, national ID, passport and birth registration number: Bangladeshi, 19862692620993890, A15988852/EE0444946/AF3831770, 003236; PhD (Doctor of Philosophy) application ID: 2612540, PhD student ID: 3820066, program name: DR213, PhD (fashion and textiles), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; lecturer on textile engineering (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh acknowledges RMIT University and the Australian government for funding through research training program (RTP) stipend scholarship, 2020-2025. Author, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain; Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

(<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>) also acknowledges ‘Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang’ (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7300-9271>) and ‘Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks’ (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3790-5148>) for their PhD supervision works at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.

12 Achievement and invention of ‘twin PhD’ at RMIT

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) is the first inventor, first achiever, and first introducer of ‘twin PhD’ in textile engineering, and applied law and criminology at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (M. A. Hossain, 2023g, 2023bx; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x).

12.1 Limitations and struggling of achieving ‘twin PhD’ of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain (M. A. Hossain, 2023g, 2023bx; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x).

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) had food crisis, living cost crisis, and safety crisis to achieve ‘twin PhD’ in textile engineering, and applied law and criminology at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia when Professor Rajiv Padhye parallelly continued the conspiracy of killing and conspiracy of killing to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.). Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain asked help and support to the cabinet ministry of Bangladesh, the cabinet ministry of Australia, and secretary general of United Nations who had zero support and zero contribution to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) when Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was a valid member/citizen of Bangladesh association/country (M. A. Hossain, 2023g, 2023bw, 2023bx; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k, 2024x; Hossain, 2025f, 2025g).

13 Limitations of writing this report to the prime minister of Australia, ministerial cabinet of Australia, ministerial cabinet of Bangladesh, and United Nations

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) had food crisis, living cost crisis, and safety crisis to write this report to the ministerial cabinet of Australia, ministerial cabinet of Bangladesh, and United Nations for the legal costs and legal support for the legal claim in Australian court and/or international court when Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was a valid member/citizen of Bangladesh association/country (M. A. Hossain, 2023g, 2023bw, 2023bx; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k, 2024x; Hossain, 2025f, 2025g).

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.). Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anwar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anwar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anwar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	---	---

14 Author contribution and authorship status of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

The author has contribution in conceptualization, visualization, resource, self-supervision, funding acquisition, project administration, research communications, planning and prediction, analysis, writing the original draft, manuscript editing, and publication process. The scholarship or funder has no scholarly role of the design of research, research idea or visualization, research and innovation, drafting of manuscript, editing of manuscript, and publication of manuscript.

15 Declaration of conflicting interests

The author declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship and/or publication of this article.

16 Funding

The author received no financial support for the research, authorship and/or publication of this article.

17 Data availability

All data generated during the coalescing of this article are included, attached and briefly cited in reference list.

18 Notes of exemption in the research of applied law and criminology for zero crime approach for the peace of mankind

The criminal/criminals/crime/crimes/people/peoples is/are international. The crime history is original and practical in PhD and Postdoc journey of Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain at RMIT University, Australia. In the research of applied law and criminology, the relevant human assessment, names, case studies, and organizations have been cited and implemented

- ✓ to establish the legal rights and human rights to the researchers/PhD scholars/professors/scientists.
- ✓ to enhance the responsibilities of relevant ministerial cabinet of a country/organization.
- ✓ to protect the data information of crimes and criminals for the international category judicial assessment.
- ✓ to show the practical evidence of crime and criminals.

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anwar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

- ✓ to protect the peoples to ensure human defence and human peace in international platform.
- ✓ to ensure the safety of relevant peoples and/or organizations and/or professor community and/or researcher community and/or RMIT University, Australia.
- ✓ to notify crime courts, judges, review boards, judicial board, human rights, united nations, and relevant international communities.
- ✓ to continue research and development.
- ✓ to circulate the outcomes of academic research.
- ✓ to approach zero crime for the peace of mankind.

19 Legal authorization and signing

Kind regards

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

27 September 2025

(Md. Anowar Hossain)

Signature

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.); Barrister (Dr.); Postdoc & PhD in Applied Law; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, and BSc Engineering in Textile Technology

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, MTech
PhD Researcher, ID: 3820066
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University
512.01.12, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick
Vic-3056, Australia.

Office of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain; Defence Scientist; Barrister (Dr.); Postdoc & PhD in Applied Law; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, and BSc Engineering in Textile Technology

19.1 Research address and contact

512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia.

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	--	--

E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile Phone: +8801788396264

19.2 Please visit online profile of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Page | 241

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

19.3 Permanent Address

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Vill: Purbo Nuthurchar, Post Office: K. Mohonpur (1990), Police Station: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh (by birth)

19.4 Professional Address

School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia.

E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, Mobile phone: +8801788396264

20 For showing honour, for the excellency of PhD schooling; a copy of this report is also being forwarded (randomly sequenced) to (relevant concern should be liable for their responsibility of this letter of legal protection and legal service to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain)

Professor Dr. Lijing Wang, RMIT University; PhD supervisor of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist

PhD student ID: 3820066, 512.01.12, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, RMIT University, Melbourne, Vic-3056, The Commonwealth of Australia.

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

lijing.wang@rmit.edu.au

Emeritus Professor Dr. Robert Shanks, RMIT University; PhD supervisor of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist

Page | 242

PhD student ID: 3820066, 512.01.12, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, RMIT University, Melbourne, Vic-3056, The Commonwealth of Australia.

robert.shanks@rmit.edu.au

robert.shanks.scientific@gmail.com

Ms. Penny Wong, Foreign minister of Australia

Online form

vso@dfat.gov.au

Mr. Anthony Albanese, MP, Australian Prime Minister, Department of the Prime Minister and Cabinet, The Commonwealth of Australia

Online form

Mr. Md. Touhid Hossain, Foreign Minister of Bangladesh

Mr. Md. Jashim Uddin, Foreign Secretary of Bangladesh

Mr. Asad Alam Siam, Foreign Secretary of Bangladesh

fa@mofa.gov.bd

apsfao@mofa.gov.bd

dirfao@mofa.gov.bd

pro@mofa.gov.bd

fs@mofa.gov.bd

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)³ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁴ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCME College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia, Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	---	---

dirfso@mofa.gov.bd

ssa@mofa.gov.bd

Advocate Md. Asaduzzaman, Chairman, Bangladesh bar council

info@barcouncil.gov.bd

Mr. Md. Asaduzzaman (translated)

Attorney General, Bangladesh

attorneygeneral@attorneygeneral.gov.bd

ps_ag@attorneygeneral.gov.bd

Mr. Muhammad Abdul Jabbar Bhuiyan (translated)

Additional Attorney General, Bangladesh

Adv.ajbl@gmail.com

ps_addl_ag1@attorneygeneral.gov.bd

Mr. Md. Arshadur Rouf (translated)

Additional attorney general

addl_ag2@attorneygeneral.gov.bd

ps_addl_ag2@attorneygeneral.gov.bd

Mr. Mohammad Anik Rushad Haque (translated)

Additional attorney general

addl_ag3@attorneygeneral.gov.bd

ps_addl_ag3@attorneygeneral.gov.bd

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Attorney-General's Department, Australia

Online form

Page | 244

Central library of Bangladesh

cdlbd21@gmail.com

British library, United Kingdom

customer@bl.uk

British Library of United Kingdom

customer@bl.uk

Library, RMIT University, Australia

repository@rmit.edu.au

Office of the Registry, High Court of Australia

Registry@hcourt.gov.au

Professor Dr. SMA Faiz, Chairman, University Grant Commission, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

fakhrul@ugc.gov.bd

secretary@ugc.gov.bd

syrawarn@gmail.com

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court; international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	---	--

nazmul@ugc.gov.bd

director_research@ugc.gov.bd

ferdousugc@gmail.com

chairman@ugc.gov.bd

mustafiz@ugc.gov.bd, mustafizugc@gmail.com, pschairman@ugc.gov.bd

Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye, RMIT University, Australia; Chief defendant of life-threatening conspiracy against Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

rajiv.padhye@rmit.edu.au

Dr. Kamal Hossain, lawyer, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

khossain@citechco.net

Brig Gen Prof. Dr. Engr. Md Lutfor Rahman (Retd), Vice Chancellor, City University, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

vc@cityuniversity.ac.bd

registrar@cityuniversity.ac.bd

Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President, Office of President, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh, Bangabhaban, Dhaka, Bangladesh

secretary@bangabhaban.gov.bd

press.secy@bangabhaban.gov.bd

ps_president@bangabhaban.gov.bd

akmmonirul31@gmail.com

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Ms. Michelle Rowland, MP, Attorney General/Law Minister of Australia and Mr. Mark Dreyfus KC MP, Attorney General/Law Minister of Australia

Online form

Page | 246

Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Economist

Chief Advisor, Office of Chief Advisor, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

State Guest House Jamuna, Dhaka, Bangladesh

majumderali1950@gmail.com

musfiquldu33@gmail.com

psecy@cao.gov.bd

secretary@cao.gov.bd

seafath.mahmud@cao.gov.bd

lutfey.siddiqi@cao.gov.bd

Professor Dr. Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University, Melbourne, The Commonwealth of Australia

vc@rmit.edu.au

brooke.griffin@rmit.edu.au

ea.vc@rmit.edu.au

jason.ngam@rmit.edu.au

nicole.hendrie@rmit.edu.au

alec.cameron@rmit.edu.au

alec.cameron@aarnet.edu.au

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.). Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	---	---

Dr. AKM Saiful Islam, City University, Dhaka, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

s.islam05@gmail.com

saiful.bste@cityuniversity.ac.bd

Professor Dr. AK Samanta, University of Calcutta, Kolkata, West Bengal, The Republic of India

ijtaksamanta@gmail.com

ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com

Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh, University of Calcutta, The Republic of India

ijtskg40@gmail.com

Professor Dr. Sadhan Chandra Roy, University of Calcutta, The Republic of India

sadhan53@yahoo.co.in

Professor Dr. Danmei Sun, Herriot Watt University, United Kingdom

d.sun@hw.ac.uk

Professor Lola Akin Ojelabi, Interim Dean, School of Law, RMIT University, Australia

lola.akinjelabi@rmit.edu.au

Dr. Andrea Eckersley, HDR Coordinator, RMIT University, The Commonwealth of Australia

andrea.eckersley@rmit.edu.au

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Dr. Scott Mayson, Associate Dean, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, The Commonwealth of Australia

scott.mayson@rmit.edu.au

Dr. Xin Wang, RMIT University, The Commonwealth of Australia

xin.wang@rmit.edu.au

Academic Registrar, RMIT University, The Commonwealth of Australia

academic.registrar@rmit.edu.au

Chief Executive Officer, Victoria Legal Aid, The Commonwealth of Australia

Grants@vla.vic.gov.au

Professor Dr. Alice Payne, Dean, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, The Commonwealth of Australia

alice.payne@rmit.edu.au

Professor Dr. Robyn Healy, Former Dean, College of Design and Social Context, RMIT University

Mobile: +61399259100

Email address: robyn.healy@rmit.edu.au

Professional address: Level 7, Building 8, 360 Swanston Street, Melbourne, 3000; Postal Address: College of Design and Social Context, GPO Box 2476, Melbourne, Victoria, 3001

Professor Dr. Calum Drummond, Deputy Vice Chancellor, Research & Innovation, and Vice president, RMIT

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	--	--

Mobile: +61 3 9925 4265

Email address: calum.drummond@rmit.edu.au

Professional Address: RMIT University, GPO Box 2476, Melbourne VIC 3001 Australia

Dr. Karien Dekker, Associate Professor and HDR Director

Mobile: +61 399253354

Email address: karien.dekker@rmit.edu.au

Professional Address: RMIT University, GPO Box 2476, Melbourne VIC 3001 Australia

Professor Dr. Ray Kirby, Dean, School of Engineering, RMIT University, The Commonwealth of Australia

ray.kirby@rmit.edu.au

Dr. Sean Ryan, ethics and integrity concern/officer, RMIT University, The Commonwealth of Australia

sean.ryan@rmit.edu.au

Professor Shelley Marshall, Deputy Dean, Research & Innovation, School of Law, RMIT University, Australia

shelley.marshall@rmit.edu.au

Professor Felix Steffek, Professor of Law, University of Cambridge, UK

Fs256@cam.ac.uk

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Ms. Susan Ryle, High Commissioner of Australia, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

Ms. Nardia Simpson, Acting High Commissioner of Australia, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

ahc.dhaka@dfat.gov.au

consular.dhaka@dfat.gov.au

Page | 250

Mr. M. Allama Siddiki, High Commissioner of The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh, The Commonwealth of Australia

consular.canberra@mofa.gov.bd

labour.canberra@mofa.gov.bd

commerce.canberra@mofa.gov.bd

mission.canberra@mofa.gov.bd

Foreign Minister and/or Foreign Secretary, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

fs@mofa.gov.bd

dirfso@mofa.gov.bd

ssa@mofa.gov.bd

aswelfare@mofa.gov.bd

dgcnw@mofa.gov.bd

dirwelfare@mofa.gov.bd

asconsular2@mofa.gov.bd

Barrister A.M. Mahub Uddin Khokon, President, Bangladesh Supreme Court Bar Association, Shahbag, Dhaka-1000.

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)³ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁴ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg., City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg., BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	---	--

scba.bd@gmail.com

Professor Dr. Md. Shah-E-Alam, Former Vice Chancellor, City University, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

Page | 251

registrar@smuct.ac.bd

Professor Dr. Niaz Ahmed Khan, Vice Chancellor, University of Dhaka, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

registrar@du.ac.bd

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Forhad Hossen, Dean, Dyes and Chemical Engineering Department, Bangladesh University of Textiles, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

head@dce.butex.edu.bd

butexdce@gmail.com

Professor Dr. Md. Nurul Absar, Jahangirnagar University, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

absarju@yahoo.com

Dr. Md. Emran Hossain, Department of Law, City University, Dhaka, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

ehossainsau@gmail.com

Professor Dr Abu Borhan Mohammad Badruzzaman, Vice Chancellor, Bangladesh University of Engineering and Technology, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

kamrul_regbuet@yahoo.com

rakib_ao@regtr.buet.ac.bd

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

saikatbarua@dce.buet.ac.bd

Professor Dr. Bodh Raj Mehta, Vice Chancellor, Indian Institute of Technology, The Republic of India

Page | 252

registrar@admin.iitd.ac.in

brmehta@physics.iitd.ernet.in

brmehta_p@hotmail.com

Professor Dr. Mohammad Kamrul Ahsan, Vice Chancellor, Jahangirnagar University, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

registrarju@gmail.com

Professor Dr. Engr. Saifur Rahman, Daffodil International University, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

drsaifur@diu.edu.bd

fukudaiko@yahoo.com

Dr. Kamal Uddin Ahmed, Chairman, Human Rights Commission, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

ftm@nhrc.org.bd

chairman@nhrc.org.bd

secretary@nhrc.org.bd

liptonbjs@gmail.com

Human Rights Commission, The Commonwealth of Australia

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)³ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁴ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India, Australia, Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	---	---

Online form

Professor Dr. Ayub Nabi, Pro Vice Chancellor, BGMEA University of Fashion & Technology,
 The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

provc@buft.edu.bd

Barrister Sarwar Jahan Shamim, Supreme Court of Bangladesh

bshamimsc@gmail.com

Ms. Tasmima Hossain, Editor, The Daily Ittefaq, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

ittefaqdigital@gmail.com

ittefaq.adsection@gmail.com

Editor, The Australians, The Commonwealth of Australia

letters@theaustralian.com.au

victoria@theaustralian.com.au

wa@theaustralian.com.au

act@theaustralian.com.au

Mr. Peter Dunning KC, President, Australian Bar Association, The Commonwealth of Australia

dunning@callinanchambers.com.au

contact@austbar.asn.au

media@austbar.asn.au

Mr. Vlka Singh, President of Supreme Court Bar Association, India

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Singh.vikas@gmail.com

Advocate Kapil Sibal, President, The Bar Association of India, 93, Lawyers Chambers, Supreme Court of India, New Delhi - 110 001, The Republic of India

Page | 254

info@barindia.in

barindia1959@gmail.com

William R. Bay, President, American Bar Association

service@americanbar.org

The Bar Council of United Kingdom

ContactUs@BarCouncil.org.uk

press@barcouncil.org.uk

Amnesty International, American Human Rights

info.eseaprobangkok@amnesty.org

contactus@amnesty.org

Ministry of Law, Bangladesh

secretary@lawjusticediv.gov.bd;

adviser@minlaw.gov.bd;

zillurlaw@gmail.com;

shamimsrm@yahoo.com;

svdul1980@gmail.com;

additional_secretary@lawjusticediv.gov.bd

Chairman, Department of Textile Engineering, Dhaka University of Engineering and Technology, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁹ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	---	--

head_te@duet.ac.bd

Vice Chancellor, Dhaka University of Engineering and Technology, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

reg_duet@duet.ac.bd

Professor Dr. Md. Anwarul Azim Akhand, Vice Chancellor, Maulana Bhashani Science and Technology University, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

registrar@mbstu.ac.bd

Professor Dr. Md. Abdullah Al Mamun, Chairman, Department of Textile Engineering, Maulana Bhashani Science and Technology University, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

registrar@mbstu.ac.bd

Professor Dr. Md. Anwarul Azim Akhand, Vice Chancellor, Maulana Bhashani Science and Technology University, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

registrar@mbstu.ac.bd

Professor Dr. Mohammad Abdul Jalil, Chairman, Department of Textile Engineering, Khulna University of Engineering and Technology, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

drjalil@te.kuet.ac.bd

Prof. Mohammad Mashud, Vice Chancellor, Khulna University of Engineering and Technology, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

registrar@kuet.ac.bd

vc@kuet.ac.bd

ps2vc@kuet.ac.bd

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Engr. Md. Ashrafur Kabir, Chairman, BCMC College of Engineering and Technology, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

bmccrm@hotmail.com

Page | 256

Professor Dr. Arun Kanti Guha, Department of Textile Engineering, South East University, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

arun.guha@seu.edu.bd

Prof. Dr. Nitai Chandra Sutradhar, Chairman, Department of Textile Engineering, Green University of Bangladesh, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

chairman@tex.green.edu.bd

Ms. Freya Baetens, Professor of Public International Law; University of Oxford, Research Director, Oxford Human Rights Hub; E-mail: Freya.Baetens@law.ox.ac.uk

Mr. John Armour, Professor of Law and Finance, University of Oxford; E-mail: lawfac@law.ox.ac.uk

Mr. Jason Clare, MP, Education Minister and/or Secretary of Education Department, The Commonwealth of Australia

contact.centre@education.gov.au

Mr. Tony Burke, MP, Minister of Home Affairs of Australia

Online form

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.). Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁹ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	--	--

International team (chancery), Judicial Office, High Court, 11th floor, Thomas More Building

Royal Courts of Justice, Strand London, WC2A 2LL, United Kingdom; E-mail:
international@judiciary.uk

U.S. Department of Justice, Civil Division, 950 Pennsylvania Avenue, N.W. Washington, DC
 20530-0001, E-mail: Civil.Feedback@usdoj.gov; OIIA@usdoj.gov

Mr. Donald Trump, President, United States of America; Office of President, United States of
 America

Online form

Mr. Keir Starmer, Prime minister of United Kingdom; Office of Prime minister, United Kingdom

Online form

Mr. Frank-Walter Steinmeier, President of Germany; Office of President, Germany

Online form

Mr. Mark Carney, Prime Minister of Canada; Office of Prime Minister, Canada

Online form

Mr. Shigeru Ishiba, Office of Prime Minister of Japan; Office of Prime Minister, Japan

Online form

Ms. Droupadi Murmu, President of India; Office of President, India

Online form

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of
 Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT
 University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Ulf Kristersson, President of Sweden; Office of President, Sweden

Online form

Mr. Jonas Gahr Store, Prime Minister of Norway; Office of Prime Minister, Norway

Online form

Vladimir Vladimirovich Putin, President of Russia; Office of President, Russia

Online form

Xi Jinping, President of China; Office of President, China

Online form

Mr. Emmanuel Macron, President of France; Office of President, France

Online form

Asif Ali Zardari; President of Pakistan; Office of President, Pakistan

Online form

Office of Secretary General, United Nations

Online form

Office of President, United Nations

Online form

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.). Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	---	---

Director, Nobel Prize Organization

Online form

Charles Philip Arthur George, King Charles III, King of United Kingdom

Online form

Ms. Sam Mostyn, Governor General, Australia

Online form

General Registrar, High Court of Bangladesh

rg@supremecourt.gov.bd

Justice Syed Refaat Ahmed, Chief Justice, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

contact@dhakatribune.com

Professor Iain Martin, Vice Chancellor, Deakin University, The Commonwealth of Australia

igmartin@deakin.edu.au

Professor Calum Drummond, RMIT University, The Commonwealth of Australia

calum.drummond@rmit.edu.au

Professor Dr. Md. Abdur Rahman Bhuiyan, Dhaka University of Engineering and Technology,
The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

arahman@duet.ac.bd

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Professor V. Ramgopal Rao, Vice Chancellor, Birla Institute of Technology, Pilani, vc@pilani.bits-pilani.ac.in

Page | 260

International/UN Human Rights Commission

headquarters@ihrhq.org, office@ihrhq.org, geneva@ihrhq.org, ohchr-infoDesk@un.org

Registrar office of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist; Plaintiff of self-life-threatening conspiracy of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.); The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

21 Professional excellency of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Invitation of PhD Researchers in international platform for global peace of mankind. a. f. P. e. a. o. t. w. o. A. Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, engr.anowar@yahoo.com.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19237.88800>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8268846>

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is expected for full-time/part-time/contractual/casual positions of professional services all over the world. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13240.32001>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10360586>

Services for crime in higher education & quality enhancement in an international platform. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26551.70569>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8278997>

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)³ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁴ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	--	---

Services for crime protection and crime analysis for the peace of mankind in an international platform. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36618.03522>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8279067>

Specialized services and payment rate of Professor (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21820.00643>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10360742>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is the first inventor of '2100–4200-point policy for the impact factor to certify researcher for PhD degree by Research' and 'PhD in PhD'.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35642.20167>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12604715>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is the first inventor of a 1150–2300-point policy to certify or review a research manuscript or thesis for publication R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; engr.anowar@yahoo.com.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30482.88003>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12735576>

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1100–2200-point policy for the impact factor to admit/appoint researcher position for Master degree by research.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12531.75048>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11516770>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1250–2500-point policy for the impact factor to certify university designation and university promotion from lecturer to professor.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13177.68968>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11183360>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 7050–14100-point policy for the impact factor or ranking of an international standard University.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25604.13447>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10814275>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the inventor of 10-point policy to elect the democratic leaders all over the world. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19343.76968>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10662617>

Invitation of law researchers in Master by thesis, PhD by thesis, and Postdoc by thesis.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30060.63369>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16995119>

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), M.Tech Textile Engg (CU, India), B.Sc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assisit. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assisit. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assisit. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	--	---

Invitation of legal client for legal service to individual and/or organization.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13073.70249>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16990186>

Invitation of researchers in textile engineering in Master by thesis, PhD by thesis, and Postdoc by thesis. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17215.57765>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16960861> Page | 263

22 Reference

- Anowar Hossain, A. K. S., A. Bagchi, Kashmita Bhattacharya. (2016). Simultaneous Dyeing and Fragrance Finishing of Cotton Fabric. *Journal of Materials Sciences and Applications, American Association for Science and Technology (AASCIT), USA, 2(4), 25-34.*
<https://documents.pub/document/simultaneous-dyeing-and-fragrance-finishing-of-cotton-simultaneous-dyeing-and.html?page=1>
- Hossain, A. (2020). A Practical Guideline of Few Standardized Ready Made Shades of Natural Dyed Textiles. In A. K. Samanta & N. S. Awwad (Eds.), *Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments* (pp. 151-170). IntechOpen.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.92360>
- Hossain, A. (2021a). Concealment, Detection, Recognition, and Identification of Target Signature on Water Background under Natural Illumination. *International Journal of Science and Engineering Investigations, 10(117), 1-11, Article 1011721-01.*
<http://www.ijsei.com/papers/ijsei-1011721-01.pdf>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8242827>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.10885.32487>
- Hossain, A. (2021b). Spectral simulation and method design of camouflage textiles for concealment of hyperspectral imaging in UV-Vis-IR against multidimensional combat background. *The Journal of the Textile Institute, 1-12.*
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00405000.2022.2027074>
- Hossain, A. (2023). *Reporting to Victoria Legal Aid, Australia for the grant of legal assistance for ethical defending for the peace in PhD education against conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in Australian PhD School.*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18289.25443>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10207100>
- Hossain, A., Islam, A. S., & Samanta, A. K. (2018). Pollution Free Dyeing on Cotton Fabric Extracted from Swietenia macrophylla and Musa Acuminata as Unpolluted Dyes and Citrus. Limon (L.) as Unpolluted Mordanting Agent. *Trends in Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology, 3(2), 1-8.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.31031/TTEFT.2018.03.000558>
- Hossain, A., & Samanta, A. (2019). Effect of Variation in Different Mechanical Setting of Draft Change Pinion in Trutzschler Carding, Machine for Cotton and Polyester Carded Slivers. *Current Trends in Fashion Technology & Textile Engineering, 4(4).*
<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Effect-of-Variation-in-Different-Mechanical->

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

[Setting-Hossain/9402f52697c08f2b6104abb07e1f4f414aa3f332;](http://dx.doi.org/10.19080/CTFTTE.2019.04.555650)
<http://dx.doi.org/10.19080/CTFTTE.2019.04.555650>

- Hossain, A., & Samanta, A. K. (2018). Cost Minimization in Sample Development and Approval Process by Proper Merchandising Action for kids and Ladies Garments. *Trends in Textile Engineering and Fashion Technology (Online), USA*.
<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Cost-Minimisation-in-Sample-Development-and-Process-Hossain-Samanta/ee6de04748b507cdec19cb7af66cfde0870a5b0d>;
<https://doi.org/10.31031/TTEFT.2018.04.000590>
- Hossain, A., Samanta, A. K., Bhaumik, N. S., Vankar, P. S., & Shukla, D. (2018). Organic Colouration and Antimicrobial Finishing of Organic Cotton Fabric by Exploiting Distilled Organic Extraction of Organic Tectona grandis and Azadirachta indica with Organic Mordanting Compare to Conventional Inorganic Mordants. *International Journal of Textile Science and Engineering*, 2018(1), 1-12.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21790.51524>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8245102>
- Hossain, A., Samanta, A. K., NS, B., PS, V., & Shukla. (2018). Non-toxic Coloration of Cotton Fabric using Non-toxic Colorant and Nontoxic Crosslinker. *Journal of Textile Science & Engineering*, 8(5), 1-5. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Non-toxic-Coloration-of-Cotton-Fabric-using-and-Hossain-Samanta/76a9a8128bc038db760f2b93328e4eeFeb2ae4d1>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.4172/2165-8064.1000374>
- Hossain, A., Sun, D., & Samanta, A. (2019). Modern Technology versus Rapid Economical Growth in Smart Textiles Incorporated with Encapsulated Phase Change Materials Containing Latent Heat for Special Workers and Extreme Weather Conditions. *JResLit Journal of Science and Technology*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15079.62880>;
https://pure.hw.ac.uk/ws/portalfiles/portal/92968499/Modern_Technology_versus_Rapid_Economical_Growth....pdf; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8245107>
- Hossain, M. A. (17 May 2023). *Anowar's Handbook on Application of Computer in Textiles*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23199.53923>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15709410>
- Hossain, M. A. (2009). *Basic Knowledge of Wet Processing Technology*, ISBN-978-984-35-2885-8, Issued on 10 August 2022, Department of Archives and Library, Ministry of Cultural affairs, Government of The People's Republic of Bangladesh (Vol. 1-4). Rupok Publications. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844857>
- Hossain, M. A. (2010a). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Raw Materials II*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar,

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)*
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)*
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assis. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assis. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assis. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29667.94247>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8241586>

Hossain, M. A. (2010b). *Garments Technology for Merchandiser and Fashion Designer*, ISBN-978-984-35-2883-4, Issued on 10 August 2022, Department of Archives and Library, Ministry of Cultural affairs, Government of The People's Republic of Bangladesh. Rupok Publications, 140, Islamia market, Nilkhet, Dhaka, 2010.

Page | 265

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844933>

Hossain, M. A. (2010c). *Principle of garments production*, ISBN-978-984-35-2884-1, Issued on 10 August 2022, Department of Archives and Library, Ministry of Cultural affairs, Government of The People's Republic of Bangladesh. Rupok Publications.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844918>

Hossain, M. A. (2015a, 26th April, 2015). *Integrated dyeing and cosmetic finishing on cotton fabric* 6th all India Inter Engineering college academic meet-2015 and Science & Technology exhibition for a sustainable society, Organised by Forum of Scientist, Engineers & Technologists (FOSET), 15N, Nelli Sengupta Sarani (Lindsay Street), Kolkata-7000087, India. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29340.26244>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13304637>

Hossain, M. A. (2015b). *Power Point Presentation on Combined dyeing and cosmetic finishing of woven cotton fabric for garments* (Department of Jute and Fibre technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, India, Issue. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28804.50568>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8311367>

Hossain, M. A. (2015c). *Textile coloration and fragrance finishing for perfumed garments* [Textile Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-70019, West Bengal, India.]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15918.48965>;
<http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7854437>

Hossain, M. A. (2018). *Power Point Presentation on Applications and Engineering of Geotextiles* (Department of Textile Engineering, City university, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh (engr.anowar@yahoo.com), Issue. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17899.31521>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8311345>

Hossain, M. A. (2019a). Cyclodextrin for Aroma Finishing on Textile Substrate-A Review Article. *International Journal of Science and Engineering Investigations*, 8(89). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.11724.18561>; <http://www.ijsei.com/archive-88919.htm>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8242756>

Hossain, M. A. (2019b). Uster analysis of cotton/polyester blended spun yarns with different counts. *Journal of Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology*, 5(4). <http://dx.doi.org/10.15406/jteft.2019.05.00204>

Hossain, M. A. (2019c). Uster Imperfections of 35% Cotton and 65% Polyester Blended Yarn for 40Ne, 50Ne and 60Ne Ring Spun Yarn. *South Asian Research Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 1(2).

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

<https://www.sciencegate.app/document/10.36346/sarjet.2019.v01i02.002;>

https://sarpublication.com/media/articles/SARJET_12_43-49_c.pdf

Hossain, M. A. (2019d). Zero Toxic Approach of Cotton Fabric Coloration with Botanical Waste resource via Psidium P. guajava (Guava Leaves) as Natural Dyes and Citrus Lemon (Lemon Leaves) as Natural Mordanting Agent. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18112.75524;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13850320>

Hossain, M. A. (2020). My first presentation at PhD School for selection of PhD research proposal on camouflage textiles in 2020. Academic conference at PhD School, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Australia, Vic-3056, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7918250>, <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33383.11680>.

Hossain, M. A. (2021a). Adaptive Camouflage Textiles with Thermochromic Colorant and Liquid Crystal for Multidimensional Combat Background, a Technical Approach for Advancement in Defence Protection. *American Journal of Materials Engineering and Technology*, 9(1), 31-47. <http://pubs.sciepub.com/materials/9/1/3/>

Hossain, M. A. (2021b). *Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration and Incorporating Illumination* (Presented in academic conference, First milestone of PhD candidature, RMIT University, 12 February 2021, Issue. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844692>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28897.48488>

Hossain, M. A. (2021c). Evaluation of Camouflage Coloration of Polyamide-6,6 Fabric by Comparing Simultaneous Spectrum in Visible and Near-Infrared Region for Defense Applications. In A. K. Samanta (Ed.), *Colorimetry* (pp. 1-22). IntechOpen. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.101537>

Hossain, M. A. (2022a). Camouflage Assessment Of Aluminium Coated Textiles for Woodland and Desertland Combat Background in Visible and Infrared Spectrum under UV-Vis-IR Background Illumination. *Defence Science Journal*, 72(3), 359-370. <https://publications.drdo.gov.in/ojs/index.php/dsj/article/view/17731/7785>

Hossain, M. A. (2022b). *Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration and Incorporating Illumination under Multidimensional Combat Background* (Presented in humanities and social context conference, second milestone of PhD candidature, RMIT University; 15 February 2022, Issue. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844729>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32252.92803>

Hossain, M. A. (2022c). Ecofriendly Camouflage Textiles with Natural Sand-based Silicon Dioxide against Simultaneous Combat Background of Woodland, Desertland, Rockland, Concreteland and Water/Marine. *Preprint (Version 1) available at Research Square* <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2359705/v1>

Hossain, M. A. (2022). Simulation of chromatic and achromatic assessments for camouflage textiles and combat background. *Journal of Defense Modeling and Simulation*:

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

A follow-up letter from Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is asking for legal costs, legal support, and 1,00,000 Australian penalty units to Mr. Anthony Albanese, Prime Minister of Australia.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD⁵ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology</p> <p>Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁶ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁷ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia</p> <p>International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg., City University, Bangladesh Former Assis. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg., BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assis. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assis. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva</p> <p>Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
--	---	--

Applications, Methodology, Technology, 1-16.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/15485129211067759>

Hossain, M. A. (2023a). *50% income support and 100% life-safety compensation were requested and proposed to Professor Dr. Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University for 63 years duration under calculation of 100 years life-time of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29528.47360>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10159331>

Hossain, M. A. (2023b). *Academic Certificates, academic achievements and citizen identity of Professor (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33349.83689>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16256788>

Hossain, M. A. (2023c). *Advancement in UV-Visible-IR Camouflage Textiles and Camouflage Physics. Scholarly Community Encyclopedia.* <https://encyclopedia.pub/entry/49095>

Hossain, M. A. (2023d). *Anowar's Handbook on Color Engineering for Textile Engineers (Part-2).* School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29805.15844>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7944616>

Hossain, M. A. (2023e). *Anowar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019.* R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13431.39840>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8280942>

Hossain, M. A. (2023f). *Anowar Hossain's invention for peace in PhD schooling, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33291.67366>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14223162>

Hossain, M. A. (2023g). *Anowar Hossain's invention of camouflage physics at PhD School, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29936.23048>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14282063>

Hossain, M. A. (2023h). *Anowar's Handbook International Trade and Marketing Management.* School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25788.21120>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240631>

Hossain, M. A. (2023i). *Anowar's Handbook of Electrical and Electronics Engineering.* School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13624.72966>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15709555>

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

- Hossain, M. A. (2023j). *Anowar's Handbook on Chemistry (Part-1)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12923.49448>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8238071>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023k). *Anowar's Handbook on Chemistry (Part-2)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15879.16801>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8238806>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023l). *Anowar's Handbook on Color Engineering for Textile Engineers (Part-01)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19654.04160>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8239097>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023m). *Anowar's Handbook on Color Engineering for Textile Engineers (Part-3)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35625.16486>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8232618>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023n). *Anowar's Handbook on Color Engineering for Textile Engineers (Part-4)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16822.88641>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8239492>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023o). *Anowar's Handbook on Elements of Mechanical Engineering*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25368.78089>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240371>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023p). *Anowar's Handbook on Elements of Theory of Machine and Machine Design*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28724.22405>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240383>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023q). *Anowar's Handbook on Environment and Safety Management*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia,

Nobel Nominée Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
 Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*}
 Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
 MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process,
 color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)*
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)*
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
 PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assis. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg
 & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assis. Registrar (Exam);
 Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
 Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assis. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
 Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
 University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and
 Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36273.97126>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240507>

Hossain, M. A. (2023r). *Anowar's Handbook on Fabric Structure and Design*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30821.37606>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240534>

Hossain, M. A. (2023s). *Anowar's Handbook on Garments Manufacturing Technology*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27465.93280>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240547>

Hossain, M. A. (2023t). *Anowar's Handbook on Industrial Economics*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34176.81925>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240589>

Hossain, M. A. (2023u). *Anowar's Handbook on Machine Technology & Maintenance of Wet Processing Machineries*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22432.76802>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240660>

Hossain, M. A. (2023v). *Anowar's Handbook on Materials Engineering and Practices*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14883.02082>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240703>

Hossain, M. A. (2023w). *Anowar's Handbook on Microprocessor, Robotics and Control Engineering*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26627.07204>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240796>

Hossain, M. A. (2023x). *Anowar's Handbook on Statistics for Engineer*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17714.17602>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240984>

Hossain, M. A. (2023y). *Anowar's Handbook on Technical Textiles*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar,

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

- Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19391.89763>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8241043>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023z). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Physics (Part-1)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17294.74561>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15613666>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023aa). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Project Management*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35461.32480>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15709510>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ab). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Raw Materials I*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22537.62568>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8241631>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ac). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Testing & Quality Control (Part-3)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23166.77121>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8241394>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ad). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Testing and Quality Control (Part-1)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14778.16327>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8241291>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ae). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Testing and Quality Control (Part-2)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34071.96169>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8241183>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023af). *Anowar's Handbook on Yarn Manufacturing Technology (Part-01)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19896.52484>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8233503>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ag). *Anowar's Handbook on Yarn Manufacturing Technology (Part-2)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick,

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.),
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia),
 Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*}
 Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
 MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process,
 color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)*
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)*
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
 PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg
 & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam);
 Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
 Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
 Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
 University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and
 Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University,
 Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29857.99683>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8233914>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ah). *Application for promotion as Professor (Textile Engineering) and/or right adjustment of my designation under consideration of my Curriculum Vitae (CV), publications and teaching experiences under the promotion act of City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh; supported by the act of University Grants Commission of Bangladesh, Dhaka, Bangladesh.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35245.05606>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8286913>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ai). *Camouflage Textiles against advanced surveillance of defence in UV-Visible-IR spectrums for Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds* (Global Summit on Chemical Engineering and Catalysis (ISTRCEC 2023), accepted on 20 March 2023; Rome, Italy, Issue. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7847802>;

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23969.17766>

Hossain, M. A. (2023aj). *Camouflage textiles against advanced surveillance of defence in UV-Visible-IR spectrums for multidimensional combat backgrounds* (5th Edition of International Conference on Materials Science and Engineering, Accepted on 28 March 2023; Valencia, Spain, Issue. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22550.73282>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844652>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ak). *Camouflage textiles with technical coloration incorporating illumination under multidimensional combat backgrounds, PhD student: 3820066, Second milestone thesis for the degree of doctor of philosophy* [Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2022].

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15701.50403>,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7898707>

Hossain, M. A. (2023al). *Camouflage textiles with technical coloration incorporating illumination, PhD student: 3820066, First milestone thesis for the degree of doctor of philosophy* [Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2021].

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15701.50403>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7898541>

Hossain, M. A. (2023am). *Coloration of polyamide-6,6 fabric with carbon black nano particle for camouflage textiles of simultaneous spectrum probe in visible and near infrared. Advance Research in Textile Engineering, Austin Publishing Group.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36504.98560>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8297554>

Hossain, M. A. (2023an). *Compliance, cost minimization & production support for textile industry.* R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.11452.21127>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8278881>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ao). *Conference Presentation on "Camouflage Engineering and Camouflage Textiles for Defence Technology"; 2023 Philippine Textile Congress, Future Thinking for*

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

Philippine Textiles, Philippine Textile Research Institute (PTRI), Department of Science and Technology-Central Office (DOST-CO), General Santos Avenue Bicutan, Taguig City, Metro Manila, 1631, Philippine; Speaker during the Textile for Human Security and Defense Session (Session 8) of the Congress on 20 November 2023; Accepted.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19380.22407;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117340>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ap). Cr oxide coated woodland camouflage textiles for protection of defense target signature in UV-Visible-IR spectrum opposing of hyperspectral and digital imaging. *Preprint (Version 1) available at Research Square* 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2298847/v1>

Hossain, M. A. (2023aq). "Cut the cost of defence and invest more for education" when Self-studying of a student from primary schooling to PhD schooling is an automatic contribution to national and worldwide development without getting money *Accepted in Scientific Research Publishing.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31778.20161;>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8242777>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ar). *Decision of RMIT University against Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye did a conspiracy to kill Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD candidate, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University supervised by Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang and Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University; Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain faced hidden conspiracy of life threatening and notified to Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor and delegate, RMIT University* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33536.61441;> <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8317924>

Hossain, M. A. (2023as). *Dress code from primary schooling to PhD schooling, harassment, motivation and understanding in an international education platform* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23508.78724/2;>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12747451>

Hossain, M. A. (2023at). *First Action and Support Plan at PhD School during COVID-19 in 2020, Supervised by Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang and Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks.* [http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26567.68006;](http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26567.68006) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7923009>

Hossain, M. A. (2023au). *Invitation of PhD Researchers in international platform for global peace of mankind.* a. f. P. e. a. o. t. w. o. A. Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, engr.anowar@yahoo.com. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19237.88800;>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8268846>

Hossain, M. A. (2023av). *Letter of study leave extension for PhD research works from 1st November 2023 to 31 October 2025, designated for Md. Anowar Hossain, lecturer (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Permanent campus, Dhaka, Bangladesh.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15384.16648;>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13862986>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)*
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)*
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Hossain, M. A. (2023aw). *Md. Anowar Hossain, Anowar's Handbook on Polymer Science & Engineering*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31974.80969>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240852>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ax). Md. Anowar Hossain, Video presentation of Anowar Hossain's PhD invention in PhD School, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia. In. School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21104.43524>.

Hossain, M. A. (2023ay). *My declaration, acknowledgement and dedication to achieve PhD degree (Fashion & Textiles) on "camouflage textiles with technical coloration and incorporating illumination under multidimensional combat backgrounds"* [Textile Engineering, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2021]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18532.65925>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7898850>

Hossain, M. A. (2023az). *My family struggling from my child schooling to PhD schooling; communication and relation with my family/relative peoples for my life-threatening investigation during my PhD schooling at RMIT University in Australia (Part-3)* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19378.38089>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10970344>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ba). *My family struggling from my child schooling to PhD schooling; communication and relation with my maternal family for my life-threatening investigation during my PhD schooling at RMIT University in Australia (Part-1)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16475.13603/1>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10970310>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bb). *My family struggling from my child schooling to PhD schooling; communication and relation with my paternal family for my life-threatening investigation during my PhD schooling at RMIT University in Australia (Part-2)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29896.90887>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10970241>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bc). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-01)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7890974>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bd). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-02)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23241.72807>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7892431>

Hossain, M. A. (2023be). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-03)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.10134.52802>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7913011>

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

- Hossain, M. A. (2023bf). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-04)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27336.08962>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8047201>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bg). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-05)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23045.93929>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8137396>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bh). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-06)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27723.57120>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8146631>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bi). Neuro-Camouflaging is an Indicator of Human Camouflage, an Assumption of Brain Engineering for Self-protection against Criminal Attacking. *Journal of Applied Material Science & Engineering Research*, 7(1), 67-71. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13401.90729>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bj). Neuro-camouflaging is an Indicator of Human Camouflage, an Assumption of Brain Engineering for Self-protection against Criminal Attacking. *PREPRINT (Version 1) available at Research Square*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2710224/v1>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bk). *Non-paid salary of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD ID: 3820066, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University submitted for approval of Professor Dr. Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27962.16328>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10132457>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bl). *An optical platform of material engineering for design of camouflage product against multidimensional combat backgrounds from 400 nm to 2500 nm (Scholars World Congress on Material Science and Nanotechnology” (MatScience 2023), Accepted on 18 April 2023, Issue*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844597>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28176.28165>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bm). *PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21433.34402>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12747607>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bn). *Plaintiff, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, PhD ID: 3820066 is seeking necessary action by the Australian crime commission act (ACC), 2002; 7A, 7C and/or relevant act of criminal investigation in PhD school*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26327.04002>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10116196>

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD⁵ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assis. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assis. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assis. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
---	---	--

Hossain, M. A. (2023a). *Plaintiff, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist; School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, PhD ID: 3820066 is seeking free of cost legal action to high court of Australia and/or fully funded PhD Scholarship for every cost of high court of Australia.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27057.76642>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10182345>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bo). *Power Point Presentation on Camouflage Textiles against advanced surveillance of defence in UV-Vis-IR spectrums for Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds* (5th Edition of International Conference on Materials Science and Engineering, Issue. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8298582>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bp). *Power Point Presentation on Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration Incorporating Illumination under Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds* (School of fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2022, Issue. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8311145>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bq). *Presentation on Camouflage textiles with technical coloration incorporating illumination under multidimensional combat backgrounds, PhD student: 3820066, RMIT University;* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8146048> <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29042.48322>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8146048>

Hossain, M. A. (2023br). *Professional Certificates and Professional achievements of Md. Anowar Hossain.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16572.62089>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16258214>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bs). Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. *Scholarly Community Encyclopedia.* <https://encyclopedia.pub/entry/49098>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bt). Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist. <https://encyclopedia.pub/entry/49098>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34177.43368>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10208384>

Hossain, M. A. (2023b). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Bangladeshi Passport No: EE0444946; Bangladeshi Address: Vill: Purbo Nuthurchar, P.O: K. Mohonpur (Postal Code: 1990) P.S: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh is reporting life-threatening conspiracy to Mr. Jeremy Bruer, Australian High Commissioner to Bangladesh located at 184 Gulshan Avenue, Gulshan, Dhaka, Bangladesh.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28153.24164>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10025287>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bu). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is begging to Mr. António Guterres, the Secretary General of United Nations to stop the conflict between Gaza & Israel.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25967.41129>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10318727>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bv). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is expected for full-time/part-time/contractual/casual positions of professional services all over the world.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13240.32001>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10360586>

- Hossain, M. A. (2023bw). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is seeking legal support to The Hon Anthony Albanese MP, Prime Minister, Australia for the conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in PhD school, RMIT University.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19140.19849>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10990583>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bx). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's invention for the peace in PhD schooling for the peace of mankind for the excellency in higher education, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33291.67366>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12742364>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023c). *Reporting and filing to High Court of Australia for court hearing & court writ of life-threatening conspiracy to kill PhD researcher and artificial killing conspiracy of PhD dream of a PhD scholar in a prestigious platform of PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.20689.30567>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10986579>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023d). *Reporting for psychologist involvement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, delegate of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University as per office order of RMIT University, Australia.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.11792.99846>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8330262>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023e). *Reporting to Honorable Minister, Department of Home Affairs, Australia and delegates for activation and extension of VISA of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Delegate of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University until the final order of Australian Supreme Court, Australian human rights commission and chief authorities of Australian Government relates to PhD harassment and conspiracy of life-threatening of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21520.17927>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11195451>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023by). *Reporting to Tertiary Education Quality & Standards Agency of Australian Government for compliance investigation of unethical PhD suspension, unethical scholarship suspension, psychologist bullying of school administration and cancellation of PhD enrolment of Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD ID: 3820066 under the official act of hidden life threatening and killing conspiracy to kill PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain when few complaint letters against Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye were submitted to the whole concern of RMIT University including Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University; Professor Calum Drummond, Deputy Vice Chancellor, Research and Innovation, RMIT University; Dr. Scott Mayson, Associate dean, Research and Innovation; Dr. Andrea Eckersley, HDR coordinator, School of Fashion & Textiles; Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Senior Supervisor and Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, Associate supervisor, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when PhD candidate contributed for 42 month duration (full time) PhD*

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)*
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)*
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assis. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assis. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assis. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India, Australia, Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.348831>

candidature under nonpaid scholarship of one year duration under Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship. . <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27226.72648>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8260252>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bz). *Reporting to Victorian Ombudsman for compliance investigation of unethical PhD suspension, unethical scholarship suspension, psychologist bullying of school administration and cancellation of PhD enrolment of Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD ID: 3820066 under the official act of hidden life threatening and killing conspiracy to kill PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain when few complaint letters against Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye were submitted to the whole concern of RMIT University including Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University; Professor Calum Drummond, Deputy Vice Chancellor, Research and Innovation, RMIT University; Dr. Scott Mayson, Associate dean, Research and Innovation, RMIT University; Dr. Andrea Eckersley, HDR coordinator, School of Fashion & Textiles; Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Senior Supervisor and Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, Associate supervisor, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when PhD candidate contributed for 42 month duration (full time) PhD candidature under nonpaid scholarship of one year duration under Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship. . <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31999.79522>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8315574>*

Hossain, M. A. (2023ca). *Research and publication output of Md. Anowar Hossain on Textile Engineering under affiliation of City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh, Year 2006-2010 (academic), 2017-2019 (professional). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19275.98087>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8286941>*

Hossain, M. A. (2023cb). *Research and publication output of Md. Anowar Hossain on Textile Engineering under affiliation of University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India, 2013-2015. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12565.09440>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15068327>*

Hossain, M. A. (2023cc). *Self-declared certificate on PhD (Fashion & Textiles). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30457.65123>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10978165>*

Self-declared certificate on Professor (Textile Engineering), (2023cd). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36591.82084>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8275164>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ce). *Self-declared certificate on Scientist (Camouflage Physics) (Australia Patent No. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13103.71848>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8275143>*

Hossain, M. A. (2023f). *Services for crime in higher education & quality enhancement in an international platform. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26551.70569>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8278997>*

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

- Hossain, M. A. (2023g). *Services for crime protection and crime analysis for the peace of mankind in an international platform*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36618.03522>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8279067>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023cf). *A short summery and evidences of Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship for Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD student ID: 3820066, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14593.43368>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12722555>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023cg). Simultaneous Thermoregulated and Sensorial effect of Smart Textiles with Artificial Composite Phase Change Materials (CPCM) incorporated with Carbon Nano Conductive Materials for special workers and extreme weather conditions; Accepted in Advanced Material Research (2019-2020). *School of Fashions and Textiles, RMIT University, Victoria 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8112357>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32289.79204>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ch). *Specialized services and payment rate of Professor (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21820.00643>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10360742>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ci). *Specialized services and payment rate of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist. a. f. P. e. a. o. t. w. o. J. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21820.00643>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10360742>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023cj). Spectral simulation and materials design for camouflage textiles coloration against materials of multidimensional combat backgrounds in visible and near infrared spectrums. *MRS Communications* <https://doi.org/10.1557/s43579-023-00344-3>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ck). UV–Visible–NIR camouflage textiles with natural plant based natural dyes on natural fibre against woodland combat background for defence protection. *Scientific Reports*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-31725-2>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023cl). *Video reporting for removal of executive suspension and reporting to withdraw of executive suspension when Australian schooling compliance was breached for my PhD candidature in PhD school through the official act of hidden life threatening of PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain (Part-01)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33752.88325>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8154453>; <https://youtu.be/86cxLN3Z9ro>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023cm). *Video reporting for removal of executive suspension and reporting to withdraw of executive suspension when Australian schooling compliance was breached for my PhD candidature in PhD school through the official act of hidden life threatening of PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain (Part-02)*.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia),
 Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*}
 Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
 MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)*
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)*
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)
 Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assit. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
 Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
 Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.24105.98403>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8162633>; <https://youtu.be/0WXVkgicfKg>

Hossain, M. A. (2024a). Advancement in UV-Vis-IR camouflage Textiles for concealment of defense surveillance against multidimensional combat background. *Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Engineering*. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40712-024-00182-8>;
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17601.12648>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14282484>

Hossain, M. A. (2024b). *Australian Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist asked 100000 Australian penalty unit to Hon Mark Dreyfus KC MP, Australian Attorney General/law minister of Australian Government*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14776.72967>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10556279>

Hossain, M. A. (2024c). *Coalesced the syllabus and course structures in textile engineering and relevant courses in the eighteen years duration academic and professional journey of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist from 2006 to 2024*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21803.66082>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13888294>

Hossain, M. A. (2024d). *Cyber securities for protection of cyber-crimes*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14367.98729>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10841349>

Hossain, M. A. (2024e). *A follow-up letter to The Hon Jason Clare MP, Education Minister, Australia for the conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in Australian PhD school*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18413.19685>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10964382>

Hossain, M. A. (2024f). *Journal Peer Review Report of PhD Thesis of “Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist” on “Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration Incorporating Illumination under Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds”* School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36270.32328>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13182515>

Hossain, M. A. (2024g). *Letter to Nobel committee for Nobel prize in camouflage physics*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36807.51367>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10842435>

Hossain, M. A. (2024h). *Letter to Nobel Committee for Nobel Prize in Peace*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35129.79208>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10842361>

Hossain, M. A. (2024i). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is searching research fund for surviving in research profession and self-learning*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia.

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22732.42888;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13997939>

Hossain, M. A. (2024j). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is asking to Ms. Nardia Simpson, Australian High Commissioner for approving the extension of Australian Student VISA for legal and ethical claiming to Australian court under the ethical support of Minister of home affairs, foreign affairs and education.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14584.05126;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14699107>

Hossain, M. A. (2024k). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14837268>

Hossain, M. A. (2024l). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking support of 'free of cost google drive (2TB) access' to Pichai Sundararajan, Chief Executive Officer, Google against the e-mail address of engranowar06@gmail.com.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28761.94568;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13994976>

Hossain, M. A. (2024m). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is self-nominating for 'global excellence award' at Functional Textiles and Clothing (FTC), Indian Institute of Technology (IIT), Delhi, India under the category of 'Leadership in Research' and/or 'Emerging Innovator' under the invitation of FTC team, IIT, Delhi, India.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36325.61929;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14213757>

Hossain, M. A. (2024n). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is asking an exemption of visa fees for the 'Australian global talent permanent residence visa (subclass 858)' under the Australian migration act 45C (c), 1958 and 500.211,1994.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25869.14560;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12754106>

Hossain, M. A. (2024o). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is the first inventor of '2100–4200-point policy for the impact factor to certify researcher for PhD degree by Research' and 'PhD in PhD'.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35642.20167;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12604715>

Hossain, M. A. (2024p). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is the first inventor of a 1150–2300-point policy to certify or review a research manuscript or thesis for publication R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.),
Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*}
Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process,
color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)*
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)*
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
Former Assis. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg
& Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assis. Registrar (Exam);
Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assis. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and
Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; engr.anowar@yahoo.com.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30482.88003>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12735576>

Hossain, M. A. (2024q). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is asking 'honorary doctorate degree' to the Vice Chancellor of University of Calcutta for his contribution of PhD harassment at RMIT University.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.20869.15843>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10842021>

Hossain, M. A. (2024r). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is asking 'honorary doctorate degree' to the Vice Chancellor of University of Dhaka for his contribution of PhD harassment at RMIT University.* R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36388.08325>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10841964>

Hossain, M. A. (2024s). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is searching a good-looking lady for his marriage, a requirement of RMIT PhD school.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13112.97282>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12747830>

Hossain, M. A. (2024t). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1100–2200-point policy for the impact factor to admit/appoint researcher position for Master degree by research.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12531.75048>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16628548>

Hossain, M. A. (2024u). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1250–2500-point policy for the impact factor to certify university designation and university promotion from lecturer to professor.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13177.68968>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11183360>

Hossain, M. A. (2024v). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 7050–14100-point policy for the impact factor or ranking of an international standard University.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25604.13447>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10814275>

Hossain, M. A. (2024w). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the inventor of 10-point policy to elect the democratic leaders all over the world.* R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19343.76968>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10662617>

Hossain, M. A. (2024x). *Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection [Biodata].*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15612185>

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.

- Hossain, M. A. (2024y). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist represented his photographic memories of profession in textile engineering and casual life journey.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32669.69609>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10449995>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024z). *Research services, journal peer reviews, and editorial support of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15157.90080>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13142538>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024). *Seeking VISA extension, legal support, legal costs, legal insurance support, accommodation costs, fooding costs, personal safety, PhD compensation award of Australian Government, PhD compensation award of RMIT University, PhD certificate, PhD mark sheets or academic transcript and job offer letter to Australian Home affairs.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34569.04960>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13822693>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024aa). *A self-understanding of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist about Bangladeshi Nobel laureate Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus and law implementation of Bangladesh Government.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26912.35846>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10461097>
- Hossain, M. A. (2025a). *Invitation of law researchers in Master by thesis, PhD by thesis, and Postdoc by thesis.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30060.63369>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16995119>
- Hossain, M. A. (2025b). *Invitation of legal client for legal service to individual and/or organization.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13073.70249>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16990186>
- Hossain, M. A. (2025c). *Invitation of researchers in textile engineering in Master by thesis, PhD by thesis, and Postdoc by thesis.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17215.57765>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16960861>
- Hossain, M. A. (2025d). *Local government in Bangladesh to minimize official crimes in public administration in a democratic country* School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28463.85929>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15826808>
- Hossain, M. A. (2025e). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is self-approaching for the prestigious 'best researcher award' under the provisional nomination of organizing committee, research scientist awards of Indian government [Grant].* School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.).
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia),
 Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*}
 Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
 MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process,
 color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)³
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁴
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
 PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assisit. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg
& Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assisit. Registrar (Exam);
 Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
 Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assisit. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
 Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
 University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and
 Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36413.17128;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15064119>

Hossain, M. A. (2025f). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is self-approaching to enhance higher education and research support in Bangladesh and Australia* School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32735.16801;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15718630>

Hossain, M. A. (2025g). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is requesting to Mr. António Guterres, Secretary-General of United Nations for a legal stipend or legal award to proceed with legal proceeding of life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35976.12805;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14934539>

Hossain, M. A. (2025h). *Textile, Defence, and Law Research Centre.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.24765.32485;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16961335>

Hossain, M. A., & Samanta, A. (2018). Green Dyeing On Cotton Fabric Demodulated From Diospyros Malabarica and Camellia Sinensis with Green Mordanting Agent. *Latest Trends in Textile and Fashion Designing*, 2(2), 1-8.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.32474/LTTFD.2018.02.000132>

Hossain, M. A., Samanta, A., Abser, M. N., & Dilruba, F. A. (2019). A Review on Technological and Natural Dyeing Concepts for Natural Dyeing along with Natural Finishing on Natural Fibre. *International Journal of Textile Science and Engineering*, 3(1), 1-3.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36811.36648;> <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8245079>

Hossain, M. A., & Samanta, A. K. (2019). A cost minimization process of heat and energy consumption for direct dyeing of cotton fabric coloration with triethanolamine. *Journal of Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology*, 5(5), 235-240.

<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/A-cost-minimization-process-of-heat-and-energy-for-Hossain-Samanta/145246a45b40a7ef33c3e37cc99083f91f6555fa;>

<http://dx.doi.org/10.15406/jteft.2019.05.00207>

Nobel Nominee Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, D. S., Barrister (Dr.). (2025). *Journal of Dr. Anowar.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29003.30243;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15550150>

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; a follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 27 September 2025.